

ID	Alphanumeric ID	Additional numbering	Title	Start Date	End Date	Box #	Notes
1	A1		Transit Circle	11/7/1848	7/30/1849	1	
2	A2		Transit Circle	7/30/1849	9/25/1849	1	
3	A3		Transit Circle	9/26/1849	11/29/1849	1*	
4	A4		Transit Circle	11/30/1849	2/6/1850	1	
5	A5		Transit Circle	2/6/1850	4/30/1850	1	
6	A6		Transit Circle	5/1/1850	10/20/1850	1	
7	A7		Transit Circle	10/21/1850	12/26/1850	1	
8	A8		Transit Circle	12/26/1850	4/3/1851	1*	
9	A9		Transit Circle	4/3/1851	7/13/1851	1	
10	A10		Transit Circle	7/13/1851	9/5/1851	1*	
11	A11		Transit Circle	9/5/1851	1/15/1852	1	
12	A12		Transit Circle	1/15/1852	6/28/1852	1	
13	A13		Transit Circle	6/28/1852	12/5/1852	1	
14	A14		Transit Circle	12/1/1852	7/8/1853	1	
15	A15		Transit Circle	7/8/1853	2/26/1854	1	
16	A16		Transit Circle	2/28/1854	8/15/1854	1	
17	A17		Transit Circle	8/15/1854	11/27/1854	1	
18	A18		Transit Circle	11/27/1854	1/25/1855	1	
19	A19		Transit Circle	1/25/1855	5/6/1855	1*	
20	A20		Transit Circle	5/6/1855	7/31/1855	1	
21	A21		Transit Circle	8/1/1855	9/25/1855	1	
22	A22		Transit Circle	9/25/1855	3/27/1856	1	
23	A23		Transit Circle	3/27/1856	6/15/1856	1	
24	A24		Transit Circle	6/16/1856	9/5/1856	1	
25	A25		Transit Circle	9/8/1856	2/9/1857	1	
26	A26		Transit Circle	2/17/1857	9/21/1857	1	
27	A27		Transit Circle	9/21/1857	11/3/1857	1	
28	A28		Transit Circle	11/3/1857	2/10/1858	1	
29	A29		Transit Circle	2/10/1858	7/5/1858	1	
30	A30		Transit Circle	7/5/1858	1/24/1859	1	
31	A31		Transit Circle	1/24/1859	8/17/1859	1	
32	A32		Transit Circle	8/17/1859	1/23/1860	1	
33	A33		Transit Circle	1/23/1860	6/23/1860	1	
34	A34		Transit Circle	6/23/1860	11/29/1860	1	
35	A35		Transit Circle	11/29/1860	3/21/1861	1	
36	A36		Transit Circle	3/21/1861	10/1/1861	1	
37	A37		Transit Circle	10/1/1861	3/28/1862	1	
38	A38		Meridian Circle	3/28/1862	5/7/1862	1	
39	A39		Meridian Circle	5/7/1862	8/6/1862	1	
40	A40		Meridian Circle	8/11/1862	9/25/1862	1	
41	A41		Meridian Circle	9/27/1862	12/8/1862	1	
42	A42		Meridian Circle	12/10/1862	2/16/1863	1	
43	A43		Meridian Circle	2/17/1863	5/25/1863	1	
44	A44		Meridian Circle	5/26/1863	8/14/1863	1	
45	A45		Meridian Circle	8/14/1863	9/22/1863	2	
46	A46		Meridian Circle	9/23/1863	12/2/1863	2	
47	A47		Meridian Circle	12/5/1863	1/11/1864	2	
48	A48		Meridian Circle	1/11/1864	3/3/1864	2	
49	A49		Meridian Circle	3/7/1864	4/9/1864	2	
50	A50		Meridian Circle	4/9/1864	5/19/1864	2	
51	A51		Meridian Circle	5/22/1864	6/6/1864	2	
52	A52		Meridian Circle	6/7/1864	6/19/1864	2	
53	A53		Meridian Circle	6/21/1864	7/5/1864	2	unlabeled
54	A54		Meridian Circle	7/6/1864	7/19/1864	2	
55	A55		Meridian Circle	7/20/1864	9/9/1864	2	
56	A56		Meridian Circle	9/10/1864	10/10/1864	2	
57	A57		Meridian Circle	10/10/1864	11/4/1864	2	
58	A58		Meridian Circle	11/10/1864	11/23/1864	2	
59	A59		Meridian Circle	11/25/1864	12/20/1864	2	
60	A60		Meridian Circle	12/30/1864	1/18/1865	2	
61	A61		Meridian Circle	1/20/1865	2/1/1865	2	
62	A62		Meridian Circle	2/2/1865	2/25/1865	2	
63	A63		Meridian Circle	2/27/1865	4/3/1865	2	
64	A64		Meridian Circle	4/3/1865	4/26/1865	2	

65	A65	Meridian Circle	5/1/1865	6/2/1865	2
66	A66	Meridian Circle	6/3/1865	7/4/1865	2
67	A67	Meridian Circle	7/5/1868	7/18/1865	2
68	A68	Meridian Circle	7/20/1865	8/1/1865	2
69	A69	Meridian Circle	8/2/1865	8/28/1865	2
70	A70	Meridian Circle	8/29/1865	9/15/1865	2
71	A71	Meridian Circle	9/16/1865	9/30/1865	2
72	B1	Reduction of Transits	1/1/1849	8/16/1849	2
73	B2	Reduction of Transits	8/16/1849	12/7/1849	2
74	B3	Reduction of Transits	12/7/1849	4/2/1850	2
75	B4	Reduction of Transits	4/2/1850	10/5/1850	2
76	B5	Reduction of Transits	10/5/1850	12/30/1850	2
77	B6	Reduction of Transits	12/30/1850	4/5/1851	2
78	B7	Reduction of Transits	4/5/1851	7/8/1851	2
79	B8	Reduction of Transits	7/8/1851	9/4/1851	2
80	B9	Reduction of Transits	9/4/1851	11/11/1851	2
81	B10	Reduction of Transits	11/11/1851	2/25/1852	2
82	B11	Reduction of Transits	2/25/1852	7/6/1852	2
83	B12	Reduction of Transits	7/6/1852	11/17/1852	2
84	B13	Reduction of Transits	11/17/1852	5/1/1853	2
85	B14	Reduction of Transits	5/1/1853	11/2/1853	2
86	B15	Reduction of Transits	11/2/1853	4/4/1854	2
87	B16	Reduction of Transits	4/4/1854	8/9/1854	2
88	B17	Reduction of Transits	8/6/1854	11/27/1854	2
89	B18	Reduction of Transits	11/27/1854	1/30/1855	2
90	B19	Reduction of Transits	1/30/1855	5/6/1855	2
91	B20	Reduction of Transits	5/6/1855	8/1/1855	2
92	B21	Reduction of Transits	7/31/1855	9/25/1855	3
93	B22	Reduction of Transits	9/25/1855	3/30/1856	3
94	B23	Reduction of Transits	3/30/1856	6/11/1856	3
95	B24	Reduction of Transits	6/11/1856	8/22/1856	3
96	B25	Reduction of Transits	8/22/1856	11/20/1856	3
97	B26	Reduction of Transits	11/20/1856	4/30/1857	3
98	B27	Reduction of Transits	4/30/1857	10/4/1857	3
99	B28	Reduction of Transits	10/4/1857	11/28/1857	3
100	B29	Reduction of Transits	11/28/1857	2/23/1858	3
101	B30	Reduction of Transits	2/23/1858	6/24/1858	3
102	B31	Reduction of Transits	6/24/1858	11/9/1858	3
103	B32	Reduction of Transits	11/9/1858	6/19/1859	3
104	B33	Reduction of Transits	6/19/1859	10/14/1859	3
105	B34	Reduction of Transits	10/14/1859	3/27/1860	3
106	B35	Reduction of Transits	3/27/1860	11/16/1860	3
107	B36	Reduction of Transits	11/16/1860	1/1/1861	3
108	C1	N + S Meridian Marks and Level Readings	12/5/1849	7/4/1853	3
109	C2	N + S Meridian Marks and Level Readings	7/1853	4/21/1855	3
110	C3	N + S Meridian Marks and Level Readings	4/21/1855	9/8/1856	3
111	C4	N + S Meridian Marks and Level Readings	9/1856	2/24/1859	3
112	C5	N + S Meridian Marks and Level Readings	2/24/1859	3/11/1862	3
113	C8	Instrumental Corrections	12/29/1863	10/1865	3
114	C9	Computed AR of Polar Stars	3/11/1862	8/19/1863	3
115	C10	Computed AR of Polar Stars	8/22/1863	11/14/1864	3
116	C11	Chronograph Record	6/1861	7/1863	3
117	C12	Chronograph Record	7/23/1863	11/4/1864	3
118	C13	Chronograph Record	11/10/1864	9/12/1865	3
119	C14	Chronograph Record	9/13/1865	2/20/1866	3
120	C12[C15]	Misc. time observations			3
121	D1	Minutes of Chronometer Expect.	4/1849	2/1850	3*
122	E1	Meridian Circle	11/7/1859	5/25/1860	3
123	E2	Meridian Circle	5/24/1859	11/3/1859	3
124	E3	Meridian Circle	5/25/1860	11/13/1860	3
125	E4	Declinations	12/20/1862	9/9/1863	3
126	E5	Declinations	9/14/1863	10/17/1864	3
127	E6	New Transit Circle	2/17/1857	5/28/1858	3*
128	E7	Transit Circle	1851	1853	3
129	E8	Transit Circle	8/7/1851	12/4/1851	3

130	F1		Moon Culminations and Transits		12/1845	4/1846	3	(Comets also)
131	F2		Comets and Meridian Transits		4/1846	10/1846	3	(Earthquake 8/25)
132	F3		Comets and Meridian Transits		10/1846	4/16/1847	3	
133	F4		Comets and Meridian Transits		4/24/1847	2/9/1848	3	
134	F5		Comets and Meridian Transits		2/18/1848	8/1/1848	3	
135	F6		Comets and Meridian Transits		8/1/1849	2/27/1850	3	*
138	F7		Meridian and Prime Vertical Observations		11/6/1844	12/12/1844	3	(Early)
137	F8		West Transit		11/5/1851	12/16/1851	3	
138	F9		Prime Vertical		11/18/1854	?	3	
139	F10		Magnetic and Prime Vertical		1858		3	
140	F11		Terrestrial Magnetism		3/25/1858	6/5/1861	3	
141	F12a		Chronograph		6/8/1864	7/21/1864	4	
142	F12b		Prime vertical computation of Latitude		1864		4	
143	F13		Telegraph		7/6/1848	10/28/1848	4	
144	G1		Chronometers		10/6/1851	7/1/1853	4	
145	G2		Chronometers		7/1/1853	4/21/1855	4	annular eclipse 5/26/1954
146	G3		Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks		4/21/1856	1/1/1856	4	
147	G4		Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks		1/1/1856	2/27/1857	4	
148	G5		Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks		2/27/1857	7/2/1856	4	
149	G6		Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks		7/2/1856	7/16/1860	4	
150	G7		Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks		7/16/1860	9/3/1862	4	
151	G8		Sidereal and Mean Time Clocks		9/16/1862	3/2/1866	4	
152	Ga		Railroad Time Commenced		6/29/1854	10/1854	4	
153	Gb		Trials of Pendulums and Chronometers		4/27/1857	2/19/1859	4	
154	Ha	Vol I	517-604		11/1848	2/1849	4	
155	Ha		Equatorial Reductions		6/21/1860	1/22/1861	4	
156	H1	Vol I	1-80 Equatorial		10/1846	7/1847	4	
157	H2	Vol I	Equatorial		7/1847	12/1847	4	
158	H3		Equatorial		12/1847	8/1848	4	
159	H4		Equatorial		11/1847	2/1848	4	
160	H5		Equatorial		2/1848	9/1848	4	
161	H6		Equatorial		5/1848	11/1848	4	
162	H7	Vol II	Equatorial		2/1849	6/1849	4	
163	H8		Equatorial		1/1849	11/1849	4	
164	H10		Equatorial		12/1849	4/1850	4	daguerotyping
165	H11		Equatorial		5/10/1850	9/1/1850	4	
166	H12		Equatorial		9/21/1850	2/25/1851	4	
167	H13		Equatorial		2/25/1851	12/4/1851	4	
168	H14	Vol III	Equatorial		12/4/1851	5/18/1852	4	
169	H15		Equatorial		5/19/1852	10/26/1852	4	
170	H16		Equatorial		10/28/1852	3/10/1853	4	
171	H17		Equatorial		3/10/1853	4/4/1854	4	
172	H18		Equatorial		4/4/1854	6/13/1855	4	
173	H19		Equatorial		6/13/1855	4/1/1856	4	
174	H20		Equatorial		4/1/1856	2/15/1857	4	
175	H21		Equatorial		2/15/1857	5/13/1857	4	
176	H22		Equatorial		5/13/1857	8/23/1857	4	
177	H23		Equatorial		8/23/1857	10/20/1857	4	
178	H24		Equatorial		10/20/1857	12/15/1857	4	
179	H25		Equatorial		12/15/1857	3/18/1858	4	
180	H26		Equatorial		3/18/1858	7/14/1858	4	
181	H27		Equatorial		7/14/1858	9/25/1858	4	
182	H28		Equatorial		9/25/1858	11/11/1858	4	
183	H29		Equatorial		11/11/1858	5/4/1859	5	last obs. Of W.C.B.
184	H30		Equatorial		5/4/1859	10/26/1859	5	
185	H31		Equatorial		10/26/1859	1/31/1860	5	
186	H32		Equatorial		1/31/1860	3/15/1860	5	
187	H33		Equatorial		3/15/1860	3/30/1860	5	
188	H34		Equatorial		3/30/1860	5/2/1860	5	
189	H35		Equatorial		5/2/1860	6/24/1860	5	
190	H36		Equatorial		6/24/1860	7/4/1860	5	
191	H37		Equatorial		7/4/1860	9/26/1860	5	
192	H38		Equatorial		9/26/1860	1/31/1861	5	
193	H39		Equatorial		1/31/1861	4/9/1861	5	
194	H40		Equatorial		4/9/1861	5/3/1861	5	

195	H41	Equatorial	5/3/1861	6/22/1861	5	
196	H42	Equatorial	6/22/1861	7/13/1861	5	
197	H43	Equatorial	7/13/1861	9/16/1861	5	
198	H44	Equatorial	9/16/1861	1/1/1862	5	
199	H45	Equatorial	1/1/1862	4/19/1862	5	
200	H46	Equatorial	4/19/1862	7/6/1862	5	
201	H47	Equatorial	7/6/1862	8/19/1862	5	
202	H48	Equatorial	8/19/1862	12/6/1862	5	
203	H49	Equatorial	12/6/1862	4/13/1863	5	
204	H50	Equatorial	4/13/1863	6/10/1863	5	
205	H51	Equatorial	6/10/1863	10/5/1863	5	
206	H52	Equatorial	10/5/1863	2/19/1864	5	
207	H53	Equatorial	2/19/1864	3/21/1864	5	
208	H54	Equatorial	3/21/1864	6/1864	5	
209	H55	Equatorial	6/1864	4/3/1865	5	
210	H56	Equatorial	4/3/1865	2/5/1866	5	see 284 for more
211	K1	Zones 1-7	4/7/1852	5/4/1852	5	
212	K2	Zones 7-13	5/4/1852	11/4/1852	5	
213	K3	Zones 14-19, Bessel	11/4/1852	12/15/1852	5	
214	K4	Zones 20-26	12/15/1852	1/11/1853	5	
215	K5	Zones 27-33	1/11/1853	2/12/1853	5	
216	K6	Zones 34-39	2/12/1853	3/16/1853	5	
217	K7	Zones 40-45	3/16/1853	4/8/1853	5	
218	K8	Zones 46-54	4/8/1853	12/8/1854	5	
219	K9	Zones 55-62	5/31/1853	9/27/1854	5	
220	K10	Zones 65-84a	9/27/1854	12/8/1854	5	
221	K11	Zones 84a-88	12/8/1854	2/12/1855	5	
222	K12	Zones 89-100	2/12/1855	4/23/1855	5	
223	K13	Zones 101-116	4/23/1855	7/17/1855	5	
224	K14	Zones 1-6	3/30/1859	5/3/1859	5	
225	K15	Zones 6-7	5/3/1859	5/23/1859	5	
226	K16	Zones 117-124	5/23/1859	8/29/1859	6	
227	K17	Zones 125-135	8/29/1859	11/26/1859	6	
228	K18	Zones 134-146	11/26/1859	2/21/1860	6	
229	K19	Zones 147-149	2/21/1860	11/20/1860	6	catalog #s
230	K20	Zones	11/20/1860	2/26/1860	6	
231	K21	Zones	2/26/1860	4/8/1861	6	
232	K22	Zones	4/8/1861	7/11/1861	6	
233	K23	Zones	7/11/1861	9/24/1861	6	
234	K24	Zones	9/24/1861	10/22/1862	6	
235	K25	Zones	10/22/1862	2/18/1863	6	
236	K26	Zones	2/18/1863	6/23/1864	6	
237	K27	Zones	6/23/1864	9/27/1864	6	
238	L1	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853		6	explanation
239	K28	Zones	10/5/1864	12/1/1864	6	
240	L2	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853		6	
241	L3	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853		6	
242	L4	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853		6	
243	L5	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853		6	
244	L6	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853		6	
245	L7	Reduction of Zone Observations			6	
246	L8	Reduction of Zone Observations			6	
247	L9	Comparisons of Zones			6	
248	L10	Reductions of Zones No Reductions	1859		6	
249	L11	Reductions of Zones Comparison of Magnitudes	1859		6	
250	L12	Special Zones and Magnitudes			6	
251	L13	Revision of Zones Magnitudes			6	
252	M2	Reduction of Zones I			6	
253	M3	Gould's Universal Index			6	
254	M5	[Tables, Procedures]			6	
255	M6	Table of Contents of various books containing records of observations	1841-1855		6	
256	M7	Various memoranda [Longitude determination, mag. Measure, etc.]	1844-55		6	
257	M9	Catalog Stars	1854-58		6	
258	M10	Tables for apportioning Instrumental Corrections	1855		6	
259	M11	Catalogue of Stars for Zones	1853		6	

260	M12	Reduction of Stars in Weisse(?) from 0 to 1	1853		7
261	M13	Printing of Zone Obs'ns & History and Description of the Obs.	1854		7
262	M14	Lists of persons and Institution recipients of H. Annals			7
263	M15	Meteorological	1/1/1861	5/1863	7
264	M16	1859-60 Comet Sukev	12/1/1859	9/11/1860	7
265	M17	Colorado Survey - Time	12/13/1857	5/23/1858	7
266	M18	Colorado Survey - Latitude by Polaris	12/13/1857	5/23/1858	7
267	M19	[Solar Observations]	01/08/55	5/2/1850	7
268	M20	[Catalog of Bright Nebulae and Clusters]	6/16/1850	5/1853	7
269	M21	[Comet Seeking]	6/10/1847	6/5/1850	7
270	M23	Books received at the Obs. Of Harv. Coll.	1862-67		7
271	M24	Reductions of Moon Culminations	1/1849	5/28/1852	7
272	M25	Reductions of Moon Culminations	7/1851	10/2/1854	7
273	M26	P.S.N [drawings of star config'n and angles]	6/16/1856	7/4/1856	7
274	M27	P.S.N [drawings of star config'n and angles]	11/15/1850	8/22/1851	7
275	M28	Goulds Universal Index			7
276	M29	Printing			7
277	M30	Memoranda for Obs. Report	1/7/1861	12/31/1864	7
278	M31	Memoranda	1/3/1862	1/2/1865	7
279	M32	Catalog of Books in the Phillips Library, commenced	10/9/1856		7
280	M33	Chronometer - Stars	1862-5		7
281	M34	Transit Catalog			7
282	M35	Eclipse of 4/25/1864 - Portland			7
283	M36	Account of Various Records and Papers belonging to the Obs	1866		7
284	N1	Equatorial	6/9/1866	7/9/1866	7
285	N2	Equatorial	7/9/1866	7/24/1866	7
286	N3	Equatorial	7/24/1866	8/13/1866	7
287	N4	Equatorial	8/13/1866	8/26/1866	7
288	N5	Equatorial	8/26/1866	9/12/1866	7
289	N6	Equatorial	9/12/1866	10/2/1866	7
290	N7	Equatorial	10/2/1866	10/22/1866	7
291	N8	Equatorial	10/22/1866	1/23/1867	7
292	N9	Equatorial	1/23/1867	4/25/1867	7
293	N10	Equatorial	4/25/1867	10/25/1867	7
294	N11	Equatorial	10/25/1867	1/27/1868	7
295	N12	Equatorial	1/27/1868	4/1/1868	7
296	N13	Equatorial	4/1/1868	10/10/1868	8
297	N14	Equatorial	10/10/1868	12/22/1868	8
298	N15	Equatorial	12/22/1868	4/28/1869	8
299	N16	Equatorial	4/28/1869	10/14/1869	8
300	N17	Equatorial	10/14/1869	10/31/1871	8
301	N18	Equatorial Misc. Observations	10/31/1871	12/24/1869	8
302	N19	Equatorial Misc. Observations	12/24/1869	12/8/1874	8
303	N20	Equatorial Misc. Observations	12/8/1874	7/13/1870	8
304	N21	Asteroids	7/13/1870	2/13/1871	8
305	N22	Asteroids	2/13/1871	8/10/1871	8
306	N23	Asteroids (W.A. Rogers)			8
307	N24	Asteroids			8
308	N25	Reduction of Asteroid Obsns	1870		8
309	N26	Reduction of Asteroid Obsns	1870-71		8
310	N27	Reduction of aff flare to some stars used in 1870			8
311	N28	Reduction of aff flare to some stars used in 1870			8
312	N29	Reduction of Asteroid Obsns	1870		8
313	N30	Search for Asteroids	1870		8
314	N31	Equatorial - obsns of asteroids and comets			8
315	N32	computation of app flare, differ refract, equatorial comps	6/30/1866	4/26/1866	8
316	N33	Reduction of Equatorial Obsns	10/15/1866	8/26/1866	8
317	N34	Equatorial (copy)	4/9/1866	8/26/1866	8
318	N35	Equatorial (copy)	8/27/1866	10/21/1866	8
319	N36	Equatorial (copy)	10/21/1866	1/14/1867	8
320	N37	Equatorial (copy)	1/14/1867	4/26/1867	8
321	N38	Equatorial (copy)	4/26/1867	10/22/1867	8
322	N39	Equatorial (copy)	10/22/1867	2/3/1868	8
323	N40	Equatorial (copy)	2/3/1868	6/28/1868	8
324	N41	Catalog of Nebulae			8

325	N42	Measurement of photog's of eclipse	1869-70		8	
326	N43	Measurement of photog's of solar eclipse	1870		8	
327	N44	Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot	10/30/1870	4/14/1873	8	
328	N45	Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot	4/14/1873	9/30/1874	8	
329	N46	Solar Photography	7/4/1870	11/30/1876	8	
329a	N48	General Record of Work	1869-1872			
330	N50	Tables, etc.	1866-67		8	
331	N51	Reduced Measures of Double Stars - Equatorial	1866-67		8	
332	O1	East Transit Observations	5/1/1866	9/4/1866	8	
333	O2	East Transit Observations	9/4/1866	5/31/1867	8	
334	O3	East Transit Observations	5/31/1867	11/9/1867	8	
335	O4	East Transit Observations	11/9/1867	7/16/1868	9	
336	O5	East Transit Observations	7/16/1868	10/3/1868	9	
337	O6	East Transit Observations (time)	10/3/1868	8/29/1869	9	
338	O7	East Transit Observations (time)	8/29/1869	6/12/1870	9	
339	O8	East Transit Observations (Occultations)	6/12/1870	12/1/1871	9	
340	O9	East Transit Observations (time)	12/1/1871	12/27/1871	9	
341	O10	Chronograph Record	4/2/1866	7/29/1869	9	
342	O11	East Transit (errors)	4/17/1866	9/17/1867	9	
343	O12	Longitude Campaign: Cambridge - Washington	1867		9	
344	O13	Transit Observations	6/28/1867	6/29/1867	9	
345	O14	Formulae for Reduction of Transit Observations and Tables	1867		9	
346	O15	Chronograph Record	7/31/1867	12/19/1867	9	
347	O16	Chronograph Record	12/19/1867	8/4/1868	9	
348	O17	Chronograph Record	8/4/1868	8/13/1869	9	
349	O18	Chronograph Record	8/13/1869	7/7/1870	9	
350	O19	Record of Errors of Clocks	1866-69		9	
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359	O27	Notes on Astron Engravings. Spanish Weather Record, Phillips Fund			9	
360	O28	Eclipse of 1869, Reports			9	beautiful volume
361	O29	Personal equation observations	1871		9	
362	P1	Magnetic Observations	8/16/1866	2/17/1868	9	
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370	P9	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1872		10	
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372	P11	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1874		10	
373	P12	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1875		10	
374	P13	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1876		10	
375	P14	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1877		10	
376	P15	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1878		10	
377	P16	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1879		10	
378	Q1	Meteorological Record of HCO	1866, 1867, 1868		10	
379	Q2	Meteorological Record of HCO	1869		10	
380	Q3	Meteorological Record of HCO	1870, 1871		10	
381	Q4	Meteorological Record of HCO	1872-77		10	
382	Q5	Meteorological Record of HCO	1878-79		10	
383		Mr. J.G. Homer's Original Minutes of Chronometer Expedition	1857		10	
384		A A of the White Mts. Of New Hampshire	1853		10	N.B. Annular eclipse
385		[Paris to Cambridge Telegraph]	1861		10	
386		U.S. Coast Survey, Benj. Pierce, Subplot: Letter Book and Abstract - Long Party	1868		10	
387		Observations and Longitude Computations	1872		10	U.S. Coast Survey
388		Longitude and Latitude no. 1 (Bolivia)	1892-93		10	

389		Time Service		4/18/1880	4/19/1881	10	
390		Meridian Circle Record - Mr Austin		8/16/1870	5/13/1871	10	
391	Vol 1	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		3/6/1872	3/22/1872	10	
392	Vol 2	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		3/22/1872	6/6/1872	10	
393	Vol 3	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		6/6/1872	7/2/1872	10	
394	Vol 4	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		5/4/1872	5/31/1872	10	
395	Vol 5	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		5/31/1872	6/10/1872	10	
396	Vol 6	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		6/10/1872	6/30/1872	10	
397	Vol 7	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		6/30/1872	7/30/1872	10	
398	Vol 8	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		7/30/1872	8/9/1872	10	
399	Vol 9	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		8/9/1872	8/18/1872	10	
400	Vol 10	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		8/18/1872	3/9/1873	11	
401	Vol 11	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		3/9/1873	6/8/1873	11	
402	Vol 12	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		6/8/1873	9/6/1873	11	
403	Vol 13	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		9/6/1873	9/22/1873	11	
404	Vol 14	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		9/22/1873	9/30/1873	11	
405	Vol 15	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		9/30/1873	10/11/1873	11	
406	Vol 16	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		10/11/1873	4/13/1874	11	
407	Vol 18	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		4/13/1874	5/20/1874	11	
408	Vol 19	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		5/20/1874	7/17/1874	11	
409	Vol 20	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		7/17/1874	8/3/1874	11	
410	Vol 21	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		8/3/1874	8/22/1874	11	
411	Vol 22	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		8/22/1874	11/26/1874	11	
412	Vol 23	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		11/26/1874	12/21/1874	11	
413	Vol 24	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		12/21/1874	1/14/1875	11	
414	Vol 25	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Pierce		5/28/1872		11	
415	[paper folder]	Index to books on Meridian Circle Work		1870-1886		11	
416		Fundamental Stars for Zones		3/17/1873	12/1/1873	11	
417		General Catalog Obsns and Reductions		1871-72		11	
418		Fundamental Star Obsns and Reductions, Final Values		1870-71		11	
419		Mars, Mars Companion Stars, ARIADNE Comp. Stars		1877		11	
420		Flexure Constants, Equator Point Corrections		1874-75		11	
421		Instrumental Constants 1870-71, depending on new Pulkowa Places				11	
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424		Obsns w/ Meridian Circle on Zones 50 to 55		11/16/1870	12/16/1870	11	
425		Obsns w/ Meridian Circle on Zones 50 to 55		12/16/1870	3/28/1871	11	
426		Misc. Tables Formulae for Zone Reductions		1870-71		11	
427		Misc. Obsns Transit of Vanus Longitude Montreal - Cambridge		1883-87		11	
428		Obsns of Tempel's Comet 1873, Asteroids 1873, Periodicity of Ruling Machine Screw				11	
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431		Orbit of 109 and 112		1871-74		11	
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433		Planetary Positions (Heliocentric)		1750-1860		11	
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435		Chronograph Record		5/27/1880	10/5/1880	11	
436		Absolute work Star List - Final list of dates of obsns		1879-81		11	John A. Dunne
437		Absolute work Meridian Circle Obsns		1879-81		12	Anna Winlock
438		Absolute Work Notebook		1898-1907		12	Selina C. Bo??
439		Posting Book		1897-1908		12	
440		Roger's Absolute work notebook		1904-1911		12	John A. Dunne
441		Special Light Curves with Photometer		1895-96		12	
442		Variable Stars		1897		12	
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449	IV	Obsns of Variable Stars		1892		12	Maxwell Reed
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454	IX	Obsns of Variable Stars	1898-1900		12	Maxwell Reed
455		Obsns of Variable Stars	1900		12	Maxwell Reed
456		Notebook of Visual Observations	189-1902		12	H.R. Colson, Jr.
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506		Comets (10)	1890		15	
507		Comets (9)	1889-90		15	
508		Journal (Construction of Dome, etc.)	1889-91		15	R.W. Clifford
509			1890		15	
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511		Gigenschein & Zodiacal Light Obsn's	1891-92		15	
512		Comets	1891-92		15	
513		Journal (Arequipa)	1891-94		15	Andrew E. Douglas
514			1892		15	
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526		Variable Stars	1894-95	16	William B Clymer
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538		Telescope Mechanical Notes and Golf Scores	1897-1911	16	Charles P. Howard
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541		Variable Stars	1899	16	
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544			1900-1901	16	A.J. Carron
545			1901	17	
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547		Notebook #2	1902-05	17	H.R. Colson
548			1901-05	17	
549			1901	17	
550			1901	17	
551			1901	17	
552			1901-2	17	
553			1902	17	
554			1902	17	
555			1902	17	
556			1902	17	
557			1902	17	
558			1902-3	17	
559			1903	17	
560			1903	17	
561			1903	17	
562			1903	17	
563			1903	17	
564			1903	17	
565			1903-4	18	
566			1904	18	
567			1904	18	
568			1904	18	
569			1904	18	
570			1904	18	
571			1904	18	
572			1904-5	18	
573			1905	18	
574			1905	18	
575			1905	18	
576			1905	18	
577			1905-6	18	
578			1906	18	
579			1906	18	
580			1906	18	
581			1906	18	
582			1906-7	18	
583			1907	18	

584			1907	18
585			1907	18
586			1907	19
587			1907-8	19
588			1908	19
589			1908	19
590			1908	19
591			1908	19
592			1908	19
593			1908-9	19
594			1909	19
595			1909	19
596			1909	19
597			1909	19
598			1909	19
599			1909-10	19
600			1910	19
601			1910	19
602			1910	19
603			1910-11	19
604			1911	19
605			1911	19
606			1911	19
607			1911-12	19
608			1912	20
609			1912	20
610			1912	20
611		15° Record	1912-13	20
612			1912-15	20
613			1915-16	20
614			1916	20
615			1916	20
616			1916	20
617			1916	20
618			1916-17	20
619			1917	20
620			1917	20
621		15° Equatorial	1917	20
622		15° Equatorial	1917	20
623		15° Equatorial	1917-18	20
624		15° Equatorial	1918	20
625		15° Equatorial	1918	20
626		15° Equatorial	1918-19	20
627		15° Equatorial	1919-20	20
628		15° Equatorial	1920-23	21
629		15° Equatorial	1926-27	21
630		15° Equatorial	1928-30	21
631		15° Equatorial	1934-35	21
632		15° Equatorial	1935-36	21
633		15° Equatorial	1936	21
634		15° Equatorial	1936	21
635		15° Equatorial	1936-39	21
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637		12° Equatorial	1914	21
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642		[Box of Papers] II Meteors (Leonids)	1898-99	21
643		12° Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1919-20	22
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648		12° Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1921	22

649		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1921-22	22	
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651		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1922	22	
652		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1922-23	22	
653		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1923	22	
654		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1923	22	
655		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1923-24	22	
656		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1924	22	
657		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1924-25	22	
658		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1925	22	
659		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1925-26	22	
660		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1925-26	22	
661		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1926-27	22	
662		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1927	22	
663		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1927-28	23	
664		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1928-29	23	
665		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1928-33	23	
666		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1934-35	23	
667		12" Equatorial - Variable Star Observations	1935-36	23	
668		[24" Clark Refractor]	1905-06	23	Leon Campbell?
669		[24" Clark Refractor]	1907	23	Leon Campbell?
670		[24" Clark Refractor]	1907-08	23	Leon Campbell?
671		[24" Clark Refractor]	1908-09	23	Leon Campbell?
672		[24" Clark Refractor]	1909	23	Leon Campbell?
673		[24" Clark Refractor]	1909	23	Leon Campbell?
674		[24" Clark Refractor]	1909-10	23	Leon Campbell?
675		[24" Clark Refractor]	1910-11	23	Leon Campbell?
676		Photometric Observations		23	C.S. Pierce
677		Photometric Observations	1872	23	C.S. Pierce
678		Photometric Observations	1872	23	C.S. Pierce
679		Photometric Observations	1873	23	C.S. Pierce
680		Photometric Observations	1873	23	C.S. Pierce
681		Photometric Observations	1874	23	C.S. Pierce
682		Photometric Observations	1874	23	C.S. Pierce
683		Photometric Observations	1874-75	23	C.S. Pierce
684		Experiments with Photometer	1872	23	C.S. Pierce
685		eta Centauri Spectral Study	1911	23	Leah B. Allen
686		Clusters - spectrophotometric tracings	1930	23	Carol Jane Anger
687		alpha Cyg, Vega - spectrophotometric tracings	1930-36?	23	Carol Jane Anger
688		alpha Cyg, Vega - spectrophotometric tracings	1930-36?	23	Carol Jane Anger
689		eta Per, NGC 663 - spectrophotometric tracings		24	Carol Jane Anger
690		Clusters - spectrophotometric tracings	c.1932	24	Carol Jane Anger
691		Clusters - spectrophotometric tracings	1934	24	Carol Jane Anger
692		Misc; Variables	1918-19	24	Mary D. Applegate
693		Variables, Map of the Sky	1918-19	24	Mary D. Applegate
694		Map of the Sky, Sequences for Orion Nebula	1919	24	Mary D. Applegate
695		Asteroids and Novae	1919-20	24	Mary D. Applegate
696		Novae and Variables	1920-21	24	Mary D. Applegate
697		Map of the Sky	1920-21	24	Mary D. Applegate
698		Daily Journal (13" - Peru)	1889-90	24	S.I. Bailey
699		Double Stars; Planets (13" - Peru)	1864-96	24	S.I. Bailey
700		Misc.; Variables	1917-19	24	Dorothy W. Block
701		Spectrum Work	1917-19	24	Dorothy W. Block
702		omicron Ceti, Nova Aql 3	1917-19	24	Dorothy W. Block
703		Variables	1918-19	24	Dorothy W. Block
704		Asteroids	1918-19	24	Dorothy W. Block
705		Variables	1919	24	Dorothy W. Block
706		Variable Stars and Meteors	1903	24	F.E. Brasch
707		Variable Stars	1896-98	24	S.E. Breslin
708		Variable Stars	1898	24	S.E. Breslin
709		Variable Stars	1898	25	S.E. Breslin
710		Variable Stars	1899	25	S.E. Breslin
711		Variable Stars	1901-02	25	S.E. Breslin
712		Variable Stars	1902	25	S.E. Breslin
713		Variable Stars	1902-03	25	S.E. Breslin

714		Variable Stars	1903	25	S.E. Breslin
715		Variable Stars	1903	25	S.E. Breslin
716		Variable Stars	1903	25	S.E. Breslin
717		Variable Stars	1903	25	S.E. Breslin
718		Variable Stars	1903-04	25	S.E. Breslin
719		Variable Stars	1904	25	S.E. Breslin
720		Variable Stars	1904	25	S.E. Breslin
721		Variable Stars	1904	25	S.E. Breslin
722		Variable Stars	1904	25	S.E. Breslin
723		Variable Stars	1904	25	S.E. Breslin
724		Variable Stars	1904-05	25	S.E. Breslin
725		Variable Stars	1905	25	S.E. Breslin
726		Variable Stars	1905	25	S.E. Breslin
727		Variable Stars	1905-06	25	S.E. Breslin
728		Variable Stars	1906	25	S.E. Breslin
729		Variable Stars	1906	26	S.E. Breslin
730		Variable Stars	1906	26	S.E. Breslin
731		Variable Stars	1906	26	S.E. Breslin
732		Variable Stars	1906	26	S.E. Breslin
733		Variable Stars	1907	26	S.E. Breslin
734		Variable Stars	1907	26	S.E. Breslin
735		Variable Stars	1907	26	S.E. Breslin
736		Variable Stars	1907-08	26	S.E. Breslin
737		Variable Stars	1908	26	S.E. Breslin
738		Variable Stars	1908	26	S.E. Breslin
739		Variable Stars	1909	26	S.E. Breslin
740		Variable Stars	1909-10	26	S.E. Breslin
741		Variable Stars	1910-11	26	S.E. Breslin
742		Mag. Estimates	1903	26	S.E. Breslin
743		Comparison Stars for Variables	1922	26	L.A. Brigham
744		Variable Stars	1919	26	G.R. Brooks
745		Variable Stars	1901-02	26	Leon Campbell
746		Variable Stars	1902-03	26	Leon Campbell
747		Variable Stars	1903	26	Leon Campbell
748		Variable Stars	1903-04	26	Leon Campbell
749		Variable Stars	1904	27	Leon Campbell
750		Variable Stars	1904-05	27	Leon Campbell
751		Variable Stars	1905-07	27	Leon Campbell
752		Variable Stars	1907-08	27	Leon Campbell
753		Variable Stars	1908-09	27	Leon Campbell
754		Variable Stars	1909-11	27	Leon Campbell
755		Observations w/ Phot. X on 5"	1903-06	27	Leon Campbell
756		Observations w/ Phot. X on 5"	1903-05	27	Leon Campbell
757		Observations w/ Phot. X on 5"	1905	27	Leon Campbell
758			1906-07	27	Leon Campbell
759		Photometric Observations	1915	27	Leon Campbell
760		6" (west) Equatorial	1917-24	27	Leon Campbell
761		Memoranda on Variable Stars	1904-05	27	Leon Campbell
762		8" Polar Telescope	1908-09	27	Leon Campbell
763		8" Polar Telescope	1909-11	27	Leon Campbell
764		Variable Star Observations	1911-12	27	Leon Campbell
765		Variable Star Observations	1912-14	27	Leon Campbell
766		S 18 17	1911-12	27	Leon Campbell
767		Photometric Records	1913-15	27	
768		Variable Star Observations	1914-15	28	Leon Campbell
769		Log Book - Arequipa Station of HCO	1915	28	
770		P #17	1913	28	
771		Pyrheliometer 17 Observation	1914	28	
772		Estimate of Work (Arequipa)	1911	28	
773		Long Period Southern Variables	1910	28	
774		Variables	1907-09	28	E.S. Manson, H.E. Blackett, K. L.
775		Long Period Southern Variables	1904-08	28	
776		Long Period Southern Variables	1918	28	
777		Nova Aquilae No. 3	1918	28	Leon Campbell
779		Variable Star Observations	1900-01	28	Leon Campbell

780		Visual Observations	1901-02	28	
781		Visual Observations	1902-03	28	
782		Visual Observations	1903-04	28	
783		Visual Observations	1904	28	
784		Visual Observations	1904-05	28	
785		Visual Observations	1905-09	28	
786		Visual Observations	1906-07	28	
787		Visual Observations	1907-09	28	Annie J. Cannon
788		Notes for Reading	1911-39	28	Annie J. Cannon
789		Guest Book	1912-35	28	Annie J. Cannon
790		Variable Stars, Longitude Determination	1862-82	29	Seth C. Chandler
791				29	Seth C. Chandler
792		W. Virginis I	1916	29	C.A. Chant
793		lambda of Sp. Lines in red region of stars	1926-27	29	CT Chase
794		Spectra of Novae	1926	29	Paul Daidovich
795				29	
796		Journal - Lat. And Long. Work	1896	29	Andrew E. Douglas
797		Radiometric Nook I	1937-38	29	
798		Radiometry II	1939-40	29	EM Berson
799		Radiometry Program Book I	1936-38	29	EM Berson
800		Galvanometry Book I	1937-38	29	
801		Variable Stars	1890-92	29	W.P. Fleming
802		Variable Stars	1892-94	29	W.P. Fleming
803		Variable Stars; Spectra	1892-94	29	W.P. Fleming
804		Variable Stars	1893-98	29	W.P. Fleming
805		Variable Stars	1894-95	29	W.P. Fleming
806		Variable Stars; Spectra	1895-99	29	W.P. Fleming
807		Variable Stars	1895-96	29	W.P. Fleming
808		Variable Stars	1896	29	W.P. Fleming
809		Variable Stars	1896-97	29	W.P. Fleming
810		Variable Stars	1897-98	30	W.P. Fleming
811		Variable Stars	1897-1902	30	W.P. Fleming
812		Variable Stars	1898-1903	30	W.P. Fleming
813		Variable Stars	1898-1905	30	W.P. Fleming
814		Variable Stars	1899-1905	30	W.P. Fleming
815		Variable Stars; Comp. Spectra	1903-07	30	W.P. Fleming
816		Variable Stars; Comp. Spectra	1903-10	30	W.P. Fleming
817		Variable Stars; Photometer	1905-08	30	W.P. Fleming
818		Novae, Comets, Spectra	1906-11	30	W.P. Fleming
819		Sp. Class; Misc. Obsns	1908-11	30	W.P. Fleming
820		Ledger of LPV's 000339-095659		30	W.P. Fleming
821		Ledger of LPV's 100661-185905		30	W.P. Fleming
822		Ledger of LPV's 190048-235939		30	W.P. Fleming
823		Clusters and Faint Stars	1904-11	30	W.P. Fleming
824		Nova Persei Reductions	1902	30	W.P. Fleming
825		Variable Stars		30	W.P. Fleming
826		Measurements of Bright Line Spectra	1890	30	W.P. Fleming
827		Reductions of Photographic Observations		30	W.P. Fleming
828		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1886-87	30	W.P. Fleming
829		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1886	30	W.P. Fleming
830		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1886	31	W.P. Fleming
831		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1886-87	31	W.P. Fleming
832		Reductions of Photographic Observations		31	W.P. Fleming
833		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1886-87	31	W.P. Fleming
834		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1886-87	31	W.P. Fleming
835		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
836		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
837		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
838		Reductions of Photographic Observations		31	W.P. Fleming
839		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
840		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
841		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
842		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887-88	31	W.P. Fleming
843		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887	31	W.P. Fleming
844		Reductions of Photographic Observations	1887-89	31	W.P. Fleming

845		Reductions of Photographic Observations			31	W.P. Fleming
846		Catalog of E Stars			31	W.P. Fleming
847		Description of Spectra		1887-88	31	W.P. Fleming
848		Description of Spectra		1887-89	31	W.P. Fleming
849		Catalog of E Stars			32	W.P. Fleming
850		Catalog of E Stars			32	W.P. Fleming
851		Discordant Spectra; Remarks on Rejected Measures			32	W.P. Fleming
852		G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
853		E Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
854		Description of Spectra			32	W.P. Fleming
855		G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
856		Description of Spectra			32	W.P. Fleming
857		C Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
858		Catalog of I Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
859		Reductions of Photographic Observations			32	W.P. Fleming
860		F + G Discordant Spectra			32	W.P. Fleming
861		Reductions of Photographic Observations			32	W.P. Fleming
862		Catalog of Plates Classes N, H, L; Peruvian Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
863		Catalog of Plates Classes C, D; Peruvian Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
864		Objects of Interest on Spectrum Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
865		Objects of Interest on Spectrum Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
866		Objects of Interest on So. Bache Plates			32	W.P. Fleming
867		Miscellaneous (Ecl, Solar, Etc)			32	W.P. Fleming
868		Discussion of Draper Catalog			32	W.P. Fleming
869		Measurement of Spectrum Plates			33	W.P. Fleming
870		Description of Spectrum Measures			33	W.P. Fleming
871		Discussion of Draper Catalog			33	W.P. Fleming
872		Discussion of Draper Catalog			33	W.P. Fleming
873		Catalog of Chart Plates (I - 8")			33	W.P. Fleming
874		Catalog of Chart Plates (I - 8")			33	W.P. Fleming
875		Catalog of Chart Plates (B in Peru)			33	W.P. Fleming
876			1892		33	W.P. Fleming
877		1892-93			33	W.P. Fleming
878			1893		33	W.P. Fleming
879			1893		33	W.P. Fleming
880			1893		33	W.P. Fleming
881			1893		33	W.P. Fleming
882			1893		33	W.P. Fleming
883		1893-94			33	W.P. Fleming
884		1894-1903			33	W.P. Fleming
885		Description of Spectra Measures So. Draper Cat.			33	W.P. Fleming
886		Spectra Class C			33	W.P. Fleming
887		Description of Spectra Measures So. Draper Cat.		1894-1904	33	W.P. Fleming
888	1	Spectra to be confirmed in Cat of III Stars			33	W.P. Fleming
889	2	Spectra to be confirmed in Cat of III Stars			34	W.P. Fleming
890		Stellar Parallax Stars (13")			34	W.P. Fleming
891	3	Spectra to be confirmed in Cat of III Stars			34	W.P. Fleming
892		Constraints in South Draper Catalog			34	W.P. Fleming
893		Reduction of Plates having less than 4 Std. Stars			34	W.P. Fleming
894		Notes on Draper Cat; Accounts of Share-Holders of the Camera		5/1892	34	W.P. Fleming
895		Measures of Spect. Plates (South Draper Catalog)		1903-04	34	W.P. Fleming
896		Measures of Spect. Plates (South Draper Catalog)		1903	34	W.P. Fleming
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898		Objects of Interest - Bruce Spectrum Plates		1896-1909	34	W.P. Fleming
899		Objects of Interest - northern		1898-1911	34	W.P. Fleming
900		Objects of Interest - So. Bache Plates		1907-1911	34	W.P. Fleming
901	1	Variables and Halley's Comet			34	W.S. Franks
902		Colors of 2149 Southern Stars			34	W.S. Franks
903	1	Variables			34	BPG
904	2	Variables		1912-29	34	BPG
905	3	Variables		1900-20	34	BPG
906	4	Variables		1899-1927	34	BPG
907	5	Spectrophotometry of B + O Stars			34	BPG
908	6	New Variables		1899-1919	34	BPG
909	7	Color Indices of Long Period Variables			35	BPG

910	8	Spectrophotometry of B and Wolf-Rayet Stars			35	BPG
911	9	Variable Stars	1900-27		35	BPG
912		B Star Observations	1902		35	Maude E. Harriman
913		MC Plates taken for Standard magnitude	1908		35	Maude E. Harriman
914		Measurement of Variable Stars	1908		35	Margaret Harwood
915		Measurement widths of A + B stars	1922		35	Marian A. Hawes
916	4	Assorted Plate Measurements	1912-18		35	Marian A. Hawes
917		5° Equatorial	1918		35	Marian A. Hawes
918	1	Variable Stars	1904-06		35	Anson S. Leary, Guy Hill
919		Variable Star Observations	1889-1916		35	E.H?
920		Color correction for tel. objectives	1878		35	Charles P. Howard
921		Assorted Plate Measurements			35	L. Hofrager
922		Assorted Plate Measurements	1928-30		35	L. Hofrager
923	1	Measurements of Plates, Stars, etc.	1895-98		35	Edward S. King
924	2	Reductions of Measures	1899		35	Edward S. King
925	3	Notes: Photographic Instruments	1904-24		35	Edward S. King
926	3	Measurements: Distances, Altitudes, Plates	1901-02		35	Edward S. King
927	4	Assorted Plate Measurements	1902		35	Edward S. King
928	5	Color Distance measurements	1920		36	Edward S. King
929	6	Schilt Photometry	1927-28		36	Edward S. King
930		Photographic measurement of light	1897		36	
931		Computation Book No. 2	1916		36	Edward S. King
932	1	Photographic Magnitudes, Misc	1914-18		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
933	2	Variables; Observations	1902-03		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
934	4	Examination of Plates	1903		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
935	5	Variables	1903		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
936		Phoebe	1904		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
937	1	Circumpolar Variables	1895-96		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
938	2	Variable Star Observations	1896		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
939	3	Variable Star Observations	1896		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
940	4	Variable Star Observations	1896		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
941	5	Variable Star Observations	1902		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
942	6	Circumpolar Variables	1902-04		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
943	7	Variable Star Observations	1904		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
944	9	Miscellaneous Observations	1904-10		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
945	13	Miscellaneous Observations	1906-16		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
946	22	Discovery of New Variables	1907-08		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
947	23	Comparison Stars	1906-07		36	Henrietta S. Leavitt
948	24	Observations of new Variables	1906-07		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
949	25	Observations of new Variables	1907-14		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
950	26	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - T plates	1907-09		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
951	27	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - T plates	1908-10		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
952	28	Std. Magnitudes	1909-14		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
953	29	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole	1910-12		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
954	30	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole	1910		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
955	32	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole	1911-14		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
956	33	Miscellaneous Journal	1911-12		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
957	34	Miscellaneous	1911-14		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
958	35	Objects looked up by request	1914-18		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
959	36	Standard Magnitudes	1914-19		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
960	37	Miscellaneous - Comp. Stars	1914-16		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
961	38	Catalogs Comparison Stars	1915-19		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
962	39	Miscellaneous (Variables)	1915-19		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
963	40	Discovery of New Variables	1916-20		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
964	41	Miscellaneous (esp. Novae)	1916-20		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
965	43	Standard Magnitudes	1919-21		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
966	44	Miscellaneous (Variables)	1920-21		37	Henrietta S. Leavitt
967	1	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables	1893-96		37	Evelyn F. Leland
968	2	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables M5	1896		38	Evelyn F. Leland
969	3	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables M5	1896		38	Evelyn F. Leland
970	4	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables M5	1896-97		38	Evelyn F. Leland
971	5	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables M5	1898-98		38	Evelyn F. Leland
972	7	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables W Cen.	1897-98		38	Evelyn F. Leland
973	15	Measure of Eros (South Pole)	1899-1902		38	Evelyn F. Leland
974	16	Measures New. Sat. (Phoebe) of Saturn, Nova Sgr	1899-1906		38	Evelyn F. Leland

975	25	Measures of M3, etc.	1902-03	38	Evelyn F. Leland
976	26	Measures of Eros	1902-04	38	Evelyn F. Leland
977	27	Search for variables; measures	1902-03	38	Evelyn F. Leland
978	28	Search for variables; measures	1903-04	38	Evelyn F. Leland
979	30	Search for variables; measures	1904-07	38	Evelyn F. Leland
980	31 or 32	Search for variables; measures	1907-09	38	Evelyn F. Leland
981	33	Search for variables; measures	1904-10	38	Evelyn F. Leland
982	34	Scale measures	1907-10	38	Evelyn F. Leland
983	37	Scale measures	1911-12	38	Evelyn F. Leland
984	35	Scale measures	1910-12	38	Evelyn F. Leland
985	36	Scale measures	1910-11	38	Evelyn F. Leland
986	38	Scale measures	1912	38	Evelyn F. Leland
987	39	Scale measures	1913-14	38	Evelyn F. Leland
988	40	Series Reductions	1913	39	Evelyn F. Leland
989	41	Observing Book - M5	1913	39	Evelyn F. Leland
990	42	Series Reductions	1913	39	Evelyn F. Leland
991	43	Series Reductions	1913-14	39	Evelyn F. Leland
992	44	Series Reductions and M5 variables	1914-15	39	Evelyn F. Leland
993	45	Series Reductions	1913-14	39	Evelyn F. Leland
994	46	Series Reductions	1913-15	39	Evelyn F. Leland
995	47	Series Reductions	1914-15	39	Evelyn F. Leland
996	48	Series Reductions	1914-15	39	Evelyn F. Leland
997	49	Series Reductions	1915-17	39	Evelyn F. Leland
998	50	Series Reductions	1915-17	39	Evelyn F. Leland
999	51	Series Reductions	1915-17	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1000	53	Measures of Variables in M15	1917	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1001	52	Measures of Variables in M15	1916-17	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1002	54	Measures of Variables in M15	1917-18	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1003	55	Measures of Variables in M15	1917-18	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1004	56	Observing Book	1918	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1005	57	Observing Book	1918	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1006	58	Long Exposure H.S. Regions and Series	1918-19	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1007	29	New Satellite of Saturn and N. Polar Seq.	1904-11	39	Evelyn F. Leland
1008	59	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1918-19	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1009	60	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1919	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1010	61	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1919-20	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1011	62	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1919-20	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1012	63	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1920	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1013	64	MF Series	1920	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1014	65	MF Series	1920-21	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1015	66	MC and A Plates	1921	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1016	67	Large Magellanic Cloud	1921	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1017	68	MC Plates	1921-22	40	Evelyn F. Leland
1018	1	MC Plates	1915-16	40	H.S. Locke
1019	2	MC Plates	1915-16	40	H.S. Locke
1020	3	MC Plates	1916	40	H.S. Locke
1021	4	MC Plates	1916, 1918	40	H.S. Locke
1022	5	MC Plates	1916-17	40	H.S. Locke
1023	6	MC Plates	1917	40	H.S. Locke
1024	7	Misc Plates	1917-18	40	H.S. Locke
1025	8	MC Plates	1917-18	40	H.S. Locke
1026	9	MC Plates	1917-18	40	H.S. Locke
1027	10	B and MC Plates	1917-19	40	H.S. Locke
1028	1	Observing Book	1910-19	41	JCM
1029	2	Observing Book (Scale Measures)	1913-18	41	JCM
1030	3	Observing Book (MD Plates)	1913-19	41	JCM
1031	5	Observing Book (Misc. Plates)	1918-19	41	JCM
1032	7	B Series	1919	41	JCM
1033	8	Observing Book (B Series)	1919	41	JCM
1034	9	Observing Book (Misc. Measures)	1919-20	41	M K?
1035	10	Novae? (Maps of S, AC Plates)	1919-20	41	M K?
1036	1	Observing Book - Variable Stars	1912-13	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1037	2	Observing Book - Scale Measures	1913	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1038	3	Observing Book Series Measures	1913-16	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1039	4	Observing Book - Series, etc.	1914	41	Genevieve F. Matthews

1040	5	Observing Book Miscellaneous	1914-15	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1041	7	Circumpolar Variables	1914-15	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1042	8	Circumpolar Variables	1914-15	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1043	9	Series Measures (principally blue plates)	1915	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1044	10	Series Measures (principally yellow plates)	1915-16	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1045	6	Circumpolar Variables	1914-16	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1046	11	Circumpolar Variables (est. of brightness)	1915-16	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1047	12	Circumpolar variables (overflow)	1915	41	Genevieve F. Matthews
1048	13	Circumpolar variables	1916	42	Genevieve F. Matthews
1049	14	Circumpolar variables (record of obsns on phlog's)	1918	42	Genevieve F. Matthews
1050		Tables of Ursae Majoris	1894-96	42	Antonia C. Maury
1051		Rotation of Primary Star and Separation of Satellites	1928-32	42	Antonia C. Maury
1052		Formulae for reduction, Phase in HA84	1918-22	42	Antonia C. Maury
1053		(loose papers) beta Lyras and others	1933	42	Antonia C. Maury
1054	1	Obs. Book, Meas. of Variables and Standard Seq.	1912	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1055	2	Misc. Observations, Variables, Etc.	1914-17	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1056	3	Safe Meas. of Std. Regions on I series	1913-14	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1057	4	circumpolar variables - meas. of comp stars	1914	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1058	5	MC Plates	1914	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1059	6	Meas. of Misc. Plates	1914	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1060	7	Meas. of Misc. Plates	1914	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1061	8	MC and Misc Plates	1914	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1062	9	MC and Misc Plates	1914	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1063	10	MC and Misc Plates	1914-15	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1064	11	MC and Misc Plates	1914-15	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1065	12	MC and Misc Plates	1915-17	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1066	13	MC and Misc Plates	1915	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1067	14	MC and Misc Plates	1915	42	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1068	15	MC and Misc Plates	1915	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1069	16	MC and Misc Plates	1915	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1070	17	MC and Misc Plates	1915-16	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1071	18	Southern and AS Plates	1915-16	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1072	19	MC and Misc Plates	1916-17	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1073	20	Miscellaneous	1916-17	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1074	21	Obs. Book	1916-17	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1075	22	Southern plates	1916	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1076	23	Mostly Southern Regions	1916	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1077	24	Mostly Southern Regions	1916-17	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1078	25	Mostly Southern Regions	1917	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1079	26	Mostly Southern Regions	1917	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1080	27	Miscellaneous	1917-18	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1081	28	Miscellaneous	1917-18	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1082	29	Obs. Book	1918	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1083	30	Scale measures	1918	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1084	31	B Series	1918	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1085	32	Cat. Sc. Measures	1918	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1086	33	For Cat. 1 degree Square	1918	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
1087	34	Cat 4 degree Square	1918	43	Mollie E. O'Reilly
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1089	2	8" Polar Equatorial	1912-13	44	Philip G. O'Reilly
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1102	12	Single Spectra (Capella, Rigel, Sirius, Altair)		44	Cecilia H. Payne
1103	13	Apertured beta Cas		44	Cecilia H. Payne
1104	14	General Ledgers		44	Cecilia H. Payne

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1107	17	Line Photometry			45	Cecilia H. Payne
1108	18	Plates			45	Cecilia H. Payne
1109	20	Apertured Mira, alpha Cygnus, alpha Persei			45	Cecilia H. Payne
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1171	2	Observations of Novae	1917-18	48	Mary H. Van?
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1173	4	Observations of Novae	1918	48	Mary H. Van?
1174	1	Double Star measures	1876	48	Leonard Wald?
1175		correspondence	1896-97	48	Anna Winlo?
1176		Observations - 6in. Telescope	1911-13	48	Ida E. Woods
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1179		Observations - 6in. Telescope	1912-1917	48	Ida E. Woods
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1181	5	Cluster Variables	1917-18	49	Ida E. Woods
1182	6	Cluster Variables	1919-23	49	Ida E. Woods
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1187	11	New Variables	1920-22	49	Ida E. Woods
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1205	29	New Variables	1924-26	50	Ida E. Woods
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1208	32	Misc. Milky Way Regions	1925	50	Ida E. Woods
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1271	74	Variable Star Observations, Photom.	1930	53	F Schilt
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1274	77	RH Plates	1930	53	F Schilt
1275	78	RH Plates	1930	53	F Schilt
1276	79	RH Plates	1930	54	F Schilt
1277	80	RH Plates	1930-31	54	F Schilt
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1280	83	RH Plates	1931	54	F Schilt
1281	84	RH Plates	1931-32	54	F Schilt
1282	85	RH Plates	1932	54	F Schilt
1283	86	RH Plates PTM	1932	54	F Schilt
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1286	89	RH Plates PTM	1932	54	F Schilt
1287	90	RH Plates PTM	1932	54	F Schilt
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1880	VOL 4	Harvard Lunar Plates		79	Mary Fowler
1881	VOL 5	Harvard Lunar Plates		79	Mary Fowler

1947	VOL 70		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1948	VOL 71		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1949	VOL 72		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1950	VOL 73		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1951	VOL 74		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1952	VOL 75		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1953	VOL 76		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1954	VOL 77		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1955	VOL 78		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1956	VOL 79		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1957	VOL 80		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1958	VOL 81		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1959	VOL 82		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1960	VOL 83		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1961	VOL 84		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1962	VOL 85		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1963	VOL 86		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1964	VOL 87		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1965	VOL 88		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1966	VOL 89		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1967	VOL 90		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1968	VOL 115		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1969	VOL 116		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1970	VOL 117		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1971	VOL 118		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1972	VOL 119		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1973	VOL 120		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Martha C Borton
1974	VOL 121		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Martha C Borton
1975	VOL 122		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Martha C Borton
1976	VOL 123		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1977	VOL 124		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1978	VOL 125		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Mary Fowler
1979	VOL 126		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Martha C Borton
1980	VOL 127		Harvard Lunar Plates				81	Martha C Borton
1981	VOL 128		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1982	VOL 129		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1983	VOL 130		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1984	VOL 131		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1985	VOL 132		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1986	VOL 133		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1987	VOL 134		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1988	VOL 135		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1989	VOL 137		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
1990	VOL 138		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1991	VOL 139		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1992	VOL 140		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1993	VOL 141		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1994	VOL 142		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1995	VOL 143		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
1996	VOL 144		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
1997	VOL 145		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1998	VOL 146		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
1999	VOL 147		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
2000	VOL 148		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
2001	VOL 149		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2002	VOL 150		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2003	VOL 151		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2004	VOL 152		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2005	VOL 153		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
2006	VOL 154		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
2007	VOL 155		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2008	VOL 156		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2009	VOL 157		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Martha C Borton
2010	VOL 158		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller
2011	VOL 159		Harvard Lunar Plates				82	Ernestine Fuller

2012	VOL 160	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Ernestine Fuller
2013	VOL 161	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Martha C Borton
2014	VOL 162	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Martha C Borton
2015	VOL 163	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Martha C Borton
2016	VOL 164	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Martha C Borton
2017	VOL 165	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Martha C Borton
2018	VOL 166	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Ernestine Fuller
2019	VOL 167	Harvard Lunar Plates			82	Ernestine Fuller
2020	VOL 168	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2021	VOL 169	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2022	VOL 170	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2023	VOL 171	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2024	VOL 172	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2025	VOL 173	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2026	VOL 174	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
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2028	VOL 176	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2029	VOL 177	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2030	VOL 178	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2031	VOL 179	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2032	VOL 180	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
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2036	VOL 185	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2037	VOL 186	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2038	VOL 187	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2039	VOL 188	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2040	VOL 189	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2041	VOL 190	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C Borton
2042	VOL 191	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2043	VOL 192	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C. Bortonon
2044	VOL 193	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2045	VOL 194	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C. Borton
2046	VOL 195	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Martha C. Borton
2047	VOL 196	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
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2052		?			83	Ernestine Fuller
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2064		Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2065		Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2066		Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2067		Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2068	VOL 136	Harvard Lunar Plates			83	Ernestine Fuller
2069		Fireballs - General Index			84	Pamphlet Case
2070		Correspondence (Lunar Eclipse)			85	Pamphlet Case
2071		Bright Meteors Reported to HCO 1925-32			86	Pamphlet Case
2072		Fireballs, Lunar Eclipse			87	Pamphlet Case
2073		Meteors and Fireballs			88	Pamphlet Case
2074		Meteors (includes painting)			89	Pamphlet Case
2075		Meteors, Lunar Eclipse			90	Pamphlet Case

2076		Meteors, Fireballs				91	Pamphlet Case
2077		Meteors				92	Pamphlet Case
2078		Meteors				93	Pamphlet Case
2079		Meteors (newspaper clippings)				94	Pamphlet Case
2080		Observations in 1881ff - Pickering and Chandler				95	Pamphlet Case
2081		Meteor Reports, etc.				96	Pamphlet Case

All done.

Thank God.

☺

-Rahul

KG11365.

P:\projects\plate-stacks-depository-list.xls

Box#	auth #	alpha num. ID	title	start date	end date	notes	
001	1	A1	Transit Circle	11/7/1848	7/30/1849		
	2	A2	"	7/30/1849	9/25/1849		
	3	A3	"	9/26/1849	11/29/1849	*	
	4	A4	"	11/30/1849	2/6/1850		
	5	A5	"	2/6/1850	4/30/1850		
	6	A6	"	5/1/1850	10/20/1850		
	7	A7	"	10/21/1850	12/26/1850		
	8	A8	"	12/26/1850	4/3/1851	*	
	9	A9	"	4/3/1851	7/13/1851		
	10	A10	"	7/13/1851	9/5/1851	*	
	11	A11	"	9/5/1851	1/15/1852		
	12	A12	"	1/15/1852	6/28/1852		
	13	A13	"	6/28/1852	12/5/1852		
	14	A14	"	12/1/1852	7/8/1853		
	15	A15	"	7/8/1853	2/26/1854		
	16	A16	"	2/28/1854	8/15/1854		
	001	17	A17	"	8/15/1854	11/27/1854	
		18	A18	"	11/27/1854	1/25/1855	
19		A19	"	1/25/1855	5/6/1855	*	
20		A20	"	5/6/1855	7/31/1855		
21		A21	"	8/1/1855	9/25/1855		
22		A22	"	9/25/1855	3/27/1856		
23		A23	"	3/27/1856	6/15/1856		
24		A24	"	6/16/1856	9/5/1856		
25		A25	"	9/8/1856	2/9/1857		
26		A26	"	2/17/1857	9/21/1857		
27		A27	"	9/21/1857	11/3/1857		
28		A28	"	11/3/1857	2/10/1858		
001		29	A29	"	2/10/1858	7/5/1858	
	30	A30	"	7/5/1858	1/24/1859		
	31	A31	"	1/24/1859	8/17/1859		
	32	A32	"	8/17/1859	1/23/1860		
	33	A33	"	1/23/1860	6/23/1860		
	34	A34	"	6/23/1860	11/29/1860		
	35	A35	"	11/29/1860	3/21/1861		
	36	A36	"	3/21/1861	10/1/1861		
	37	A37	"	10/1/1861	3/28/1862		
	38	A38	Meridian	"	3/28/1862	5/7/1862	
	39	A39	"	"	5/7/1862	8/6/1862	

	40	A40	Meridian Circle	8/11/1862 - 9/25/1862	
	41	A41	"	9/27/1862 - 12/8/1862	
001	42	A42	"	12/10/1862 - 2/16/1863	
	43	A43	"	2/17/1863 - 5/25/1863	
	44	A44	"	5/26/1863 - 8/14/1863	
	45	A45	"	8/14/1863 - 9/22/1863	
002	46	A46	"	9/23/1863 - 12/2/1863	
	47	A47	"	12/5/1863 - 1/11/1864	
	48	A48	"	1/11/1864 - 3/3/1864	
	49	A49	"	3/7/1864 - 4/29/1864	
	50	A50	"	4/9/1864 - 5/19/1864	
	51	A51	"	5/22/1864 - 6/6/1864	
	52	A52	"	6/7/1864 - 6/19/1864	unlabeled
	53	A53	"	6/21/1864 - 7/5/1864	unlabeled
002	54	A54	"	7/6/1864 - 7/19/1864	
	55	A55	"	7/20/1864 - 9/9/1864	
	56	A56	"	9/10/1864 - 10/10/1864	
	57	A57	"	10/10/1864 - 11/4/1864	
	58	A58	"	11/10/1864 - 11/23/1864	
	59	A59	"	11/25/1864 - 12/20/1864	
	60	A60	"	12/30/1864 - 1/18/1865	
	61	A61	"	1/20/1865 - 2/1/1865	
	62	A62	"	2/2/1865 - 2/25/1865	
002	63	A63	"	2/27/1865 - 4/3/1865	
	64	A64	"	4/3/1865 - 4/26/1865	
	65	A65	"	5/1/1865 - 6/2/1865	
	66	A66	"	6/3/1865 - 7/4/1865	
	67	A67	"	7/5/1865 - 7/18/1865	
	68	A68	"	7/20/1865 - 8/1/1865	
	69	A69	"	8/2/1865 - 8/28/1865	
	70	A70	"	8/29/1865 - 9/15/1865	
002	71	A71	"	9/16/1865 - 9/30/1865	
	72	B1	Reduction of Transits	1/1/1849 - 8/16/1849	2/22
	73	B2	"	8/16/1849 - 12/7/1849	
	74	B3	"	12/7/1849 - 4/2/1850	
	75	B4	"	4/2/1850 - 10/5/1850	
	76	B5	"	10/5/1850 - 12/30/1850	
	77	B6	"	12/30/1850 - 4/5/1851	
	78	B7	"	4/5/1851 - 7/8/1851	

002

79 B8
 80 B9
 81 B10
 82 B11
 83 B12
 84 B13
 85 B14
 86 B15
 87 B16
 88 B17
 89 B18
 90 B19

Reduction of Transits

7/8/1851 - 9/4/1851
 9/4/1851 - 11/11/1851
 11/11/1851 - 2/25/1852
 2/25/1852 - 7/6/1852
 7/6/1852 - 11/17/1852
 11/17/1852 - 5/1/1853
 5/1/1853 - 11/2/1853
 11/2/1853 - 4/9/1854
 4/9/1854 - 8/9/1854
 8/6/1854 - 11/27/1854
 11/27/1854 - 1/30/1855
 1/30/1855 - 5/6/1855

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003

91 B20
 92 B21
 93 B22
 94 B23
 95 B24
 96 B25
 97 B26
 98 B27
 99 B28
 100 B29
 101 B30
 102 B31

" "
 " "
 " "
 " "
 " "
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 " "
 " "
 " "
 " "
 " "

5/6/1855 - 8/1/1855
 7/31/1855 - 9/25/1855
 9/25/1855 - 3/30/1856
 3/30/1856 - 6/11/1856
 6/11/1856 - 8/22/1856
 8/22/1856 - 11/20/1856
 11/20/1856 - 4/30/1857
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 6/24/1858 - 11/9/1858

003

103 B32
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" "
 " "
 " "
 " "
 " "

11/9/1858 - 6/19/1859
 6/19/1859 - 10/14/1859
 10/14/1859 - 3/27/1860
 3/27/1860 - 11/16/1860
 11/16/1860 - 1/1/1861

003

108 C1
 109 C2
 110 C3
 111 C4
 112 C5
 113 C8
 114 C9
 115 C10
 116 C11
 117 C12

N.S. Meridian Marks and Level Readings

12/5/1849 - 9/4/1853
 7/1853 - 7/21/1855
 4/21/1855 - 9/8/1856
 9/1856 - 2/24/1859
 2/24/1859 - 3/11/1862

Instrumental Corrections

12/29/1863 - 10/1865

Computed AR of Polar Stars

3/11/1862 - 8/19/1863

" " "

8/22/1863 - 11/14/1864

Chronograph Record

6/1861 - 7/1863

" "

7/23/1863 - 11/4/1864

	118	C13	Chronograph Record	11/10/1864 - 9/12/1865	
	119	C14	" "	9/13/1865 - 2/20/1866	
003	120	C12 [C15]	Misc. time observations		
	121	D1	Minutes of Chronometer Exped. 4/1849 - 2/1850 #1 -		*
	122	E1	Meridian Circle	11/7/1859 - 5/25/1860	
	123	E2	" "	5/24/1859 - 11/3/1859	
	124	E3	" "	5/25/1860 - 11/13/1860	
	125	E4	Declinations	12/20/1862 - 9/9/1863	
	126	E5	"	9/14/1863 - 10/17/1864	
	127	E6	New Transit Circle	2/17/1857 - 5/28/1858	*
003	128	E7	Transit Circle	1851 - 1853	
	129	E8	" "	8/7/1851 - 12/4/1851	
	130	F1	Norm Culminations + Transits	12/1845 - 4/1846	(Comets also)
	131	F2	Comets + Meridian Transits	4/1846 - 10/1846	(Earthquake 8/25)
	132	F3	" " "	10/1846 - 4/16/1847	
	133	F4	" " "	4/24/1847 - 2/9/1848	
	134	F5	" " "	2/18/1848 - 8/1/1848	
	135	F6	" " "	8/1/1849 - 2/27/1850	*
	136	F7	Meridian + Prime Vertical Obs	11/6/1844 - 12/12/1844	(EARLY!)
003	137	F8	West Transit	11/5/1851 - 12/16/1851	
	138	F9	Prime Vertical	11/1854 - ?	
	139	F10	Magnetic + Prime Vertical	1858	
	140	F11	Terrestrial Magnetism	3/25/1858 - 6/5/1861	
	141	F12a	[Chronograph 6/8/1864 - 7/21/1864]		
	142	F12b	Prime vertical Computation of Latitude	1864	
004	143	F13	Telegraph	7/6/1848 - 10/28/1848	
	144	G1	Chronometers from July 1 st 1853 - 7/21/1855		(Annular Eclipse 5/26/54)
	145	G2	"	7/1/1853 - 4/21/1855	
	146	G3	Sidereal + Mean Time Clocks	4/21/1855 - 1/1/1856	
	147	G4	" " " "	1/1/1856 - 2/27/1857	
	148	G5	" " " "	2/28/1857 - 7/2/1858	
	149	G6	" " " "	7/2/1856 - 7/16/1860	
	150	G7	" " " "	7/14/1860 - 9/3/1862	
	151	G8	" " " "	9/16/1862 - 3/2/1866	
	152	G ^a	Railroad Time Commenced	6/29/1854 - 10/1854	
	153	G ^b	Trials of Pendulums + Chronometers	4/27/1857 - 2/19/1859	
004	154	H ^a Vol I	517-604	11/1848 - 2/1849 - Comets + Double #s 1848	
	155	H ^a	Equatorial Reductions	6/21/1860 - 1/22/1861	
	156	H1 Vol I	1 - 80	Equatorial 10/1846 - 7/1847	

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Specimen

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157	H2	Vol I	81-168
158	H3		169-256
159	H4		257-344
160	H5		345-432
161	H6		433-516
162	H7	Vol II	1-92
163	H8		93-192
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165	H11		293-392
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168	H14	Vol III	1-98
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173	H19		485-574
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175	H21		
176	H22		
177	H23		
178	H24		
179	H25		
180	H26		
181	H27		
182	H28		
183	H29		
184	H30		
185	H31		
186	H32		
187	H33		
188	H34		
189	H35		
190	H36		
191	H37		
192	H38		
193	H39		
194	H40		
195	H41		

Equatorial

7/1847	-12/1847
12/1847	-8/1848
11/1847	-2/1848
2/1848	-9/1848
5/1848	-11/1848
2/1849	-6/1849
1/1849	-11/1849
12/1849	-1/1850
5/10/1850	-9/1/1850
9/21/1850	-2/25/1851
2/25/1851	-12/4/1851
12/4/1851	-5/18/1852
5/19/1852	-10/26/1852
10/28/1852	-3/10/1853
3/10/1853	-4/3/1854
4/4/1854	-6/13/1855
6/13/1855	-4/1/1856
4/1/1856	-2/15/1857
2/15/1857	-5/13/1857
5/13/1857	-9/1/1857
8/23/1857	-10/22/1857
10/23/1857	-12/14/1857
12/15/1857	-3/17/1858
3/18/1858	-7/13/1858
7/14/1858	-9/25/1858
9/25/1858	-11/11/1858
11/11/1858	-5/4/1859
5/4/1859	-10/26/1859
10/26/1859	-1/31/1860
1/31/1860	-3/14/1860
3/15/1860	-3/29/1860
3/30/1860	-5/2/1860
5/2/1860	-6/22/1860
6/24/1860	-7/9/1860
7/4/1860	-9/22/1860
9/26/1860	-1/30/1861
1/31/1861	-4/8/1861
4/9/1861	-5/2/1861
5/3/1861	-6/22/1861

Diagrams by King

last obs. of W.C.B.

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196 H42
 197 H43
 198 H44
 199 H45
 200 H46
 201 H47
 202 H48
 203 H49
 204 H50
 205 H51
 206 H52
 207 H53
 208 H54
 209 H55
 210 H56

Equatorial

6/22/1861 - 7/13/1861
 7/13/1861 - 9/12/1861
 9/16/1861 - 12/30/1861
 1/1/1862 - 4/18/1862
 4/19/1862 - 7/5/1862
 7/6/1862 - 8/19/1862
 8/19/1862 - 12/2/1862
 12/6/1862 - 4/9/1863
 4/13/1863 - 6/4/1863
 6/10/1863 - 10/1/1863
 10/5/1863 - 2/19/1864
 2/19/1863 - 3/21/1864
 3/21/1864 - 6/1864
 6/1864 - 3/29/1865
 4/3/1865 - 2/5/1866

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See 284 for more

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211 K1
 212 K2
 213 K3
 214 K4
 215 K5
 216 K6
 217 K7
 218 K8
 219 K9
 220 K10
 221 K11
 222 K12
 223 K13
 224 K14

Zones

1-7
 7-13
 14-19, Bessel
 20-26
 27-33
 34-39
 40-45
 46-54
 55-62
 65-84a
 84a-88
~~89-100~~
 101-116
 1-6
 6-7
 117-124
 125-135
 134-146
 147-149

4/7/1852 - 5/4/1852
 5/4/1852 - 11/3/1852
 11/4/1852 - 12/14/1852
 12/15/1852 - 1/8/1853
 1/11/1853 - 2/11/1853
 2/12/1853 - 3/15/1853
 3/16/1853 - 4/1/1853
 4/8/1853 - 5/11/1853
 5/31/1853 - 9/9/1853
 9/27/1854 - 12/8/1854
 12/8/1854 - 2/3/1855
 2/12/1855 - 4/16/1855
 4/23/1855 - 7/17/1855
 3/30/1859 - 5/3/1859
 5/3/1859 - 5/14/1859
 5/23/1859 - 8/25/1859
 8/29/1859 - 11/26/1859
 11/26/1859 - 2/17/1860
 2/21/1860 - 11/29/1860
 11/20/1860 - 2/4/1861
 2/26/1860 - 4/8/1861
 4/9/1861 - 6/25/1861
 7/11/1861 - 10/29/1861
 9/24/1861 - 1/31/1862

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225 K15
 226 K16
 227 K17
 228 K18
 229 K19
 230 K20
 231 K21
 232 K22
 233 K23
 234 K24

Catalog #'s

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235 K25
236 K26
237 K27
238 L1
239 K28
240 L2
241 L3
242 L4
243 L5
244 L6
245 L7
246 L8
247 L9
248 L10
249 L11
250 L12
251 L13
252 M2
253 M3
254 M5
255 M6
256 M7
257 M9
258 M10
259 M11
260 M12
261 M13
262 M14
263 M15
264 M16
265 M18
266 M18
267 M19
268 M20
269 M21
270 M23
271 M24
272 M25
273 M26

Zones 10/22/1862 - 2/10/1863
" " 2/18/1862 - 5/1864
" " 6/23/1864 - [9/27/1864]
Reduction of Zone Observations 1853 Explanation
Zones 10/5/1864 - 12/1/1864
Reduction of Zone Observations 1853
" " " 1853
" " " 1853
" " " 1853
" " " 1853
" " " 1853
[Comparisons of Zones]
Reductions of Zones No Reductions 1859
Reductions of Zones Comparison of Magnitudes 1859
Special Zones and Magnitudes
Revision of Zones. Magnitudes
Reduction of Zones - I
Gould's Universal Index (Catalog?)
[Tables, Procedures]
Table of Contents of Various Books containing Records of Observations 1841-1855
Various Memoranda [Longitude determination, mag. meas., etc.] 1844-5
Catalog Stars 1854-58
Tables for Applying Instrumental Corrections [c. 1855]
Catalogue of Stars for Zones [c. 1853]
Reduction of Stars in Weiss (?) from 0° to 1° N to 1853
Printing of Zone Obsns 1854 + History + Description of the Obs.
Lists of persons + institutions recipients of H. Annals
Meteorological 1/1/1861 - 5/1863
1859-60 Comet Seeker 12/1/1859 - 9/11/1860
Colorado Survey - Time 12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858
" " Latitude by Polaris 12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858
[Solar Observations] 1/5/1855 - 5/2/1855
[Catalog of Bright Nebulae + Clusters] 6/16/1850 - 5/1853
[Comet Seeking] 6/10/1847 - 6/5/1850
Books Received at the Obs. of Harw. Coll. 1862-1878
Reductions of Moon Culminations 1/1849 - 5/28/1852
" " " 7/1851 - 10/2/1854
P. S. N. [drawings of * config's and angle] 6/16/1856 - 7/4/1856

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- 274 M27
- 275 M28
- 276 M29
- 277 M30
- 278 M31
- 279 M32
- 280 M33
- 281 M34
- 282 M35
- 283 M36
- 284 N1
- 285 N2
- 286 N3
- 287 N4
- 288 N5
- 289 N6
- 290 N7
- 291 N8
- 292 N9
- 293 N10
- 294 N11
- 295 N12
- 296 N13
- 297 N14
- 298 N15
- 299 N16
- 300 N17
- 301 N18
- 302 N19
- 303 N20
- 304 N21
- 305 N22
- 306 N23
- 307 N24
- 308 N25
- 309 N26
- 310 N27
- 311 N28
- 312 N29

[11/15/1850 - 8/22/1851]
 Gould's Universal Index
 Printing 1860 - 1863
 Memoranda for Obs. Report 1/7/1861 - 12/31/1864
 Memoranda 1/3/1862 - 1/2/1865
 Catalog of Books in the Phillips Library, commenced 10/9/1856
 Chronometer - Stars 1862-5
 Transit Catalog
 Eclipse of 4/25/1846 - Portland
 Account of Various Records + Papers belonging to the Obs - 1866
 Equatorial 6/9/1866 - 7/6/1866
 " 7/9/1866 - 7/22/1866
 " 7/24/1866 - 8/11/1866
 " 8/13/1866 - 8/25/1866
 " 8/26/1866 - 9/10/1866
 " 9/12/1866 - 10/2/1866
 " 10/2/1866 - 10/21/1866
 " 10/22/1866 - 1/19/1867
 " 1/23/1867 - 4/23/1867
 " 4/25/1867 - 10/24/1867
 " 10/25/1867 - 1/16/1868
 " 1/27/1868 - 4/1/1868
 " 4/1/1868 - 10/9/1868 [Spectra]
 " 10/10/1868 - 12/19/1868
 " 12/22/1868 - 4/22/1869
 " 4/28/1869 - 10/18/1869
 " 10/19/1869 - 5/17/1870
 " Miss. Obsns 10/31/1871 - 11/27/1872
 " " " 12/24/1869 - 9/2/1874
 " " " 12/8/1874 - 7/11/1875
 " Asteroids 7/13/1870 - 12/21/1870
 " " " 2/13/1871 - 8/10/1871
 " (W. A. Rogers)
 " " "
 Reduction of Asteroid Obsns 1870
 " " " 1870-71
 Reduction to app. place of some stars used in 1870
 " " " " "
 Reduction of Asteroid Obsns 1870

008	313	N30	Search for Asteroids	1870
	314	N31	Equatorial - Obsns of Asteroids + comets (copy)	
	315	N32	Computation of app. place, differ. refract., Equatorial Comp. 2	6/30/1866 - 4/26/1866
	316	N33	Reductions of Equatorial Obsns	10/15/1874 - 6/2/1875
	317	N34	v.1 Equatorial (copy)	4/9/1866 - 8/26/1866
	318	N35	v.2 " "	8/27/1866 - 10/20/1866
	319	N36	v.3 " "	10/21/1866 - 1/14/1867
	320	N37	v.4 " "	1/14/1867 - 4/26/1867
008	321	N38	v.5 " "	4/26/1867 - 10/19/1867
	322	N39	v.6 " "	10/22/1867 - 2/1/1868
	323	N40	v.7 " "	2/3/1868 - 6/28/1868
	324	N41	Catalog of Nebulae (G. M. Searle)	
→	325	N42	Measurement of photos of eclipses	1869-1870
→	326	N43	" " " Solar "	1870
	327	N44	vol I Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot	10/30/1870 - 4/13/1873
	328	N45	vol II " " " " "	4/14/1873 - 9/30/1874
→	329	N46	Solar photography (W. Lubbock plates)	7/40/1870 - 11/30/1876
	329a	N48	General record of Work	1869-1872
008	330	N50	Tables, etc.	1866-67
	331	N51	Reduced Measures of Double Stars - E. Equatorial	1866-1867
	332	O 1	East Transit Observation	5/1/1866 - 9/2/1866
	333	O 2	" " "	9/4/1866 - 5/29/1867
→	334	O 3	" " "	5/31/1867 - 11/5/1867
	335	O 4	" " "	11/9/1867 - 7/10/1868
	336	O 5	" " "	7/16/1868 - 10/2/1868
	337	O 6	" " (Time)	10/3/1868 - 8/22/1869
009	338	O 7	" " "	8/29/1869 - 6/6/1870
	339	O 8	" " (Occultations)	6/12/1870 - 1/27/1871
	340	O 9	" " (Time)	12/1/1871 - 12/27/1871
	341	O 10	Chronograph Record	4/2/1866 - 7/29/1869
	342	O 11	East Transit (Errors)	4/17/1866 - 9/17/1867
	343	O 12	Longitude Campaign: Cambridge - Washington	1867
	344	O 13	Transit Observations 1867	6/28/1867 - 6/29/1867
	345	O 14	Formulae for Reduction of Transit Observations + Tables	~1867
009	346	[O15]	Chronograph Record	7/31/1867 - 12/19/1867
	347	O 16	" "	12/19/1867 - 8/14/1868
	348	O 17	" "	8/14/1868 - 7/30/1869
	349	O 18	" "	8/13/1869 - 7/7/1870
	350	O 19	Record of Errors of Clocks	1866 - 1869

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351	[020?]	Stars to be Observed w/ East Transit	1868-1870	
352	020	Second Computation of Instrument Errors	1867-1868	
353	021	Longitude Computation from Coast Survey	1869	
354	022	[Transit Observations]	8/24/1870 - 10/23/1870	
355	023	Longitude - Field Reductions	1871	
356	024	Clock Corrections	1869-1872	
357	025	" " "	1872-1875	
358	026	" " "	1875	
359	027	Notes on Astron Engravings, Spanish Weather record, Phillips Fund		
360	028	Eclipses of 1869. Reports		[Beautiful volume]
361	029	Personal equation observations	1871	
362	P1	Magnetic Observations	8/16/1866 - 2/17/1868	
363	P2	Meteorological Observations	1866	
364	P3	" " (?)	1866	
365	P4	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1867	
366	P5	" "	1868	
367	P6	" "	1869	
368	P7	" "	1870	
369	P8	" "	1871	("Clayton's Octavo Diary")
370	P9	" "	1872	
371	P10	" "	1873	
372	P11	" "	1874	
373	P12	" "	1875	
374	P13	" "	1876	
375	P14	" "	1877	
376	P15	" "	1878	
377	P16	" "	1879	
378	Q1	Meteorological Record	1866, 1867, 1868	
379	Q2	" " of HCO	1869	
380	Q3	" " "	1870, 1871	
381	Q4	" " "	1872-1877	
382	Q5	" " "	1878-1879, July-Dec 1866	
383		Mr J.G. Home's Original Minutes of Chronometer Expedition	1857	
384		A — A — of the White Mts. of New Hampshire	1853 (N.B. Annular Eclipse is)	
385		[Paris to Cambridge Telegraph]	6/20-7/12 ~1861?	
386		U.S. Coast Survey, Benj. Pierce, Subst: Letter book + Abstract - Long Party	1868	
387		Observations and Longitude Computations	1872 (U.S. Coast Survey)	
388		Longitude + latitude No. 1 (Bolivia)	1892-93	
389		Time Service	4/18/1880 - 4/19/1881	

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390		Meridian Circle Record - Mr. Austin	8/16/1870 - 5/13/1871
391	Vol 1	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Peirce	3/6/1872 - 3/21/1872
392	2	" " " "	3/22/1872 - 4/5/1872
393	3	" " " "	6/6/1872 - 7/2/1872
394	4	" " " "	5/4/1872 - 5/30/1872 Dup
395	5	" " " "	5/31/1872 - 6/13/1872 "
396	6	" " " "	6/10/1872 - 6/30/1872 "
397	7	" " " "	6/30/1872 - 7/30/1872
398	8	" " " "	7/30/1872 - 8/9/1872
399	9	" " " "	8/9/1872 - 9/15/1872
400	10	" " " "	8/18/1872 - 3/7/1873
401	11	" " " "	3/9/1873 - 6/7/1873
402	12	" " " "	6/8/1873 - 7/1/1873
403	13	" " " "	9/6/1873 - 9/22/1873
404	14	" " " "	9/22/1873 - 9/30/1873
405	15	" " " "	9/30/1873 - 10/11/1873
406	16	" " " "	10/11/1873 - 2/10/1874
407	18	" " " "	4/13/1874 - 5/3/1874
408	19	" " " "	5/20/1874 - 7/15/1874
409	20	" " " "	7/17/1874 - 8/2/1874
410	21	" " " "	8/3/1874 - 8/4/1874
411	22	" " " "	8/22/1874 - 11/26/1874
412	23	" " " "	11/26/1874 - 12/21/1874
413	24	" " " "	12/21/1874 - 1/14/1875
414	25	" " " "	5/28/1872
415	[paper folder]	Index to books on Meridian Circle Work	1870-1886
416		Fundamental Stars for Zones B8	3/17/1873 - 12/1/1873
417		General Catalog. Obsns + Reductions B1	1871-72
418		Fundamental Stars. Obsns + Reductions. Final Values B1	1870-71
419		Mars, Mars Comparison Stars. ARIADNE Comp. Stars	1877
420		Flexure Constants. Equator Point Corrections	1874-75
421		Instrumental Constants 1870-71, depending on new Seltzowa Plates	
422		Barometer. Thermometer Runs. Collimation. Flexure	1870-79
423		Refraction Constants. B + T + S	1870-86
424		Obsns. w/ Meridian Circle on Zms 50° to 55°	11/16/1870 - 12/16/1870
425		" " " " " "	12/16/1870 - 3/28/1871
426		Misc. Tables. Formulae for Zone Reductions	1870-71
427		Misc. Obsns. Transit of Venus. Longitude Montreal - Cambridge	1883
428		Obsns of Tempul's Comet 1873, Asteroids 1873, Periodicity of Luling Machine	1877

	429		Ruling Machine Screws; Discovery of (112) and (109) + ephemerides	
	430		Asteroid 109 - Elements & Ephemeris 1877-78	
	431		Orbit of 109, 112 1871-74	
	432		112	
011	433		Planetary Positions (Heliocentric) 1750-1860	
	434		Star? lists (Zones)	
	435		Chronograph Record 5/27/1880 - 10/5/1880	
	436	A.G.?	Absolute Work Star List - Final List of Dates of Obsns. 1879-81	John A. Dunn
	437	Rogers' Work	" " Meridian Circle Obsns. 1879-81	Anna Winloe
012	438		" " Notebook 1898-1907	Selma C. Bo
	439		Posting Book 1897-1908	
	440	A.G.	Rogers' Abs. Work - notebook 1904-1911	John A. Dunn
	441		Special Light Curves with Photometer 1895-96	
	442		[Variable Stars ~1897]	
	443		Ephemerides of Variable Stars 1896-98	
	444		Measurement of Comp. Stars for Variable w/Photometer 1895-1901	
	445		[Variable Stars] ~1897-98	
	446	I	Obsns of Variable Stars 1890-91	Wm Maxwell Kee
	447	II	" " " 1891-	"
	448	III	" " " 1891-92	"
	449	IV	" " " 1892	"
	450	V	" " " 1892-93	"
01λ	451	VII	" " " 1894-95	"
	452	VI	" " " 1893-94	"
	453	VIII	" " " 1896-98	"
	454	IX	" " " 1898-1900	"
	455		" " " 1900	"
	456		Notebook of Visual Observations - SS Cyg, Nova Per 1899-1902 H.R. Colson, Jr	
	457		West Equatorial Observations 4/10/1898 - 5/12/1899 [SS Cyg]	
	458	R	Equatorial Work [Recond of 72 books]	
	459	R	Index - Also lists of Variables, etc.	
	460	R	Index	
013	461	R17	Rutherford Millimeter Plate Measurements, etc. 8/16/1877 - 7/25/1882	
	462	R18	Meteorological Observations, etc. 6/23/1880 - 8/20/1885	
	463	R19	Aug - Sept 1877	
	464	R20	Aug - Oct 1877	
1366. 868	465	R22	o Ceti, λ Cyg, S _____, β Persei 1838-1854	
	466	R23	1877-79	
013	467	R24	Photometer Reductions 1877	

	468	R25	Ephemerides of Saturn's and Jupiter's Satellites	
	469	R26	Errors of Circles, Misc. Obsns - W. Equatorial	1877-78
	470	R28	Misc. Obsns. and Reductions	c 1878
	471	R29	[Summary of Variable Stars]	1840-1862
	472	R30	5 Photometric Observations	1877
	473	R31	6 " "	1878
	474	R32	c 1878	
013	475	R33	Observations + Lists	1879-81
	476	R34	Form for Eq. Observations	1879
	477	R35	Prospective Work + Proposed Form of Publication - W. Equatorial	1874-81
	478	R43	7	1878
	479	R44	8	1878
	480	R45	14	1879
	481	R46	Photometric Obsns with W. Equatorial	1878-79
	482		" "	"
	483		Description of Procedures + Opt. Setups	
014	484		" " + Other Obsns	1879
	485		" " " "	1879-80
	486		" " " "	1879
	487		" " " "	1879-80
	488		Eclipses of Jupiter Satellites	1878-79
	489		Eye + Photom. Estimates of Standard Magn	1881
	490		Comet Reductions #1	1881
	491		" " #2	1880-83
	492	26		1881-82
	493	28		1882
	494		6 1/4 "	1882-83
	495		15" (?)	1884
	496		Comets	1882-88
	497		"	1882-85
	498		"	1883-87
	499		15" (?) Equatorial	1885
	500		Comets	1882-89
	501		"	1882-94
	502		"	1883-87
015	503		"	1885-88
	504		"	1888-89
	505		" Copies of telegrams	1889-98
	506		" (10)	1890

ECP?

Planets and Planets

J.R. Edmund

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122

Comets (9)
Journal (Construction of Dome, etc.)

Degenstein v. Zodiacal Light Obs'n's (Arequipa)
Comets
Journal (Arequipa) #2

Comets
Parallax Computations #2; Comets
Comets + Variable Star Obsns.
Comets (13)

Journal (Cambridge) #3
Variable Stars

Variable Stars 6" W. Eq.

Variable Stars (Arequipa)

Variable Stars
Telescope Mechanical Notes v. Self Seals

Variable Stars
Variable Star Observations
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1889-90
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1898-1900
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1899-1902
1900-1901
1901

R.W. Clifford

Andrew E. Douglass

Andrew E. Douglass
Wm B. Clymer

Wm B. Clymer
various
A.J. Cannon?

A.J. Cannon I
Chas. P. Howard

A.J. Cannon II

S.I. Bailey
"
"
A.J. Cannon

see KG 1346
372
including
017

129, 125 are
in KG 11366.374
and .375
017

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Notebook # 2

Are these
15" record books??

- 1901
- 1902-05
- 1901-05
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- 1901-02
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- 1902-3
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- 1903
- 1903-4
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- 1904
- 1904
- 1904-5
- 1905
- 1905
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- 1905
- 1905-6
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- 1906
- 1906-7
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- 1907

H. R. Colson

018	585	162
	586	163
	587	164
019	588	165
	589	166
	590	167
	591	168
	592	169
	593	170
	594	171
	595	172
	596	173
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	598	175
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	601	178
	602	179
	603	180
	604	181
019	605	182
	606	183
	607	184
	608	185
020	609	186
	610	187
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	615	191
	616	192
	617	193
	618	194
020	619	195
	620	196
	621	197
	622	198
	623	199

15" inch record books?

15" record

15" Equatorial

- 1907
- 1907
- 1907-8
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- 1908-9
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- 1909-10
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- 1910
- 1910-11
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- 1911
- 1911-12
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- 1912-13
- 1912-15
- 1915-16
- 1916
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- 1916
- 1916-17
- 1917
- 1917
- 1917
- 1917-18

624	200	15" Equatorial	1918
625	201	" "	1918
626	202	" "	1918-19
627	203	" "	1919-20
628	204	" "	1920-23
629	205	" "	1926-27
630	206	" "	1928-30
631	207	" "	1934-35
632	208	" "	1935-36
633	209	" "	1936
634	210	" "	1936
635	211	" " (also 12" record)	1936-39
636	212	" "	1936-37
637	1	12-in. Equatorial	1914
638		" "	1915-16
639		" "	1916-17
640		" "	1917-18
641		" "	1919
642		[Box of Papers] II Merens (Lemids)	1898-99 Araguiba Obs.
643		12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obsns	1919-20
644		" " " " "	1920
645		" " " " "	1920-21
646		" " " " "	1921
647		" " " " "	1921
648		" " " " "	1921
649		" " " " "	1921-22
650		" " " " "	1922
651		" " " " "	1922
652		" " " " "	1922-23
653		" " " " "	1923
654		" " " " "	1923
655		" " " " "	1923-24
656		" " " " "	1924
657		" " " " "	1924-25
658		" " " " "	1925
659		" " " " "	1925-26
660		" " " " "	1925-26
661		" " " " "	1926-27
662		" " " " "	1927

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.758 may be missing volume

	12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obs	1927-28	
	" " " " "	1928-29	
	" " " " "	1928-33	
	" " " " "	1934-35	
	" " " " "	1935-36	
1	[24" Clark Refractor?]	1905-06	Leon Campbell?
3		1907	
4		1907-08	
5		1908-09	
6		1909	
7		1909	
8		1909-10	
9		1910-11	
1	Photometric Observations	1872	C.S. Pierce
2	" "	1872	" "
3	" "	1872	" "
4	" "	1873	" "
5	" "	1873	" "
6	" "	1874	" "
7	" "	1874	" "
8	" "	1874-75	" "
	Experiments with Photometer	1872	C.S. Pierce
	η Centauri Spectral Study	1911	Leah B. Allen
1	Clusters - Spectrophotometric tracings	c 1930	Carol Jane Ange.
2	α Cyg, Vega	1930-36?	" " "
3	" "	"	" " "
4	h Per, NGC 463	"	" " "
5	Clusters	c 1932 +	" " "
6	Clusters	1934	" " "
1	Misc; Variables	1918-19	Mary ^D Applegate
2	Variables, Map of the Sky	1918-19	" "
4	Map of the Sky, Sequences for Orion Neb.	1919	" "
5	Asteroids + Novae	1919-20	" "
6	Novae + Variables	1920-21	" "
7	Map of the Sky	1920-21	" "
	Daily Journal (13" - Peru)	1889-90	S.I. Bailey
25	Double Stars; Planets	1894-96	" "
1	Misc.; Variables	1917-19	Dorothy W. Block
2	Spectrum Work	1917-19	" "

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702	3	o Ceti, Nova Aql 3	1917-19	Dorothy W. Blee
703	4	Variables	1918-19	" " "
704	6	Asteroids	1918-19	" " "
705	7	Variables	1919	" " "
706	1	Variable Stars + Meteors	1903	F.E. Brasch
707	1	Variable Stars	1896-98	S.E. Breslin
708	2	" "	1898	" "
709	3	" "	1898	" "
710	4	" "	1899	" "
711	5	" "	1901-02	" "
712	6	" "	1902	" "
713	7	" "	1902-03	" "
714	8	" "	1903	" "
715	9	" "	1903	" "
716	10	" "	1903	" "
717	11	" "	1903	" "
718	12	" "	1903-04	" "
719	13	" "	1904	" "
720	14	" "	1904	" "
721	15	" "	1904	" "
722	16	" "	1904	" "
723	17	" "	1904	" "
724	18	" "	1904-05	" "
725	19	" "	1905	" "
726	20	" "	1905	" "
727	21	" "	1905-06	" "
728	22	" "	1906	" "
729	23	" "	1906	" "
730	24	" "	1906	" "
731	25	" "	1906	" "
732	26	" "	1906	" "
733	27	" "	1907	" "
734	28	" "	1907	" "
735	29	" "	1907	" "
736	30	" "	1907-08	" "
737	[31]	" "	1908	" "
738	32	" "	1908	" "
739	33	" "	1909	" "
740	34	" "	1909-10	" "

028	781	V	Visual Observations	1902-03	
	782	VI		1903-04	
	783	VII		1904	
	784	VIII		1904-05	
	785	IX		1905-09	
	786	X		1906-07	
	787	XI		1907-09	Annie J. Cannon
	788			1911-39	" " "
	789	101	Notes for Reading Guest Book	1912-35	" " "
	790		Variable Stars, Longitude Determination	1862-82	Seth C. Chandler
stored under 11366. 1080	791				Ernst " "
	792		W Virginis I	1916	C.A. Chant
027	793		λ of Sp. lines in red region of stars	1926-27	C.T. Chase
	794	P.D. 1	Spectra of Novae	1926	Paul Jandovick
	795	P.D. 2			
	796	[72]	Journal - lat. + long. work	1896	Andrew E. Dingle
	797		Radiometric Book I	1937-38	
	798		Radiometry II	1939-40	Emerson
	799		" Program Bk I	1936-38	" "
	800		Galvanometry Book I	1937-38	
	801	1	Variable Stars	1890-92	W.P. Fleming
	802	2	" "	1892-94	" "
	803	3	" " ; Spectra	1892-94	" "
	804	4	" "	1893-98	" "
	805	5	" "	1894-95	" "
	806	6	" " ; Spectra	1895-99	" "
027	807	7	" "	1895-96	" "
	808	8	" "	1896	" "
	809	9	" "	1896-97	" "
	810	10	" "	1897-98	" "
	811	11	" "	1897-1902	" "
030	812	12	" "	1898-1903	" "
	813	13	" "	1898-1905	" "
	814	14	" "	1899-1905	" "
	815	15	" " ; Comp. Spectra	1903-07	" "
	816	16	" " " "	1908-10	" "
	817	17	" " ; Photometer	1905-08	" "
	818	18	Novae, Comets, Spectra	1906-11	" "
	819	19	Sp. Class; Misc Obsns.	1908-11	" "

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20	Hedger of LPV's	000339 - 095659	plates	W. P. Fleming
21	"	100661 - 185905	"	"
22	"	190048 - 235939	"	"
23	Cluster and Faint Stars		1904 - 11	"
	Nova Persei Reductions		1902	"
24	Variable Stars			"
	Measurements of Bright Line Spectra		1890	"
2	Reductions of Photographs Observations		1886-87	
3	"	"	1886-87	
4	"	"	1886	
5	"	"	1886	
6	"	"	1886-87	
7	"	"	-	
8	"	"	1886-87	
9	"	"	1886-87	
11	"	"	1887	
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15	"	"	1887	
16	"	"	1887	
17	"	"	1887	
18	"	"	1887-88	
19	"	"	1887	
20	"	"	1887-89	
21	"	"	"	
22	Catalog of E. Stars			
23	Description of Spectra		1887-88	
24	"		1887-89	
25	Catalog of E. Stars			
26	"			
27	Discordant Spectra; Remarks on Rejected Measures			
28	G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			
29	E " " "			
30	Description of Spectra			
31	G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			
32	Description of Spectra			
33	C Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates			
34	Catalog of I plates			

These may all be LUPF?

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35 Reductions of Photographs Observations 1888-90
 36 F + G Discordant Spectra
 39 Reduction of Photographs Observations
 40 Catalog of Plates Classes N, H, L; Peruvian Plates ~1889
 41 " " " C, D " " ~1889
 42 Objects of Interest on Spectrum Plates ~1889
 45 " " " " " " ~1890
 97 " " So. Bache Plates 1898-1907 W.P. Fleming
 49 Miscellaneous (Ecl., Solar, etc) 1890-91
 50 Discussion of Draper Catalog
 51 Measurement of Spectrum Plates - So. Draper Cat. 1890-92
 [52] Description of Spectrum Measures " " " 1890-93
 53 Discussion of Draper Catalog
 56 " " " "
 57 Catalog of Chart Plates (I-8")
 58 " " " "
 59 " " " (B. in Peru)
 61 1892
 62 1892-93
 63 1893
 64 1893
 65 1893
 67 1893
 68 1893
 69 1893-94
 70 1894-1903
 Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat. ~~B~~
 Spectra class C
 Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat 1894-1904
 Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III Stars
 " " " " " "
 Stellar Parallax Stars (13")
 Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III stars
 Constants in South Draper Catalog
 Reduction of Plates Having less than 4 Std. Stars.
 (15) Notes on Draper Cat; Accounts of Share-Holders of the Camera 5/1892
 81 Measures of Spect. Plates (South Draper Cat) 1903-04
 82 " " " " " " 1903
 83 " " " " " " 1903-04

all WPF?
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see 866	898	96	Objects of Interest - Bruce Spectrum Plates	1896-1909	
	899	98	" " - Northern	1898-1911	
	900	99	" " - So. Bache Plates	1907-1911	W.P. Flemin
	901	1	Variables + Halley's Comet		W.S. Frank
	902		Colors of 2149 Southern Stars		" "
	903	1	Variables		B.P.G.
	904	2	"	1912-29	"
034	905	3	"	1900-20	"
	906	4	"	1899-1927	"
	907	5	Spectrophotometry of B + O Stars		"
	908	6	New Variables	1899-1919	"
	909	7	Color Indices of Long Period Variables		"
	910	8	Spectrophotometry of B + Wolf-Rayet stars		"
035	911	9	Variable Stars	1900-27	"
	912		B Star Observations	1902	Mauds E. Harrison
	913		mc plates taken for Standard Magnitude	1908	" "
	914		Measurement of Variable Stars	1908	Margaret Harwood
	915		" widths of A + B Stars	1922	Marian A. Harwood
	916	4	Assorted Plate measurements	1912-18	" "
	917		5-in. Equatorial	1918	" "
	918	1	Variable Stars	1904-06	{Anson S. Lear Guy Hill
	919		Variable Star Observations	1889-1916	E.H. ?
	920		Color correction for tel. objectives	1878	Charles P. Houser
	921		Assorted Plate measurements		L. Hofraeger
	922		" " "	1928-30	"
	923	1	Measurements of Plates, Stars, etc.	1895-98	Edward S. Kin
035	924	2	Reductions of Measures	1899-	" "
	925	3	Notes: Photographic Instruments	1904-24	" "
	926	3	Measurements: Distances, Altitudes, Plates	1901-02	" "
	927	4	Assorted Plate Measurements	1902	" "
	928	5	Color distance measurements	1920	" "
	929	6	Schilt Photometry	1927-28	" "
	930		Photographic Measurement of Light	1897	
036	931		Computation Book No. 2	1916	Edward S. Kin
missing 1/1891	932	1	Photographic Magnitudes, Misc	1914-18	Henrietta S. Lozini
	933	2	Variables, Observations	1902-03	" "
	934	4	Examination of Plates	1903	" "
	935	5	Variables	1903	" "
	936		Phoebe	1904	" "

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 965 43
 966 44
 967 1
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Circumpolar Variables 1895-96 Henrietta S. Leavitt
 Variable Star Observations 1896 " "
 " " " + Plate measures 1896 " "
 " " " " " 1896 " "
 " " " " " 1902 " "
 Circumpolar Variables 1902-04 " "
 Variable Star Observations 1904 " "
 Miscellaneous Observations 1904-10 " "
 " " 1906-16 " "
 Discovery of New Variables 1907-08 " "
 Comparison Stars 1906-07 " "
 Observations of New Variables 1906-07 " "
 " " " 1907-14 " "
 Std. Photog. Magnitudes - T'plates 1907-09 " "
 " " " 1908-10 " "
 " Magnitudes 1909-14 " "
 Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole 1910-12 " "
 " " " 1910 " "
 " " " 1911-14 " "
 Miscellaneous Journal 1911-12 " "
 Miscellaneous 1911-14 " "
 Objects looked up by Request 1914-18 " "
 Standard Magnitudes 1914-19 " "
 Miscellaneous - Comp. Stars 1914-16 " "
 Catalogs (Comparison Stars) 1915-19 " "
 Miscellaneous (Variables) 1915-19 " "
 Discovery of New Variables 1916-20 " "
 Miscellaneous (esp. Novae) 1916-20 " "
 Standard Magnitudes 1919-21 " "
 Miscellaneous (Variables ^{incl. RV Sp.} 1905) 1920-21 H. S. Leavitt
 Miscellaneous Observations - Variables 1893-96 Evelyn F. Leavitt
 " " " MS 1896 " "
 " " " MS 1896 " "
 " " " MS 1896-97 " "
 " " " MS 1897-98 " "
 " " " WGen 1897-98 " "
 Measures of Eros (South Pole) 1899-1902 " "
 " New Sat. (Phoebe) of Saturn, Nova Sgr 1899-1906 " "
 Measures of M3, etc. 1902-03 " "

	976	26	Measures of Eros	1902-04	Evelyn F. Helan
038	977	27	Search for variables; measures	1902-03	" "
	978	28	" " "	1903-04	" "
See 11366.007	979	30	" " "	1904-07	" "
	980	31 a 32	" " "	1907-09	" "
	981	33	" " "	1904-10	" "
	982	34	Scale Measures (2p. instruction of ECP)	1907-10	" "
	983	37	" " "	1911-12	" "
038	984	35	" " "	1910-12	" "
	985	36	" " "	1910-11	" "
	986	38	" " "	1912	" "
	987	39	" " "	1913-14	" "
	988	40	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	989	41	Observing Book - M5	1913	" "
039	990	42	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	991	43	" " "	1913-14	" "
	992	44	" " and M5 Variables	1914-15	" "
	993	45	" " "	1913-14	" "
	994	46	" " "	1913-15	" "
	995	47	" " "	1914-15	" "
	996	48	" " "	1914-15	" "
	997	49	" " "	1915-17	" "
	998	50	" " "	1915-17	" "
	999	51	" " "	1915-17	" "
113.66	.000	53	Measures of Variables in M15	1917	" "
	.001	52	" " "	1916-17	" "
	002	54	" " "	1917-18	" "
	003	55	" " "	1917-18	" "
039	004	56	Observing Book	1918-	" "
	005	57	" " "	1918	" "
	006	58	Long Exposure H.S. Region + Series	1918-19	" "
	007	29	New Satellite of Saturn + N. Polar Seg.	1904-11	" "
	008	59	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1918-19	" "
	009	60	" " " " "	1919-	" "
040	010	61	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	011	62	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	012	63	" " " " "	1920	" "
	013	64	MF Series	1920	" "
	014	65	" " "	1920-21	" "

	015	66	MF Series	1921	Evelyn F. Ireland
	016	67	MC and A Plates	1921	" "
040	017	68	Large Magellanic Cloud	1921-22	" "
	018	1	MC Plates	1915-16	H.S. Locke
	019	2	" "	1915-16	" "
	020	3	" "	1916	" "
	021	4	" "	1916, 18	" "
	022	5	" "	1916-17	" "
	023	6	" "	1917	" "
	024	7	Misc. Plates (AC, etc.)	1917-18	" "
040	025	8	MC Plates	1917-18	" "
	026	9	" "	1917-18	" "
	027	10	B and MC Plates	1917-19	" "
	028	1	Observing Book	1910-19	J. C. M. → Johanna C.S. Mack
	029	2	" " (Scale Measures)	1913-18	" "
041	030	3	" " (MD Plates)	1913-19	" "
	031	5	" " (Misc. Plates)	1918-19	" "
	032	7	B Series	1919	" "
	033	8	Observing Book (B Series)	1919	" also attached M.K.?
	034	9	" " (Misc. Measures)	1919-20	" "
	035	10	Novae? (Maps of Sky, AC Plates)	1919-20	" "
	036	1	Observing Book - Variable Stars, etc.	1912-13	Genevieve F. Mattheu
	037	2	" " Scale Measures	1913	" "
	038	3	" " Series Measures	1913-16	" "
	039	4	" " Series, etc.	1914	" "
	040	5	" " Miscellaneous	1914-15	" "
	041	7	Circumpolar Variables	1914-15	" "
	042	8	" " (Est. of Mag.)	1914-15	" "
	043	9	Series Measures (Principally blue plates)	1915	" "
	044	10	" " (" yellow. ")	1915-16	" "
041	045	6	Circumpolar Variables	1914-16	" "
	046	11	" " (Est. of brightness)	1915-16	" "
	047	12	" " (overflow)	1915	" "
	048	13	" "	1916	" "
	049	14	" " (Record of Obs. on Photog's)	1916	" "
042	050		Tables of Ursa Majoris	1894-96	Antonia C. Maur.
MISSING 1/1991	051		Rotation of Primary Star + Separation of Satellites	1928-32	" "
MISSING 1/1991	052		Formulae for Reduction, Phases in HA & T	1918-22	" "
	053		(Loose Papers) β Lyrae + others	1933	" "

042	054	1	Obs. Book, Meas. of Variables + Standard Sq.	1912	Mollie E. O'Reilly
	055	2	Misc. Observations, Variables, Etc.	1914-17	" "
	056	3	Scale Meas. of Std. Regions on I series	1913-14	" "
	057	4	Circumpolar Variables - Meas. of Comp Stars	1914	" "
	058	5	MC Plates	1914	" "
	059	6	Meas. of Misc. Plates	1914	" "
	060	7	" " "	1914	" "
	061	8	MC + Misc. Plates	1914	" "
	062	9	" " "	1914	" "
	063	10	" " "	1914-15	" "
	064	11	" " "	1914-15	" "
042	065	12	" " "	1915-17	" "
	066	13	" " "	1915	" "
	067	14	" " "	1915	" "
	068	15	" " "	1915	" "
043	069	16	" " "	1915	" "
	070	17	" " "	1915-16	" "
	071	18	Southern and AS plates	1915-16	" "
	072	19	MC and Misc. Plates	1916-17	" "
	073	20	Miscellaneous	1916-17	" "
	074	21	Obs. Book -	1916-17	" "
	075	22	Southern plates	1916	" "
	076	23	Mostly southern regions	1916	" "
	077	24	" " "	1916-17	" "
	078	25	" " "	1917	" "
	079	26	" " "	1917	" "
	080	27	Miscellaneous	1917-18	" "
	081	28	"	1917-18	" "
082	29	Obs. book	1918	" Sloan	
083	30	Scale Measures	1918	" " "	
084	31	B series	1918	" " "	
043	085	32	Cat. Sc. Measures	1918	" " "
	086	33	For Cat. 1° square	1918	" " "
	087	34	Cat. 4° square	1918	" " "
44	088	1	8" Polar Equatorial	1910-12	Philip G. O'Reilly
	089	2	" " "	1912-13	" "
	090	3	" " " (Variables)	1913	" "
	091	1	Various Plate Measures		Cecilia H. Payne
	092	2	" " "		" "

044

093 3
094 4
095 5
096 6
097 7
098 8
099 9

Various Plate Measures
" " "
Wavelength Calculations
Apertured MC plates
Emission Lines, Apertured Spectra
Apertured Arcturus, Vega

c1926?

Cecilia H. Payne
" "
" "
" "

044

100 10
101 11
102 12
103 13

Microphotometer, General
Apertured Altair, Betelgeuse
Apertured c Stars + Others
Single Spectra (Capella, Rigel, Sirius, Altair)
Apertured β Cas

" "
" "
" "

104 14
105 15
106 16

General Ledgers
Line Photometry
Gaertner

" "
" "

045

107 17
108 18
109 20
110 22
111 24
112 25

Line Photometry
Plates
Apertured Mira, α Cyg, α Per
Pleiades Background
Mira, ξ UMa Summary
K Stars

" "
" "
" "
" "

113 26
114 27
115 28
116 29

Angstrom Magnitudes
Schilt Microphotometer
C Stars
" "

" "
" "
" "

045

117 30
118 31
119 32

" "
B Stars
C Stars

" "
" "
" "

120 35
121 36

Temperatures
Miscellaneous

" "
" "

046

122 37
123 38
124 39
125 40
126 42
127 43

Line Areas
Long Dispersion Spectrophotometry
Line Areas
K Stars
Line Contours; O stars
 $\mu \phi$ of C stars

" "
" "
" "
" "

127.1 52
128 56

Identifications (Sequences)
Various Plate Measurements

(Under C.H. Payne)

" "
" "

046

129 56
130 57

" " "
" " "

Madelen R. Day
Mary L. Miller
Helen M. Lewis

046
047
047
048

131	58	Various Plate Measurements	(under C. H. Payne)	Jenka Mohr
132	61	Ptm. Drating, Cluster Maps, Sequences		
133		Measures by Bond Astr. Club	under C. H. Payne 1928	
134		Various Plate Measures		
135		Miscellaneous	1897	Edward C. Pickers
136		Correspondance		E. E. Barnan
137	11	Progress of Draper Catalog		
138		Miscellaneous		
139		Various Plate Measures	1890-95	
140	1	Misc. Counts for Annual Report	1899-1900	Edward C. Pickers
141	2	" " " "	1908-18	" "
142	1	Misc. Memoranda	1902-12	" "
143	2	" " " "	1888-95	" "
144		Accident Book	1905-08	" "
145	2	Notebook		
146		Eye Estimates of Stellar Magn. - Instructions	1881	J. Smith
147		Plates + Observations		
148		Measures + Miscellaneous		? Edward C. Pickers
149		Eye piece Measurements	1877	Frank Wald
150		Financial Record + Other Computations	1906	? Edward C. Pickers
151		Eclipse Notebook	1888-1900	
152	45	Determinations of Parallax by Photoq. Means	1852	William H. Pickers
153	44	Preparations for Observing Total Eclipse	1886	" "
154		Various Essays	1878	" "
155		" "	1879	" "
156	1	Variables and Asteroids	1914-16	Susan Raymond
157	2	Eros Series Measures, Economic Scale Meas.	1916	" "
158	3	Circumpolar Variables	1916	" "
159	4	Asteroids	1911, 17	" "
160	5	Asteroids, Misc.	1917	" "
161		Misc. Observations (under H H Plashett)	1875-76	William A. Roge
162		Plates (Nova Aquilae)	1918	Arthur R. Say
163		M-determinations		" "
164		Variable Star Observations	1909-10	L. G. Schmittz
165		Observations of Nebulae	1900	Delisle Stevan
166		Plate Measures	1923?	Rufus O. Sate
167		" "		
168		Obs. + Calc. - Ecogographical Position	1897?	Winslow W. H.
169	9	Latitude + Longitude, Arequipa Station	1896?	" "

	170	1	Scale Measures-series + Chart Plates	1917-18	Mary H. Van
	171	2	Observations of Novae	1917-18	" "
	172	3	" "	1918 -	" "
	173	4	" "	1918	" "
044	174	1	Double Star Measures	1876	Leonard Wald
	175		Correspondance	1896-97	Anna Wentz
	176		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1911-13	Ada E. Woods
	177		SS Cygni	1917	" "
	178	1	Instructions, et c.	1915	" "
	179		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1913-17	" "
	180	4	Cluster Variables	1916	" "
	181	5	" "	1917-18	" "
	182	6	" "	1919-23	" "
049	183	7	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919	" "
	184	8	Objects suspected as Novae	1919	" "
	185	9	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919-20	" "
	186	10	Objects looked up for outsiders by request	1921	" "
	187	11	New Variables	1921-22	" "
	188	12	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
	189	13	Examination of Northern Regions	1920	" "
	190	14	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
	191	15	" " " "	1920-21	" "
	192	16	Objects suspected as Novae	1921	" "
	193	17	Special Objects	1922	" "
049	194	18	Examination of Southern Regions	1922	" "
	195	19	New Variables	1922?	" "
	196	20	Special Examination of MC Plates	1922-23	" "
	197	21	Nebulae and Asteroids	1923	" "
	198	22	Cluster Variables	1923	" "
	199	23	" "	1922-23	" "
	200	24	Special Examination of MC Plates	1923	" "
	201	25	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922	" "
050	202	26	Special Examination of MC Plates	1921-24	" "
	203	27	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1925-28	" "
	204	28	" " " "	1924-25	" "
	205	29	New Variables	1924-26	" "
	206	30	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1924-25	" "
	207	31	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
	208	32	Misc. Milky Way Regions	1925	" "

	209	33	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922-24 ^{02 04?}	Ida E. Woods
	210	34	Milky Way Regions, MC+MF Plates	1926-30	" "
	211	35	Interesting Objects, Suspected Variables	1926	" "
	212	36	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1926	" "
050	213	37	" " " "	1926	" "
	214	38	" " " "	1926	" "
	215	39	New Variables	1926	" "
	216	40	Misc Milky Way Regions	1927-28	" "
	217	41	" " " "	1926	" "
	218	42	" " " "	1926	" "
051	219	44	Objects looked up for outsiders	1926	" "
	220	45	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
	221	46	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1929	" "
	222	47	Dr. Gerasimovic, T Pyx, Shapley LPV's	1927	" "
	223		Spectrophotometry, Schilt Measures	1931	G. Maulbetsch
	224		" " "	1931	"
	225		" " "	1932	"
	226	140	Variables and Misc.	1905	Oliver C. Wendell
	227		A B plates	1934	G. Maulbetsch
	228	4	Spectrophotometry	1933	"
	229		Computation of Ephemerides	1904-07	? Oliver C. Wendell
	230	1	Notes on Orion Cluster, Interstars, B stars		CHL
	231		Star Sequences	1926	
051	232		RB Standard Star Identifications		JME + MM
	233	3	Chart Plates	1898-99	Louisa D. Wells
	234	1	T Andromedae	1916	H.C. Wilson
	235		Doubtful Variable, Misc. Obsn's	1904-12	
	236		Psychrometer Record	1916	W.
	237		" "	1917	
052	238		Variable Star Observations	1902-03	
	239	1	" " "	1903	Marion F. Michael
	240	1	" " "	1904	G.E.W.
	241	"	Meridian Photometer	1907	S.M.P.
	242		Halley's Comet Observations	1909	
	243		Reduction of Observations for Position	1909-10	Oliver C. Wendell " H.C.
	244	3	Nova Aquilae	1918	
	245		Comparison Stars	1906-09	
052	246		Calculations - Schaefer + Others	1905, 1911	
	247	1	24-in reflector journal	1907	

all added
296

052	248		Plates, Photometers	1935-36	J. E. Jones	
	249	94	RH Plates - Photometry	1933		
	250		Variable Observations	1907-08		
	251		SV Tauri	1925	C. Lanoszko	
	252	1	Observations	1909	Samuel C. Carter	
	253	12	Meridian Photometer	1908		
	254	22	Jupiter Eclipses, Variable Stars	1898		
	255	23	" " " "	1899		
	256	49	New Variables	1926-28	Ida E. Wood	
	257	54	Evening Cloud Record	1916-17		
053	258		Shade Glasses	1902-03	C. M. Almeter	
	259	60	Pole Plates (MC) + Misc Experiments		F. Schult	
	260	62	Photometric Experiments	1929		
	261	63	Variable Star Observations, Photm.	1929		
	262	64	" " " "	1929		
	263	65	" " " "	1929		
	264	66	" " " "	1929		
	265	67	" " " "	1929	F. Schult	
	266	68	" " " "	1929	"	
	267	69	" " " "	1929	"	
	268	71	" " " "	1929	"	
	269	72	" " " "	1929	"	
	270	73	" " " "	1929	"	
	271	74	" " " "	1930	"	
	053	272	75	" " " "	1930	"
		273	76	RH plates	1930	"
		274	77	" "	1930	"
		275	78	" "	1930	"
276		79	" "	1930	"	
277		80	" "	1930-31	"	
278		81	" "	1931	"	
279		82	" "	1931	"	
280		83	" "	1931	"	
281		84	" "	1931-32	"	
054	282	85	" "	1932	"	
	283	86	" " PTM	1932	"	
	284	87	" " "	1932	"	
	054	285	88	" " "	1932	"
		286	89	" " "	1932	"

054	287	90	RH Plates	PTM	RB	1932	F Schilt
	288	91	" "	"	"	1932-33	"
	289	92	" "	"	"	1933-34	"
	290	93	" "	"	"	1933	"
	291	95	" "	"	"	1933	"
	292	96	" "	"	"	1933-34	"
	293	97	" "	"	"	1934	
	294	98	" "	PTM	RB	1934	
	295	99	" "	"	"	1934	
		296		Equatorial Observations		1877	
		297		Equator Points, Meridian Observations		1877	
055	298		Telescope Observations		1878		
	299	R45	Reduction of Photometric Observations		1878		
	300	R47	"	"	1878		
	301	R48	11	Variable Star Observations, Red'n of Phot Obs.		1878	
	302	R50	12	"	"	1878-79	
	303	R51	13	"	"	1879	
	304	R54	15	"	"	1879	
	305	R55	16	"	"	1879	
	306	R91	17	"	"	1879-80	
	307	R92	18	"	"	1880	
	308	R93	19	"	"	1880	
055	309	R95	21	"	"	1880-81	
	310	R96	22	"	"	1881	
	311	R98	23	"	"	1881	
	312	R99	24	"	"	1881	Hensch. G. Wolf
	313	R103	29	"	"	1882	
	314	R104	30	"	"	1882-83	
	315	R107		"	"	1883	
		316	38	"	"	1884	
		317		"	"	1885	
		318		"	"	1885-97	
		319		"	"	1885-86	
056	320				1886-87		
	321a		"	"	1888		
	321b		"	"	1888		
	322a		"	"	1888		
	322b		"	"	1888-89		
	323		"	"	1889		

054

055

056

Dec 11365. 981

Various?
Variable Star Observations

324				1889
325	57	"	"	1889-90
326		"	"	1891
327		"	"	1891
328	61	"	"	1891-92
329		"	"	1893
330		"	"	1893
331		"	"	1894
332		"	"	1895
333	78	"	"	1895
334	82	"	"	1895
335	83	"	"	1896
336	84	"	"	1896
337	85	"	"	1896
338	86	"	"	1896
339	87	"	"	1897
340	88	"	"	1897
341	89	"	"	1897
342	90	"	"	1897
343	91	"	"	1897
344	92	"	"	1897
345	93	"	"	1897
346	95	"	"	1898
347	96	"	"	1898
348	97	"	"	1898
349	98	"	"	1898
350	99	"	"	1898
351	100	"	"	1898
352	101	"	"	1898
353	102	"	"	1898
354	103	"	"	1898
355	104	"	"	1899
356	105	"	"	1899
357	106	"	"	1899
358	107	"	"	1899
359	108	"	"	1899
360	109	"	"	1899
361	110	"	"	1899
362	111	"	"	1899

056
See K5-11365
531-533

057

See K6-11365
539

057

058

W. A. Pickering

continued in
K.G. 1136.5.545

058

058

059

059

060

363	112	Various? Variable	Star Observations	1899
364	113	"	" "	1900
365	114	"	" "	1900
366	115	"	" "	1900
367	116	"	" "	1900
368	117	"	" "	1900
369	118	"	" "	1900
370	119	"	" "	1900
371	120	"	" "	1900
372	121	"	" "	1900-01
373		Chronograph Record, Zone Stars, 24-in		1877
374	124	Variable Star Observations		1901
375	125	" "		1901
376	A1	General Catalog, Circle Readings		1871-72
377	A2	"	" "	1871-72
378	A3	"	" "	1871-73
379	A4	Polar Catalog,	" "	1872-73
380	A5	"	" "	1872-73
381	A6	"	" "	1872-73
382	A7	General Catalog,	" "	1874-75
383	A8	"	" "	1874-75
384	A9	"	" "	1874-75
385	A10	"	" "	1874-75
386	A11	"	" "	1874-75
387	A12	"	" "	1874-75
388	A13	Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars for Zone		1876
389	A14	"	" "	1876
390	A15	"	" "	1877
391	A16	Mushelyne Fund. Stars, Circle Readings		1877
392	A17	Circle Readings, Zone Fundamental Stars		1877
393	A18	"	" Fundamental Stars	1878
394	A19	"	" Coast Survey Catalog	1878
395	A20	"	" Fundamental Stars	1879
396	A21	"	" "	1879
397	A22	"	" "	1879
398	A23	"	" "	1879
399	A24	"	" "	1879-80
400	A25	"	" "	1880
401	A26	"	" "	1880

060

402 A27
 403 A28
 404 A29
 405 A30
 406 A31
 407 A32
 408 A33
 409 A34
 410 A35
 411 A36
 412 A37
 413 A38
 414 A39
 415 A40
 416
 417 A43
 418 B1?

060

419
 420 B3
 421 B4
 422 B5
 423 B6
 424 B7
 425 B8
 426 B9

061

427 1
 428 2
 429 3
 430 4
 431 5
 432 6
 433 B1
 434 B2
 435 B3
 436 B4
 437 B5
 438 B6
 439 B7
 440

061

Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars 1880

" " " " 1880

" " " " 1880-81

" " " " 1881

" " " " 1881

Fundamental Stars, Observations 1881

" " " " 1881-83

Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars 1883

" " " " 1883

" " " " 1883

" " " " 1883

" " " " 1883-84

" " " " 1884

" " Fund + Zone Stars 1884-85

" " " " " 1885

" " " " " 1885-86

" " " " " 1877

Observation for Inclination of Declination Wire 1878-79

Polaris Circle Readings + Observations 1879

" " " " " 1879-80

" " " " " 1880

" " " " " 1880-81

" " " " " 1881-82

" " " " " 1883-84

" " " " " 1884

Zone measurements 1882

Revision of Equatorial Zone 1883

" " " " " 1883

" " " " " 1883

" " " " " 1883

" " " " " 1883

Fundamental Stars for Zones 1870-71

" " " " " 1871

" " " " " 1871

" " " " " 1871

" " " " " 1872

" " " " " 1872

" " " " " 1872

" " " " (Obsns + Reductns) 1870-71

WSR + AM

(Augustus
McConee?)

	441	F11
061	442	F12
→	443	F13
	444	F14
	445	F15
062	446	F16
	447	F17
	448	F18
	449	F19
	450	F20
	451	F21
	452	F22
	453	F23
	454	F24
	455	F26
	456	F27
	457	F28
	458	F29
	459	F30
	460	F31
	461	F32
	462	F33
	463	F34
062	464	F35
	465	F36
	466	F37
	467	F38
→	468	F39
	469	F40
	470	F41
063	471	F42
	472	F43
	473	F44
	474	F45
	475	F46
	476	F47
	477	F48
	478	F49
	479	F50

Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions

"	"	"	"	—
"	"	"	"	—
"	"	"	"	—
General Catalog	"	"	"	1871-72
"	"	"	"	1871
"	"	"	"	1871-72
"	"	"	"	1871
"	"	"	"	1871-72
"	"	"	"	1871-72
"	"	"	"	1871-72
"	"	"	"	1871-72
"	"	"	"	1872
"	"	"	"	1872
"	"	"	"	—
Polar Catalog	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1872-73
"	"	"	"	1874-75
General Catalogue	"	"	"	—
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
"	"	"	"	1874-75
Fundamental Stars	"	"	"	1876-77
"	"	"	"	1876-77
"	"	"	"	1876-77

063
 480 F51
 481 F52
 482 F53
 483 F54
 484 F55
 485 F56
 486 —
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 487 F57
 488 F59
 489 F60
 → 490 F61
 491 F62
 492 F63
 064
 493 F64
 494 F65
 495 F66
 496 F67
 497 F68
 498 F69
 499 F70
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 502 F73
 503 F74
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 506 F77
 507 F78
 508 F79
 064
 509 F80
 510 F81
 511 F82
 512 F83
 → 513 F84
 514 F85
 065
 515 F90
 516 F89
 517 F88
 518 F87

Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions 1876-77
 " " " " 1876-77
 " " " " 1876-77
 " " " " 1877
 " " (+2ms) " " 1877
 Maskelyne Fundamentals 1877
 Meridian Circle 1875
 Maskelyne Fundamentals 1877
 Fundamental Stars 1878
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 Coast Survey Catalog 1878
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 Miscellaneous Stars 1878
 Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions 1879
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065
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066
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519 F86
 520 E1
 521 E2
 522 E4
 523 E5
 524 E6
 525 E7
 526 E8
 527 E9
 528 E10
 529 A1
 530 A2
 531 A3
 532 A4
 533 A5
 534 A6
 535 C6'
 536 A7
 537 A8
 538 A9
 539 A10
 540 A11
 541 A12
 542 A13
 543 A14
 544 A15
 545 A16
 546 A17
 547 A18
 548 A19
 549 A20
 550 A21
 551 A22
 552 A26
 553 A25
 554 A23
 555 B1
 556 B2
 557 B3

Fundamental Stars, Observations & Reductions
 Flexure, Collimation Errors

Zone Chronograph Records

Zone Circle Readings
 Zone Chronograph Records

Polaris, Observations & Reductions

1882
 1879
 1879-80
 1880-81
 1881
 1881-83
 1883
 1883-84
 1884
 1885-86
 1870
 1870
 1871
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 1871-72
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 1872-73
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 1873-74
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 1874-75
 1875
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 1875
 1875-76
 1876
 1876-77
 1878-79
 1877-78
 1877
 1879
 1879-80
 1880

066

558 B4
559 B5
560 B6
561 B2
562 B3

Polaris, Observations + Reductions

" " "
" " "
" " "
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1880-81
1881
1881-83
1883
1883-84

066

563 C1
564 C2
565 C3
566 C4
567 C5
568 C6
569 C7

Zone Observations + Reductions

" " "
" " "
" " "
" " "
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" " "

1870
1870-71
1871
1871
1871
1871

067

570 C8
571 C9
572 C10
573 C11
574 C12

missing?

575 C13
576 C14
577 C15
578 C16
579 C17

" " "
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1871
1871
1871
1871
1871-72
1872
1872-73
1873
1873

067

580 C18
581 C19
582 C20
583 C21
584 C22

" " "
" " "
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" " "

1873-74
1873
1874
1874
1874

585 C23
586 C24
587 C25
588 C26
589 C27

" " "
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1874
1874
1874
1874
1874-75

590 C28
591 C29
592 C30
593 C31
594 C32
595 C33
596 C34

67

" " "
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1875
1875
1875
1875
1875
1875-76
1876

067
 597 C35
 598 C36
 599 C37
 → 600 C38
 601 C39
 068
 602 C40
 603 C41
 604 C42
 605 C43
 606 C44
 607 C45
 608 C46
 609 C47
 610 C48
 611
 612 F91
 613 F92
 614 F96
 615 F97
 616 F98
 617 F99
 618 F100
 068
 619 F101
 620 F102
 621
 622
 → 623
 624
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 633
 069
 634
 635 J20

Zone Observations + Reductions

"	"	"	"	1876
"	"	"	"	1877
"	"	"	"	1877
"	"	"	"	1877
"	"	"	"	1877
"	"	"	"	1877
"	"	"	"	1877-78
"	"	"	"	1878
"	"	"	"	1878-79
"	"	"	"	1883
"	"	"	"	1883-84
"	"	"	"	1884
"	"	"	"	1884-85
"	"	"	"	1885
"	"	"	"	1885

Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions

"	"	"	"	1883
"	"	"	"	1883-84
"	"	"	"	1884
"	"	"	"	1885
"	"	"	"	1885
"	"	"	"	1885-86

Polar Catalog, Observations + Reductions

"	"	"	"	1885
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Collection of Results in Order of Dates

Readings of the Sun	1879-81
Observations of the Sun	1879
Error of Frodsham 1327	1879

"	1903-04	M. F. Michael, W. W. White
"	1904-05	"
"	1905	"
"	1905-06	"
"	1906-07	J. A. Dunne + W. H.
"	1907-08	W. H.
"	1908	"
"	1901	J. A. Dunne
"	1899-1900	"
"	1896-98	"
"	1902-03	J. A. Dunne, M. F. Michael

Chronograph Record

1879-	W. A. Rogers
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$J_1 + J_2$
 are 11366. and
 871
 872
 069
 missing 1/1991
 missing 11/1991
 069
 070
 070
 070

636 J3
 637 J4
 638 J5
 639 J6
 640 J7
 641 J8
 642 J9
 643 J10
 644 J11
 645 J12
 646 J13
 647 J14
 648 J15
 649 J16
 650 J17
 651 J18
 652 J19
 653 J21
 654 J22
 655 J24
 656 J25
 657 J26
 658 J27
 659 J28
 660 J29
 661 J30
 662
 663
 664
 665
 666
 667 T6
 668
 669 T.9
 670
 671
 672
 673
 674 K1

Chronograph Record

Reports, Meteorological Notes

" " "
 " " "
 " " "
 North Pole Reductions
 South Pole Reductions
 Variable Stars, Computations
 Tabulations of Observations of Variable Stars
 Memoranda and Reminders
 Bright Double Stars, Working Lists
 Current Relative + Absolute Estimate, Variable Stars
 Variable Stars, Computations
 Ephemerides of Variable Stars
 Clock Errors, Instrumental Constants

1871	A. McCannell
1871	"
1872	W. A. Rogers
1872	"
1872-73	"
1873	"
1873-74	"
1874	"
1874-75	"
1875	"
1875-76	"
1876	"
1876	"
1876-77	"
1877	"
1877	"
1878-79	"
1879-80	"
1880	"
1880-81	W. V. Brown
1881	"
1881	"
1881-82	"
1883	"
1883	"
1883-84	"
1889-94	"
1886-88	"
1883-85	"
1897-1901	"
1896-1902	"
1895, 97, 1901	"
1903	"
1896?	"
1896	"
1899	"
1902	"
1871-72	W. A. Rogers A. McCannell

070
071
071
072

675 K2
676 K3
677 K4
678 K5
679 K6
680 K7
681 K9
682 K10
683 K12
684 K13
685 K14
686 K15
687 K16
688 K17
689 K18
690 K19
691 K20
692 K21
693 K22
694 K23
695 K26
696 K27
697 K28
698 J1
699 J2
700 J3
701 J4
702 J5
703 J6
704
705
706 D4
707 D8
708 D9
709 D10
710 R14
711 R17
712 R18
713 R27

Clock Errors, Polar Catalog, Instrumental Constants	1872-73	
" " General " " "	1874-75	
" " " " "	1878-79	
" " " " "	1883	
Equator Points, Corrections	1871-73	
" " " " Flexure, Polar Cat.	1872-73	
" " " " Constants	1878	
Equator Pt. from Obsns of $\alpha + \Delta \mu$	1876	W.A. Rogers + JEM
Copy of Instrumental Constants 1870-71; Redetermin. of $\Delta T, m, h$	1870-78	
Instrumental Constants depending on Pulkovo Coordinates	1871-72	
" " " " " "	1872-73	
" " " " " "	1873-74	
" " " " " "	1875	
" " " " " "	1876	
" " " " " "	1877	
" " " " " "	1877	
Final Values of $\Delta T, m + \text{Req.}$ for Reduction of Zone Obsns	1870-74	
" " " " " "	1874-78	
" " n and c	1872-76	
" " " " " 1870-72	1876-78	
Meridian Circle Constants, A, Star Constants	1872	W.A. Rogers
Instrumental Constants, Star Constants	1876	JEM
Inclination of Declination Wires	1877	JFV
DM places for 1855 + 1875; Zone Obs'ns, Final Red'ns		
" " " " " " " " " "		
" " " " " " " " " "		
" " " " " " " " " "		
" " " " " " " " " Supplement List	1883-85	
DM List $+53^\circ +54^\circ$	1883	
" " $+50^\circ +51^\circ +52^\circ$		
Thermometer, Barometer Runs	1873	
" " " " " "	1875	
" " " " " "	1875-76	
" " " " " "	1876	
Planet + Satellite Observations		
Star Observations	1877-78	
" " " " " "	1877-78	
" " " " " "	1869 + before	

072
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714	R67	Meteorological Record	1880-82	
715		10 Notes on S.M.P.	1892	
716		12 Micrometer Level	1877	
717		17 Reduction of Observations by Schmidt by Reed		
718		33 Early lists of Gaseous Neb, Stars, Pec. Spectra	1880	
719		34 Discussion of H.A. 24, Graph M.P. accord to DM		
720		35 " " " " " " " " " " " "		
721		38 Stars + Clusters, Lists with X Plates Entered	1899	
722		Double Stars		
723		" "		
724		Asteroid Zone Book		
725	#3	Eros Book	1893	
726	#4	" "	1876	
727		Zone Stars	1870	
728	U4	Russian Transit Recordings		
729	U5	Zone Circle Readings	1870	
730	U6	" " " "		
731	U7	" " " "	1871	
732	U10	D.M. List		
733	U	Brown's Note Book	1880	
734	U	Record of work by D.B. Pratt	1883-84	D.B. Pratt
735	U14	Stars (Zone) Needing Re-examination of chronograph sheets	1871	
736	U15	Stars to be re-observed		
737	U16	Star places	1875.0	
738	U17	1 K'K d d'		
739	U18	3 " "		
740	U19	Zero stars, Red. to apparent place		
741	U20	Table for Reductions		
742	U22	Fundamental Stars, Ephemerides	1879	
743	U23	" " " "	1879	
744	U24	Working Lists, Fundamental Stars	1879	
745	U25	" " " "	1879	
746	U27	Longitude Campaign - Obs. + Red.	1872-73	
747	U28	Miscellaneous Observations	1881	
748	U30	Montreal - Cambridge Longitude Observations	1883	
749	U31	Longitude Campaign: Montreal - Cambridge	1883	
750	U34	General Catalog List		
751	U37	? (Bork)	1875	W.A. Rogers
752		Missing		

073

753 U40
754 U41
755
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761

Chronograph Record
List of Polar stars w/ dates of Obs
Flexure Collimation Runes
Investigations of Circle Observations
Longitude of Circle Errors
Investigation of Circle - Discussion
" of Errors of West Circle from Stops
" of Circle
" Observations

1885
1880
1879
1881
1884
1877-79
1871-79

W.C.

074

762
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Investigation of Errors of West Circle for Stops
" " " " "
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" " " " "
Investigation of Circle Observation
Jupiter Ecl. + Var. Stars
" " " "
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1884-85
1885
1885
1885
1879
1900
1902
1894
1903

R.W.L.

771
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774
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778
779

Various? Stars Zone P.M. XI
" " " " XII
Arequipa Time Book No. 1
Chronograph Comparisons
Comparison of Waltham Clock w/ South Clock
Error of sidereal Clock
" "
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1891-92
1892
1878
1908
1913
1911
1910

J.A. Dunne
+ W.W.
W.A. Rogers
W.H.
+ J.A. Dunne
Philip O'Reilly
" "
" "

074

780
781
782
783
784

Observations
Time Book
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1876
1875
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1874

W.A. Rogers
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785
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787

Time Service [Clock Errors?]
Clock Errors
Time Service
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1879
1878
1888-90

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075

788
789
790
791

" "
" "
" " + Russian Transit
Check Readings of Sheets of Obs. for Longitude

1890-91
1891
1877
1871

J.A. Dunne
" "
L. Waldor
H. Gannett

	792	Russian Transit	1883	
	793	Time Service, Clock Errors + Russian Transit	1877	L. Waldo
075	794	" " " " " "	1877	"
	795	" " Clock Comparisons	1881	F. Waldo
	796	Level of East Transit	1877	L. Waldo
	797	Time Service	1887-88	
	798	" "	1882-83	
	799	" "	1892-94	J.A. Dunne
	800	" "	1880	Harriet Wace
	801	" " Clock Comparisons	1879-80	F. Waldo
075	802	" " " "	1878-79	L. Waldo
	803	Reference Book: Stars, Asteroids, etc. under observation		
	804	Errata in Rogers' AGC Catalogue	1904	J.A. Dunne
	805	Meridian Circle - General Record	1879-80	W.A. Rogers
	806	Constellations		
MISSING 4/1991	807	Working List of Star Data	1871	
076	808	" " " " for 1880	1880-81	
	809	Constellation Data	1879-80	
	810	Reduction of Bonn Observations from 1855 to 1875		
	811	Discordant Stars		
	812	Reports on Obsn of Stars in N. Hemisphere to 9 th mag, Pickers	1879	
	813	Star Reduction	1890	
	814	Measure of Plates	1890	
	815	No. 2 Computations - long chat of Bolivian + Peruvian Stations	1894	
	816	Zone Observations	1883-84	
	817	No. 1 Measurements: WA Rogers Micrometer	1894-97	
	818	Sun Images	1880	
	819	Miscellaneous Notes		D.C. Baird
	820	Chronograph Sheet Readings	1884	Baird
076	821	Computation of Residuals		
	822	Corrections for Error	1869-70	
	823	Observations of Southern Variable Stars	1899-1904	
	824	Nautical Almanac	1883	
	825	Lunar Brightness	1881	
	826	XII 12-in Horizontal Telescope records	1899	
	827	Satellite IV	1888-90	
77	828	Reductions		
	829	Bibliography		
	830	Observations + Reductions Part II	1876	

	831		Observations + Reductions, Part III	1876	
	832		Re-readings of Chronograph sheets	1880	
077	833		Investigations of Division Errors of Circle "East"	1880-81	
	834		Chronograph Readings	1881	H. Stevens
	835		Readings of Chronograph sheets	1879	L. Waldo
	836		Star Data	1884-85	
	837		" "	1882	
	838		Star + Comet Data	1881-84	P.C. Ricketts
	839		Reductions	1880-81	S.C. Chandler
	840		Comet Data + Comparison Stars	1881	
	841		Time Service	1885-86	W.A. Rogers
077	842		Dates of Observations of Zone Stars for 1883+1884		
	843		Miscellaneous Star Observations		
	844		Star Observations		
	845		Zone Observations	1884	
	846		Fundamental Zone Stars Circle Readings	1885	
	847	J 2	Current Observations of Variable Stars	1895-96	
	848		Record of Observations	1898-99	F.W. Thorer
	849		Variable Star Observations	1899-1900	H.C. Bailey
	850		Absolute Work Runs 1879, 80, 81	1898-99	
078	851		(Variable Stars)	1883-84	
	852		West Dome 6 1/4"	1883	S.C. Chandler
	853		" " "	1883	
	854		" " "	1896-98	
	855		Wedge Zones	1887	
	856		Correction to Ephemeris - Jupiter's Satellites		
	857		Final Adopted Maps: Comp Stars for Variables	c 1901	
	858		" " " " "	c 1900	
	859		Variables + Other Stars - Naked Eye Obsns.	1889-1890	
	860		Variable Star Observations	1894-95	H.C. Bailey
	861	19	Variable Stars	1898-99	
078	862	18	Computation Book	1899-1900	
	863	17	" "	c 1902	
	864		Wedge Photometer Zone Stars	1894-	
	865		Meridian Photometry	1881-84	
	866		Multiplet Theory (H.N. Russell) - Notes	1925	
	867		Plates to be Examined re. Peters' Zones	1877-78	
	868	R 21	Equatorial Zones	1877	
079	869		Location of Comparison Stars for Variable	1894	

Harvard Lunar Plates

081

081

Note gaps

081

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948	LXXI	3536	3601
949	LXXII	3648	3649
950	LXXIII	3669	3783
951	LXXIV	3784	3811
952	LXXV	3812	3844
953	LXXVI	3846	3856
954	LXXVII	3857	4096
955	LXXVIII	4097	4239
956	LXXIX	4271	4272
957	LXXX	4295	4296
958	LXXXI	4297	4298
959	LXXXII	4303	4304, 4309
960	LXXXIII	4336	4374, 4375
961	LXXXIV	4423	4424, 4455
962	LXXXV	4456	4465, 4466
963	LXXXVI	4478	4481
964	LXXXVII	4503	4554, 4555
965	LXXXVIII	4571	4572, 4588
966	LXXXIX	4589	4619, 4620
967	XC	4677	4678, 4690
968	CX	7549	7571, 7572
969	CXI	7665	7666, 7677
970	CXII	7678	7692, 7693
971	CXIII	7965	7966, 7990
972	CXIV	8013	8014, 8052
973	CXV	8110	8288, 8289
974	CXVI	8299	8300, 8306
975	CXVII	8307	8316, 8317
976	CXVIII	8346	8347, 8362
977	CXIX	8635	8636, 8639
978	CXX	8640	8904, 8905
979	CXXI	8649	8650, 8690
980	CXXII	8728	8729
981	CXXIII	8726	8727, 8731
982	CXXIV	8732	8890, 8891
983	CXXV	9079	9080, 9086
984	CXXVI	9087	9193, 9194
985	CXXVII	9195	9249, 9250
986	CXXVIII	9263	9264, 9286

Mary Fowle

Martha C. Bor

Mary Fowle

Martha C. Bor

Howard Lunar Plates

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See 1068 for missing volume

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989	CXXXVII
990	CXXXVIII
991	CXXXIX
992	CXL
993	CXLI
994	CXLII
995	CXLIII
996	CXLIV
997	CXLV
998	CXLVI
999	CXLVII
1000	CXLVIII
1001	CXLIX
1002	CL
1003	CLI
1004	CLII
1005	CLIII
1006	CLIV
1007	CLV
1008	CLVI
1009	CLVII
1010	CLVIII
1011	CLIX
1012	CLX
1013	CLXI
1014	CLXII
1015	CLXIII
1016	CLXIV
1017	CLXV
1018	CLXVI
1019	CLXVII
1020	CLXVIII
1021	CLXIX
1022	CLXX
1023	CLXXI
1024	CLXXII
1025	CLXXIII

08λ

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10030	10031	10072
10073	10103	[10102]
10227	10228	10231
10232	10263	10264
10385	10386	10532
10533	10604	10760
10692	10693	10701
10702	10716	10718
10737	10738	10743
10746	10748	10753
10761	10933	10934
10605	10998	10999
11004	11006	11039
11160	[11161]	11197
11198	11201	11202
11208	11209	11218
11219	11276	11285
11286	11301	11302
11314	11315	11522
11331	11336	11337
11523	11542	11544
11549	11550	11580
11581	11597	11598
11636	11708	11709
11870	11871	11890
11891	11909	11910
11924	11925	11931
11932	11997	11998
12017	12018	12027
12028	12043	12044
12068	12069	12075

Martha C. Borth

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Ernestine Fuller

Martha C. Borth

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1026	CLXXIV	Harvard Lunar Plates	12076	12266	12267	Martha C. Borton
1027	CLXXV	"	12280	12281	12296	"
1028	CLXXVI	"	12301	12300	12297	Ernestine Fuller?
1029	CLXXVII	"	12323	12324	12469	"
1030	CLXXVIII	"	12470	12474	12475	"
1031	CLXXIX	"	12507	12508	12525	"
1032	CLXXX	"	12526	12723	12724	"
1033	CLXXXI	"	12740	12741	12774	"
1034	CLXXXII	"	12775	13018	13019	"
1035	CLXXXIV	"	13085	13274	13273	"
1036	CLXXXV	"	13109	13110	13124	Martha C. Borton
1037	CLXXXVI	"	13125	13143	13145	"
1038	CLXXXVII	"	13284	13285	13307	Ernestine Fuller?
1039	CLXXXVIII	"	13308	13329	13330	"
1040	CLXXXIX	"	13609	13611	13626	Martha C. Borton
1041	CXC	"	13627	13641	13642	"
1042	CXC1	"	13668	13669	13716	Ernestine Fuller?
1043	CXC11	"	13610	13645	13646	Martha C. Borton
1044	(193)	"	13717	13935	13936	Ernestine Fuller?
1045	(194)	"	13621	13622	13140	Martha C. Borton
1046	(195)	"	13142			"
1047	(196)	"	13331	13332	13305	Ernestine Fuller?
1048		" Plate characteristics	12017 - 144	55		
1049		Neptune Plates (Princeton?)	7099	7534		
1050		Neptune				
1051		Measures of halande 20406				Fowler
1052		?	4296	4295		"
1053		Neptune Plates				H. N. Russell
1054		Harvard Lunar Plates	Mc 650, etc.			H. N. Russell
1055		Supplementary Notes + Data				
1056		Hayn's Correction for plates of Oct 7, 1911				
1057		Harvard Lunar Plates	13306	12319	12320	Ernestine Fuller?
1058		Neptune Plates				Fowler
1059		Supplementary Notes	3535 - 11998			
1060		Harvard Lunar plates	14455			Ernestine Fuller
1061		"	14448	14449	14454	"
1062		"	14408	14416	14417	"
1063		"	14399	14400	14407	"
1064		"	14095	14131	14132	"

	1065		Howard Lunar Plates	14045	14046	14094	Ernestine Fuller
083	1066			13959	14027	14028	" "
	1067			13914	13915	13958	" "
(Ex longearlier)	1068	CXXVI		9421	9422	9460	" "
084	1069	Fisher	Fireballs - General; Index				PAMPHLET CASE
085	1070	"	Correspondence (Lunar Eclipse)				" "
086	1071	"	Bright Meteors Reported to HCO 1925-32				" "
087	1072	"	Fireballs, Lunar Eclipse				" "
088	1073	"	Meteors & Fireballs				" "
089	1074	"	Meteors (includes painting)				" "
090	1075	"	Meteors, Lunar Eclipse				" "
091	1076	"	Meteors, Fireballs				" "
092	1077	"	Meteors				" "
093	1078	"	Meteors				" "
094	1079	"	Meteors (Newspaper clippings)				" "
095	1080		Observations ~ 1881 ff. - Pickering & Chandler				" "
096	1081	Fisher	Meteor Reports, etc.				" "

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		Transit	Circle			
1	A1			11/7/1848	- 7/30/1849	
2	A2	"	"	7/30/1849	- 9/25/1849	
3	A3	"	"	9/26/1849	- 11/29/1849	*
4	A4	"	"	11/30/1849	- 2/6/1850	
5	A5	"	"	2/6/1850	- 4/30/1850	
6	A6	"	"	5/1/1850	- 10/20/1850	
7	A7	"	"	10/21/1850	- 12/26/1850	
8	A8	"	"	12/26/1850	- 4/3/1851	A
9	A9	"	"	4/3/1851	- 7/13/1851	
10	A10	"	"	7/13/1851	- 9/5/1851	*
11	A11	"	"	9/5/1851	- 1/15/1852	
12	A12	"	"	1/15/1852	- 6/28/1852	
13	A13	"	"	6/28/1852	- 12/5/1852	
14	A14	"	"	12/1/1852	- 7/8/1853	
15	A15	"	"	7/8/1853	- 2/26/1854	
16	A16	"	"	2/28/1854	- 8/15/1854	
17	A17	"	"	8/15/1854	- 11/29/1854	
18	A18	"	"	11/27/1854	- 1/25/1855	
19	A19	"	"	1/25/1855	- 5/6/1855	*
20	A20	"	"	5/6/1855	- 7/31/1855	
21	A21	"	"	8/1/1855	- 9/25/1855	
22	A22	"	"	9/25/1855	- 3/27/1856	
23	A23	"	"	3/27/1856	- 6/15/1856	
24	A24	"	"	6/16/1856	- 9/5/1856	
25	A25	"	"	9/8/1856	- 2/9/1857	
26	A26	"	"	2/17/1857	- 9/21/1857	
27	A27	"	"	9/21/1857	- 11/3/1857	
28	A28	"	"	11/3/1857	- 2/10/1858	
29	A29	"	"	2/10/1858	- 7/5/1858	
30	A30	"	"	7/5/1858	- 1/24/1859	
31	A31	"	"	1/24/1859	- 8/17/1859	
32	A32	"	"	8/17/1859	- 1/23/1860	
33	A33	"	"	1/23/1860	- 6/23/1860	
34	A34	"	"	6/23/1860	- 11/29/1860	
35	A35	"	"	11/29/1860	- 3/21/1861	
36	A36	"	"	3/21/1861	- 10/1/1861	
37	A37	"	"	10/1/1861	- 3/28/1862	
38	A38	Meridian	"	3/28/1862	- 5/7/1862	
39	A39	"	"	5/7/1862	- 8/6/1862	

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40 A40
 41 A41
 42 A42
 43 A43
 44 A44
 45 A45
 46 A46
 47 A47
 48 A48
 49 A49
 50 A50
 51 A51
 52 A52
 53 A53
 54 A54
 55 A55
 56 A56
 57 A57
 58 A58
 59 A59
 60 A60
 61 A61
 62 A62
 63 A63
 64 A64
 65 A65
 66 A66
 67 A67
 68 A68
 69 A69
 70 A70
 71 A71
 72 B1
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 77 B6
 78 B7

Meridian Circle

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8/11/1862 - 9/25/1862
 9/27/1862 - 12/8/1862
 12/10/1862 - 2/16/1863
 2/17/1863 - 5/25/1863
 5/26/1863 - 8/14/1863
 8/14/1863 - 9/22/1863
 9/23/1863 - 12/2/1863
 12/5/1863 - 1/11/1864
 1/11/1864 - 3/3/1864
 3/7/1864 - 4/29/1864
 4/9/1864 - 5/19/1864
 5/22/1864 - 6/6/1864
 6/7/1864 - 6/19/1864
 6/21/1864 - 7/5/1864
 7/6/1864 - 7/19/1864
 7/20/1864 - 9/9/1864
 9/10/1864 - 10/10/1864
 10/10/1864 - 11/4/1864
 11/10/1864 - 11/23/1864
 11/25/1864 - 12/20/1864
 12/30/1864 - 1/18/1865
 1/20/1865 - 2/1/1865
 2/2/1865 - 2/25/1865
 2/27/1865 - 4/3/1865
 4/3/1865 - 4/26/1865
 5/1/1865 - 6/2/1865
 6/3/1865 - 7/4/1865
 7/5/1865 - 7/18/1865
 7/20/1865 - 8/1/1865
 8/2/1865 - 8/28/1865
 8/29/1865 - 9/15/1865
 9/16/1865 - 9/30/1865
 1/1/1849 - 8/16/1849
 8/16/1849 - 12/7/1849
 12/7/1849 - 4/2/1850
 4/2/1850 - 10/5/1850
 10/5/1850 - 12/30/1850
 12/30/1850 - 4/5/1851
 4/5/1851 - 7/8/1851

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Reduction of Transits

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79 B8
 80 B9
 81 B10
 82 B11
 83 B12
 84 B13
 85 B14
 86 B15
 87 B16
 88 B17
 89 B18
 90 B19

Reduction of Transits

7/8/1851 - 9/4/1851
 " " 9/4/1851 - 11/11/1851
 " " 11/11/1851 - 2/25/1852
 " " 2/25/1852 - 7/6/1852
 " " 7/6/1852 - 11/17/1852
 " " 11/17/1852 - 5/1/1853
 " " 5/1/1853 - 11/2/1853
 " " 11/2/1853 - 4/4/1854
 " " 4/4/1854 - 8/9/1854
 " " 8/6/1854 - 11/27/1854
 " " 11/27/1854 - 1/30/1855
 " " 1/30/1855 - 5/6/1855

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91 B20
 92 B21
 93 B22
 94 B23
 95 B24

" " 5/6/1855 - 8/1/1855
 " " 7/31/1855 - 9/25/1855
 " " 9/25/1855 - 3/30/1856
 " " 3/30/1856 - 6/11/1856
 " " 6/11/1856 - 8/22/1856

003

96 B25
 97 B26
 98 B27
 99 B28

" " 8/22/1856 - 11/20/1856
 " " 11/20/1856 - 4/30/1857
 " " 4/30/1857 - 10/4/1857
 " " 10/4/1857 - 11/28/1857

100 B29
 101 B30
 102 B31
 103 B32

" " 11/28/1857 - 2/23/1858
 " " 2/23/1858 - 6/24/1858
 " " 6/24/1858 - 11/9/1858
 " " 11/9/1858 - 6/19/1859

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104 B33
 105 B34
 106 B35
 107 B36

" " 6/19/1859 - 10/14/1859
 " " 10/14/1859 - 3/27/1860
 " " 3/27/1860 - 11/16/1860
 " " 11/16/1860 - 1/1/1861

N. & S. Meridian Marks and Level Readings

12/5/1849 - 7/4/1853
 7/1853 - 4/21/1855
 4/21/1855 - 9/8/1856
 9/1856 - 2/24/1859
 2/24/1859 - 3/11/1862

108 C1
 109 C2
 110 C3
 111 C4
 112 C5

Instrumental Corrections

12/29/1863 - 10/1865

Computed AR of Polar Stars

3/11/1862 - 8/19/1863

Chronograph Record

8/22/1863 - 11/14/1864

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113 C8
 114 C9
 115 C10
 116 C11
 117 C12

6/1861 - 7/1863
 7/23/1863 - 11/4/1864

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118	C13	Chronograph Record	11/10/1864 - 9/12/1865	
119	C14	" "	9/13/1865 - 2/20/1866	
120	C12 [C15]	Misc. time observations		
121	D1	Minutes of Chronometer Exptd.	4/1849 - 2/1850 #1	*
122	E1	Meridian Circle	11/7/1859 - 5/25/1860	
123	E2	" "	5/29/1859 - 11/3/1859	
124	E3	" "	5/25/1860 - 11/13/1860	
125	E4	Declinations	12/20/1862 - 9/9/1863	
126	E5	"	9/14/1863 - 10/17/1864	
127	E6	New Transit Circle	2/17/1857 - 5/28/1858	*
128	E7	Transit Circle	1857 - 1853	
129	E8	" "	8/7/1851 - 12/4/1851	
130	F1	Moon Culminations + Transits	12/1845 - 4/1846	(Comets also)
131	F2	Comets + Meridian Transits	4/1846 - 10/1846	(Earthquake &cs)
132	F3	" " "	10/1846 - 4/16/1847	
133	F4	" " "	4/29/1847 - 2/9/1848	
134	F5	" " "	2/18/1848 - 8/1/1848	
135	F6	" " "	8/1/1849 - 2/27/1850	*
136	F7	Meridian + Prime Vertical Obs'ns	11/6/1844 - 12/12/1844	(EARLY!)
137	F8	West Transit	11/5/1851 - 12/16/1851	
138	F9	Prime Vertical	11/1854 - ?	
139	F10	Magnetic + Prime Vertical 1858		
140	F11	Terrestrial Magnetism	3/25/1858 - 6/5/1861	
141	F12a	[Chronograph	6/8/1864 - 7/21/1864]	
142	F12b	Prime Vertical Computation of Latitude	1864	
143	F13	Telegraph	7/6/1848 - 10/28/1848	
144	G1	Chronometers from July	¹⁸⁵³ 1/6/1853 - ¹⁸⁵⁵ 7/21/1855	(Annular Eclipse 5/24/54)
145	G2	"	7/1/1853 - 4/21/1855	
146	G3	Sideral + Mean Time Clocks	4/21/1855 - 1/1/1856	
147	G4	" " " "	1/1/1856 - 2/27/1857	
148	G5	" " " "	2/28/1857 - 7/2/1858	
149	G6	" " " "	7/2/1856 - 7/16/1860	
150	G7	" " " "	7/14/1860 - 9/3/1862	
151	G8	" " " "	9/16/1862 - 3/2/1866	
152	G ^a	Railroad Time Commenced	6/29/1854 - 10/1854	
153	G ^b	Trials of Pendulums + Chronometers	4/27/1857 - 2/19/1859	
154	H ^a	Vol I 517-604	11/1848 - 2/1849 - Comets + Double #s 1848	
155	H ^a	Equatorial Reductions	6/21/1860 - 1/22/1861	
156	H1	Vol I 1-80 Equatorial	10/1846 - 7/1847	

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#152
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9/24/57

157	H2	Vol I	81-168
158	H3		169-256
159	H4		257-344
160	H5		345-432
161	H6		433-516
162	H7	Vol II	1-92
163	H8		93-192
164	H10		193-292
165	H11		293-392
166	H12		393-488
167	H13		489-584
168	H14	Vol III	1-98
169	H15		99-194
170	H16		195-288
171	H17		289-388
172	H18		389-484
173	H19		485-574
174	H20		575-665
175	H21		
176	H22		
177	H23		
178	H24		
179	H25		
180	H26		
181	H27		
182	H28		
183	H29		
184	H30		
185	H31		
186	H32		
187	H33		
188	H34		
189	H35		
190	H36		
191	H37		
192	H38		
193	H39		
194	H40		
195	H41		

Equatorial

7/1847	-12/1847
12/1847	-8/1848
11/1847	-2/1848
2/1848	-9/1848
5/1848	-11/1848
2/1849	-6/1849
1/1849	-11/1849
12/1849	-4/1850
5/10/1850	-9/1/1850
9/21/1850	-2/25/1851
2/25/1851	-12/4/1851
12/4/1851	-5/18/1852
5/19/1852	-10/26/1852
10/28/1852	-3/10/1853
3/10/1853	-4/3/1854
4/4/1854	-6/13/1855
6/13/1855	-4/1/1856
4/1/1856	-2/15/1857
2/15/1857	-5/13/1857
5/13/1857	-9/1/1857
8/23/1857	-10/22/1857
10/23/1857	-12/14/1857
12/15/1857	-3/17/1858
3/18/1858	-7/13/1858
7/14/1858	-9/25/1858
9/25/1858	-11/11/1858
11/11/1858	-5/4/1859
5/4/1859	-10/26/1859
10/26/1859	-1/31/1860
1/31/1860	-3/14/1860
3/15/1860	-3/29/1860
3/30/1860	-5/2/1860
5/2/1860	-6/22/1860
6/24/1860	-7/4/1860
7/4/1860	-9/22/1860
9/26/1860	-1/30/1861
1/31/1861	-4/8/1861
4/9/1861	-5/2/1861
5/3/1861	-6/22/1861

Degeneracy ~~high~~

last obs. of W.C.B.

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196 H42
 197 H43
 198 H44
 199 H45
 200 H46
 201 H47
 202 H48
 203 H49
 204 H50
 205 H51
 206 H52
 207 H53
 208 H54
 209 H55
 210 H56
 211 K1
 212 K2
 213 K3
 214 K4
 215 K5
 216 K6
 217 K7
 218 K8
 219 K9
 220 K10
 221 K11
 222 K12
 223 K13
 224 K14
 225 K15
 226 K16
 227 K17
 228 K18
 229 K19
 230 K20
 231 K21
 232 K22
 233 K23
 234 K24

Equatorial

Zones

1-7

7-13

14-19, Bessel

20-26

27-33

34-39

40-45

46-54

55-62

65-84a

84a-88

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89-100

101-116

1-6

6-7

117-124

125-135

134-146

147-149

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6/22/1861 - 7/13/1861
 7/13/1861 - 9/12/1861
 9/16/1861 - 12/30/1861
 1/1/1862 - 4/18/1862
 4/19/1862 - 7/5/1862
 7/6/1862 - 8/19/1862
 8/19/1862 - 12/2/1862
 12/6/1862 - 4/9/1863
 4/13/1863 - 6/4/1863
 6/10/1863 - 10/1/1863
 10/5/1863 - 2/19/1864
 2/19/1863 - 3/21/1864
 3/21/1864 - 6/1/1864
 6/1864 - 3/29/1865
 4/3/1865 - 2/5/1866
 4/7/1852 - 5/4/1852
 5/4/1852 - 11/3/1852
 11/4/1852 - 12/14/1852
 12/15/1852 - 1/8/1853
 1/11/1853 - 2/11/1853
 2/12/1853 - 3/15/1853
 3/16/1853 - 4/1/1853
 4/8/1853 - 5/11/1853
 5/31/1853 - 9/8/1853
 9/27/1854 - 12/8/1854
 12/8/1854 - 2/3/1855
 2/12/1855 - 4/16/1855
 4/23/1855 - 7/17/1855
 3/30/1859 - 5/3/1859
 5/3/1859 - 5/14/1859
 5/23/1859 - 8/25/1859
 8/29/1859 - 11/26/1859
 11/26/1859 - 2/17/1860
 2/21/1860 - 11/29/1860
 11/20/1860 - 2/4/1861
 2/26/1860 - 4/8/1861
 4/8/1861 - 6/25/1861
 7/11/1861 - 10/29/1861
 9/24/1861 - 1/31/1862

See 284 for more

Catalog #'s

	235	K25	Zones	10/22/1862 - 2/10/1863	
006	236	K26	"	2/18/1862 - 5/1864	
	237	K27	"	6/23/1864 - [9/27/1864]	
	238	L1	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853	Explanation
	239	K28	Zones	10/5/1864 - 12/1/1864	
	240	L2	Reduction of Zone Observations	1853	
	241	L3	" " "	1853	
	242	L4	" " "	1853	
	243	L5	" " "	1853	
	244	L6	" " "	1853	
	245	L7	" " "		
	246	L8	" " "		
006	247	L9	[Comparisons of Zones]		
	248	L10	Reductions of Zones No Reductions	1859	
	249	L11	Reductions of Zones Comparison of Magnitudes	1859	
	250	L12	Special Zones and Magnitudes		
	251	L13	Revision of Zones. Magnitudes		
	252	M2	Reduction of Zones-I		
	253	M3	Gould's Universal Index (Catalog?)		
	254	M5	[Tables Procedures]		
	255	M6	Table of Contents of Various Books containing Records of Observ ^{ions} 1841-1855		
	256	M7	Various Memoranda [Longitude determination, mag. mean, etc.] 1844-5		
	257	M9	Catalog Stars 1854-58		
006	258	M10	Tables for Appointing Instrumental Corrections [c. 1855]		
	259	M11	Catalogue of Stars for Zones [c. 1853]		
	260	M12	Reduction of Stars in Weisse (?) from 0° to 1° N to 1853		
	261	M13	Printing of Zone Obsns 1854 + History & Description of the Obs.		
007	262	M14	Lists of persons + institutions recipients of H. Annals		
	263	M15	Meteorological 1/1/1861 - 5/1863		
	264	M16	1859-60 Comet Seeker 12/1/1859 - 9/11/1860		
	265	M17	Colorado Survey - Time 12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858		
	266	M18	" " Latitude by Polaris 12/23/1857 - 5/23/1858		
	267	M19	[Solar Observations] " 1/5/1855 - 5/2/1855		
	268	M20	[Catalog of Bright Nebulae + Clusters] 6/16/1850 - 5/1853		
	269	M21	[Comet Seeking] 6/10/1847 - 6/5/1850		
	270	M23	Books Received at the Obs. of Harv. Coll. 1862-1878		
	271	M24	Reductions of Moon Culminations 1/1849 - 5/28/1852		
	272	M25	" " " 7/1851 - 10/2/1854		
	273	M26	P. S. N. [drawings of * config's and angle] 6/16/1856 - 7/4/1856		

	274	M27	[11/15/1850 - 8/22/1851]	
	275	M28	Gould's Universal Index	
007	276	M29	Printing 1860 - 1863	
	277	M30	Memoranda for Obs. Report	1/7/1861 - 12/31/1864
	278	M31	Memoranda	1/3/1862 - 1/2/1865
	279	M32	Catalog of Books in the Phillips Library, commenced	10/9/1856
	280	M33	Chronometer - Stars	1862-5
	281	M34	Transit Catalog	
	282	M35	Eclipse of 4/25/1846 - Portland	
	283	M36	Account of Various Records + Papers belonging to the Obs	- 1866
	284	N1	Equatorial	6/9/1866 - 7/6/1866
007	285	N2	"	7/9/1866 - 7/22/1866
	286	N3	"	7/24/1866 - 8/11/1866
	287	N4	"	8/13/1866 - 8/25/1866
	288	N5	"	8/26/1866 - 9/10/1866
	289	N6	"	9/12/1866 - 10/2/1866
	290	N7	"	10/2/1866 - 10/21/1866
	291	N8	"	10/22/1866 - 1/19/1867
	292	N9	"	1/23/1867 - 4/23/1867
007	293	N10	"	4/25/1867 - 10/24/1867
	294	N11	"	10/25/1867 - 1/16/1868
	295	N12	"	1/27/1868 - 4/1/1868
	296	N13	"	4/1/1868 - 10/9/1868 [Spectra]
008	297	N14	"	10/10/1868 - 12/19/1868
	298	N15	"	12/22/1868 - 4/22/1869
	299	N16	"	4/28/1869 - 10/18/1869
	300	N17	"	10/19/1869 - 5/17/1870
	301	N18	" Miss. Olms	10/31/1871 - 11/27/1872
	302	N19	" " "	12/24/1869 - 9/2/1874
	303	N20	"	12/8/1874 - 7/11/1875
	304	N21	Asteroids	7/13/1870 - 12/21/1870
	305	N22	"	2/13/1871 - 8/10/1871
	306	N23	" (W. A. Rogers)	
	307	N24	"	
008	308	N25	Reduction of Asteroid Olms	1870
	309	N26	" " "	1870-71
	310	N27	Reduction to app. place of some stars used in	1870
	311	N28	" " " " "	
	312	N29	Reduction of Asteroid Olms	1870

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313	N30		Search for Asteroids	1870
314	N31		Equatorial - Obsns of Asteroids + comets (Copy)	
315	N32		Computation of app. places, differ. refract., Equatorial Comp 2	6/30/1866 - 4/26/1866
316	N33		Reductions of Equatorial Obsns.	10/15/1874 - 6/2/1875
317	N34	v.1	Equatorial (Copy)	4/9/1866 - 8/26/1866
318	N35	v.2	"	8/27/1866 - 10/20/1866
319	N36	v.3	"	10/21/1866 - 1/14/1867
320	N37	v.4	"	1/14/1867 - 4/26/1867
321	N38	v.5	"	4/26/1867 - 10/19/1867
322	N39	v.6	"	10/22/1867 - 2/1/1868
323	N40	v.7	"	2/3/1868 - 6/28/1868
324	N41		Catalog of Nebulae (G. M. Searle)	
325	N42		Measurement of photogr of eclipses	1869-1870
326	N43		" " "Solar"	1870
327	N44	vol I	Notes to sketches of sun by L. Trouvelot	10/30/1870 - 4/13/1873
328	N45	vol II	" " " " "	4/14/1873 - 9/30/1874
329	N46		Solar photography (W. M. Allen)	7/40/1870 - 11/30/1876
329a	N48		General record of Work	1869-1872
330	N50		Tables, etc.	1866-67
331	N51		Reduced Measures of Double Stars - E. Equatorial	1866-1867
332	O1		East Transit Observations	5/1/1866 - 9/2/1866
333	O2		" " "	9/4/1866 - 5/24/1867
334	O3		" " "	5/31/1867 - 11/5/1867
335	O4		" " "	11/9/1867 - 7/10/1868
336	O5		" " "	7/16/1868 - 10/2/1868
337	O6		" " (Time)	10/3/1868 - 8/22/1869
338	O7		" " "	8/29/1869 - 6/6/1870
339	O8		" " (Occultations)	6/12/1870 - 1/27/1871
340	O9		" " (Time)	12/1/1871 - 12/27/1871
341	O10		Chronograph Record	4/2/1866 - 7/29/1869
342	O11		East Transit (Errors)	4/17/1866 - 9/17/1867
343	O12		Longitude Campaign: Cambridge - Washington	1867
344	O13		Transit Observations 1867	6/28/1867 - 6/29/1867
345	O14		Formulae for Reduction of Transit Observations + Tables	~1867
346	[O15]		Chronograph Record	7/31/1867 - 12/19/1867
347	O16		"	12/19/1867 - 8/14/1868
348	O17		"	8/19/1868 - 7/30/1869
349	O18		"	8/13/1869 - 7/7/1870
350	O19		Record of Errors of Clocks	1866-1869

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351	[020?]	Stars to be Observed w/ East Transit	1868-1870
352	020	Second Computation of Instrument Errors	1867-1868
353	021	Longitude Computation from Coast Survey	1869
354	022	[Transit Observations]	8/24/1870 - 10/23/1870
355	023	Longitude - Field Reductions	1871
356	024	Clock Corrections	1869-1872
357	025	" "	1872-1875
358	026	" "	1875
359	027	Notes on Astron Engravings, Spanish Weather record, Phillips Fund.	
360	028	Eclipses of 1869. Reports	Beautiful volume
361	029	Personal equation observations	1871
362	P1	Magnetic Observations	8/16/1866 - 2/17/1868
363	P2	Meteorological Observations	1866
364	P3	" " (?)	1866
365	P4	Daily Journal [meteorological]	1867
366	P5	" "	1868
367	P6	" "	1869
368	P7	" "	1870
369	P8	" "	1871 ("Clayton's Octavo Diary")
370	P9	" "	1872
371	P10	" "	1873
372	P11	" "	1874
373	P12	" "	1875
374	P13	" "	1876
375	P14	" "	1877
376	P15	" "	1878
377	P16	" "	1879
378	Q1	Meteorological Record	1866, 1867, 1868
379	Q2	" " of HCO	1869
380	Q3	" " "	1870, 1871
381	Q4	" " "	1872-1877
382	Q5	" " "	1878-1879, July-Dec 1866
383		Mr J.G. Home's Original Minutes of Chronometer Expedition	1857
384		A — A — of the White Mts. of New Hampshire	1853 (N.B. Annular Eclipse is)
385		[Paris to Cambridge Telegraph]	6/20-7/12 ~1861?
386		U.S. Coast Survey, Benj Peirce, Subst: Letter book + Abstract - Long Party	1868
387		Observations and Longitude Computations	1872 (U.S. Coast Survey)
388		Longitude + latitude No. 1 (Bolivia)	1892-93
389		Time Service	4/18/1880 - 4/19/1881

	390		Meridian Circle Record - Mr. Austin	8/16/1870 - 5/13/1871
	391	Vol 1	Record of Photometric Observations - C.S. Peirce	3/6/1872 - 3/21/1872
	392	2	"	"
	393	3	"	"
	394	4	"	"
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	411	22	"	"
011	412	23	"	"
	413	24	"	"
	414	25	"	"
	415	[paper folder]	Index to books on Meridian Circle Work	1870-1886
	416		Fundamental Stars for Zones B8	3/17/1873 - 12/1/1873
	417		General Catalog. Obsns + Reductions B1	1871-72
	418		Fundamental Stars. Obsns + Reductions. Final Values B1	1870-71
	419		Mars. Mars Comparison Stars. ARIADNE Comp. Stars	1877
	420		Flexure Constants. Equator Point Corrections	1874-75
	421		Instrumental Constants 1870-71, depending on new Sulkowa Plates	
	422		Barometer. Thermometer Runs. Collimation. Flexure	1870-79
	423		Refraction Constants. B + T + S	1870-86
011	424		Obsns. w/ Meridian Circle on Zms 50° to 55°	11/16/1870 - 12/16/1870
	425		"	12/16/1870 - 3/28/1871
	426		Misc. Tables. Formulae for Zone Reductions	1870-71
	427		Misc. Obsns. Transit of Venus. Longitude Montreal - Cambridge	1883
	428		Obsns of Tempel's Comet 1873, Asteroids 1873, Periodicity of Luling Machine	1877

	429		Ruling Machine Screws; Discovery of (112) and (109) + ephemerides	
	430		Asteroid 109 - Elements & Ephemeris 1877-78	
	431		Orbit of 109, 112 1871-74	
	432		112	
	433		Planetary Positions (Heliocentric) 1750-1860	
011	434		Star? lists (Zones)	
	435		Chronograph Record 5/27/1880 - 10/5/1880	
	436	A.G.?	Absolute Work Star List - Final List of Dates of Obsns. 1879-81	John A. Dunne
	437	Rogers' Work	" " Meridian Circle Obsns. 1879-81	Anna Winloe
012	438		" " Notebook 1898-1907	Selma C. Bo
	439		Posting Book 1897-1908	
	440	A.G.	Rogers' Abs. Work - notebook 1904-1911	John A. Dunn
	441		Special Light Curves with Photometer 1895-96	
	442		[Variable Stars ~1897]	
	443		Ephemerides of Variable Stars 1896-98	
	444		Measurement of Comp. Stars for Variable w/Photometer 1895-1901	
	445		[Variable Stars] ~1897-98	
	446	I	Obsns of Variable Stars 1890-91	W ^m Maxwell Rec
	447	II	" " " 1891-	"
	448	III	" " " 1891-92	"
	449	IV	" " " 1892	"
	450	V	" " " 1892-93	"
012	451	VII	" " " 1894-95	"
	452	VI	" " " 1893-94	"
	453	VIII	" " " 1896-98	"
	454	IX	" " " 1898-1900	"
	455		" " " 1900	"
	456		Notebook of Visual Observations - SS Cyg, Nova Per 1899-1902	H.R. Colson, Jr.
	457		West Equatorial Observations 4/10/1898-5/12/1899 [SS Cyg]	
	458	R	Equatorial Work [Recond of 92 books]	
	459	R	Index - Also lists of Variables, etc.	
	460	R	Index	
013	461	R17	Rutherford Millimeter Plate Measurements, etc. 8/16/1897-7/25/1882	
	462	R18	Meteorological Observations, etc. 6/23/1880-8/20/1885	
	463	R19	Aug - Sept 1877	
	464	R20	Aug - Oct 1877	
1366. 868	465	R22	o Ceti, λ Cyg, S _____, β Persei 1838-1854	
	466	R23	1877-79	
013	467	R24	Photometer Reductions 1877	

	468	R25	Ephemerides of Saturn's and Jupiter's Satellites		
	469	R26	Errors of Circles, Misc. Obsns - W. Equatorial	1877-78	
	470	R28	Misc. Obsns. and Reductions	c 1878	
	471	R29	[Summary of Variable Stars]	1840-1862	
	472	R30	5 Photometric Observations	1877	
	473	R31	6 " "	1878	
	474	R32	c 1878		
013	475	R33	Observations + Lists	1879-81	ECP?
	476	R34	Form for Eq. Observations	1879	↓
	477	R35	Prospective Work + Proposed Form of Publication - W. Equatorial	1874-81	
	478	R43	7	1878	
	479	R44	8	1878	
	480	R45	14	1879	
	481	R46	Photometric Obsns with W. Equatorial	1878-79	
	482		" "	"	
	483		Description of Procedures + Opt. Setups		
014	484		" " + Other Obsns	1879	
	485		" " " "	1879-80	
	486		" " " "	1879	
	487		" " " "	1879-80	Planets and Planets
	488		Eclipses of Jupiter Satellites	1878-79	
	489		Eye + Photom. Estimator of Standard Magn	1881	J.R. Edmund
	490		Comet Reductions #1	1881	
	491		" " #2	1880-83	
	492	26		1881-82	
	493	28		1882	
	494		6 1/4 "	1882-83	
	495		15" (?)	1884	
	496		Comets	1882-88	
	497		"	1882-85	
	498		"	1883-87	
	499		15" (?) Equatorial	1885	
	500		Comets	1882-89	
	501		"	1882-94	
	502		"	1883-87	
015	503		"	1885-88	
	504		"	1888-89	
	505		"	1889-98	
	506		" Copies of telegrams (10)	1890	

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See KG 372
+ Interchange

507	Comets (9)	1889-90	
508	Journal (Construction of Dome, etc)	1889-91	R.W. Clifford
509	55	1890	
510	59	1891	
511	51	Begenschein + Zodiacal Light Obs's (Arequipa)	1891-92
512	11	Comets	1891-92
513	56	Journal (Arequipa) #2	1891-94
514	62		1892
515		Comets	1892-99
516		Parallax Computations #2; Comets	1891-93
517		Comets + Variable Star Obsns.	1892
518		Comets (13)	1892-97
519	67		1892-93
520	67		1893
521	68		1893-94
522	69		1894
523	70		1894
524	72		1894
525		Journal (Cambridge) #3	1893-95
526		Variable Stars	1894-95
527	73?		1894-95
528	76		1895
529		Variable Stars 6" W. Eq.	1895-98
530	77		1895
531	79		1896
532	80		1896
533	81		1896
534		Variable Stars (Arequipa)	1895-98
535			1895-98
536	85?		1896
537		Variable Stars	1895-99
538		Telescope Mechanical Notes + Golf Scores	1897-1911
539	94		1897-98
540			1898-1900
541		Variable Stars	1899
542		Variable Star Observations	1899
543		" " "	1899-1902
544		" " "	1900-1901
545	122		1901

Andrew E. Douglass

Andrew S. Douglass
Wm B. Clymer

Wm B. Clymer
~~various~~
A.J. Cannon?

A.J. Cannon I
Chas. P. Howard

A.J. Cannon II

S.I. Bailey

A.J. Cannon

129, 125 are
in KG 11366.374
and .375

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Notebook # 2

Are these
15" record books??

- 1901
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H.R. Colson

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15" inch record books?

15" record

15" Equatorial

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624	200	15" Equatorial	1918
625	201	" "	1918
626	202	" "	1918-19
627	203	" "	1919-20
628	204	" "	1920-23
629	205	" "	1926-27
630	206	" "	1928-30
631	207	" "	1934-35
632	208	" "	1935-36
633	209	" "	1936
634	210	" "	1936
635	211	" " (also 12" record)	1936-39
636	212	" "	1936-37
637	1	12-in. Equatorial	1914
638		" "	1915-16
639		" "	1916-17
640		" "	1917-18
641		" "	1919
642		[Box of Papers] II Metens (Leonids)	1919-99 Araguiba Obs.
643		12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obsns	1919-20
644		" " " " "	1920
645		" " " " "	1920-21
646		" " " " "	1921
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648		" " " " "	1921
649		" " " " "	1921-22
650		" " " " "	1922
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662		" " " " "	1927

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Number	Description	Year	Author
	12-in Equatorial - Variable Star Obs	1927-28	
	" " " " "	1928-29	
	" " " " "	1928-33	
	" " " " "	1934-35	
	" " " " "	1935-36	
1	[24" Clark Refractor?]	1905-06	Leon Campbell?
3		1907	
4		1907-08	
5		1908-09	
6		1909	
7		1909	
8		1909-10	
9		1910-11	
1	Photometric Observations	1872	C.S. Pierce
2	" "	1872	" "
3	" "	1872	" "
4	" "	1873	" "
5	" "	1873	" "
6	" "	1874	" "
7	" "	1874	" "
8	" "	1874-75	" "
	Experiments with Photometer	1872	C.S. Pierce
	η Centauri Spectral Study	1911	Leah B. Allen
1	Clusters - Spectrophotometric tracings	c 1930	Carol Jane Ange.
2	α Cyg, Vega	1930-36?	" " "
3	" "	"	" " "
4	h Per, NGC 463	"	" " "
5	Clusters	c 1932 +	" " "
6	Clusters	1934	" " "
1	Misc; Variables	1918-19	Mary ^D Applegate
2	Variables, Map of the Sky	1918-19	" "
4	Map of the Sky, Sequences for Orion Neb.	1919	" "
5	Asteroids + Novae	1919-20	" "
6	Novae + Variables	1920-21	" "
7	Map of the Sky	1920-21	" "
	Daily Journal (13" - Peru)	1889-90	S.I. Bailey
25	Double Stars; Planets	1894-96	" "
1	Misc.; Variables	1917-19	Dorothy W. Block
2	Spectrum Work	1917-19	" "

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 703 4
 704 6
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o Ceti, Nova Aql 3
 Variables
 Asteroids
 Variables
 Variable Stars + Meteors
 Variable Stars

1917-19 Dorothy W. Blee
 1918-19 " " "
 1918-19 " " "
 1919 " " "
 1903 F.E. Brasch
 1896-98 S.E. Breslin

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779 seems to be first volume here

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741	35	Variable stars	1910-11	S.E. Breslin
742	[4]	Mag. estimates	1903	[S.E.B. ?]
743		Companion Stars for Variable	1922	L.A. Brigham
744		Variable stars (?)	1919	G.R. Brooks
745	II	Variable stars	1901-02	Leon Campbell
746	III	" "	1902-03	" "
747	IV	" "	1903	" "
748	V	" "	1903-04	" "
749	VI	" "	1904	" "
750	VII	" "	1904-05	" "
751	VIII	" " - 5-in	1905-07	" "
752	IX	" " "	1907-08	" "
753	X	" " "	1908-09	" "
754	XI	" " "	1909-11	" "
755	XII	Observations w/ Phot. X on 5-in	1903-06	" "
756		" " "	1903-05	" "
757			1905	" "
758	2		1906-07	" "
759		Photometric Observations	1915	" "
760		6-in (west) equatorial	1917-24	" "
761		Memoanda on Variable Stars	1904-05	" "
762	I	8-in Polar telescope	1908-09	" "
763	II	" " "	1909-11	" "
764		Variable Star Observations	1911-12	" "
765		" " "	1912-14	" "
766		S I & 17	1911-12	" "
767		Photometer Records	1913-15	
768		Variable Star Observations	1914-15	Leon Campbell
769		Log Book - Arequipa Station of HCO	1915	
770		P # 17	1913	
771		Pyrheliometer 17 Observations	1914	
772		Estimate of Work (Arequipa)	1911	
773		Long-Period Southern Variables	1910	
774		Variables	1907-09	{ E.S. Manson H.E. Blackett K. L.
775		Long Period Southern Variable	1904-08	
776	I	" " "	1918	
777	II	Nova Aquilae No 3 (list of preceding observations)	1918	Leon Campbell
779	[I?]	Variable Star Observations	1900-01	" "
780	IV	Visual Observations	1901-02	

028	781	V	Visual Observations	1902-03	
	782	VI		1903-04	
	783	VII		1904	
	784	VIII		1904-05	
	785	IX		1905-09	
	786	X		1906-07	
	787	XI		1907-09	Annie J. Cannon
	788	101	Notes for Reading	1911-39	" " "
	789		Quest. Book	1912-35	" " "
	790		Variable Stars, Longitude Determination	1862-82	Seth C. Chandler
stored under 11366. 1080	791				Erst " "
	792		W Virginis I	1916	C.A. Chant
027	793		λ of Sp. lines in red region of stars	1926-27	C.T. Chase
	794	P.D. 1	Spectra of Novae	1926	Paul Jourd'heuil
	795	P.D. 2			
	796	[72]	Journal - lat. + long. work	1896	Andrew E. Doyle
	797		Radiometric Book I	1937-38	
	798		Radiometry II	1939-40	Emerson
	799		" " Program Bk I	1936-38	" "
	800		Galvanometry Book I	1937-38	
	801	1	Variable Stars	1890-92	W.P. Fleming
	802	2	" "	1892-94	" "
	803	3	" " ; Spectra	1892-94	" "
	804	4	" "	1893-98	" "
	805	5	" "	1894-95	" "
	806	6	" " ; Spectra	1895-99	" "
027	807	7	" "	1895-96	" "
	808	8	" "	1896	" "
	809	9	" "	1896-97	" "
	810	10	" "	1897-98	" "
	811	11	" "	1897-1902	" "
030	812	12	" "	1898-1903	" "
	813	13	" "	1898-1905	" "
	814	14	" "	1899-1905	" "
	815	15	" " ; Comp. Spectra	1903-07	" "
	816	16	" " " "	1908-10	" "
	817	17	" " ; Photometer	1905-08	" "
	818	18	Novae, Comets, Spectra	1906-11	" "
	819	19	St. Class; Misc Obsns.	1908-11	" "

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20	Hedger of LPV's	000339 - 095659	1886-87
21	"	100661 - 185905	"
22	"	190048 - 235939	"
23	Cluster and Faint Stars		1904 - 11
	Nova Persei Reductions		1902
24	Variable Stars		"
	Measurements of Bright Line Spectra		1890
2	Reductions of Photographs Observations		1886-87
3	"		1886-87
4	"		1886
5	"		1886
6	"		1886-87
7	"		-
8	"		1886-87
9	"		1886-87
11	"		1887
12	"		1887
13	"		1887
14	"		-
15	"		1887
16	"		1887
17	"		1887
18	"		1887-88
19	"		1887
20	"		1887-89
21	"		"
22	Catalog of E. Stars		
23	Description of Spectra		1887-88
24	"		1887-89
25	Catalog of E. Stars		
26	"		
27	Discordant Spectra; Remarks on Rejected Measures		
28	G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates		
29	E " " "		
30	Description of Spectra		
31	G Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates		
32	Description of Spectra		
33	C Standard Stars on Spectrum Plates		
34	Catalog of I plates		

W. P. Fleming

These may all be LUPF?

032	859	35	Reductions of Photographs Observations 1888-90	
	860	36	F + G Discordant Spectra	
	861	39	Reduction of Photographs Observations	
	862	40	Catalog of Plates Class N, H, L; Peruvian Plates ~1889	
	863	41	" " " C, D " " ~1889	
	864	42	Objects of Interest on Spectrum Plates ~1889	
	865	45	" " " " " " ~1890	
	866	97	" " So. Boche Plates 1898-1907	W.P. Fleming
	867	49	Miscellaneous (Ecl., Solar, etc.) 1890-91	
	868	50	Discussion of Draper Catalog	
	869	51	Measurement of Spectrum Plates - So. Draper Cat. 1890-92	
033	870	[52]	Description of Spectrum Measures " " " 1890-93	
	871	53	Discussion of Draper Catalog	
	872	56	" " " "	
	873	57	Catalog of Chart Plates (I-8")	
	874	58	" " " "	
	875	59	" " " (B. in Peru)	
	876	61		1892
	877	62		1892-93
	878	63		1893
	879	64		1893
	880	65		1893
	881	67		1893
	882	68		1893
	883	69		1893-94
	884	70		1894-1903
033	885		Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat. 5	
	886		Spectra class C	
	887		Description of Spectra Measures - So. Draper Cat 1894-1904	
	888	①	Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III Stars	
	889	②	" " " " " "	
	890		Stellar Parallax Stars (13")	
034	891	③	Spectra to be confirmed in cat. of III stars	
	892		Constants in South Draper Catalog	
	893		Reduction of Plates Having less than 4 Std. Stars.	
	894	(15)	Notion Draper Cat; Accounts of Share-Holders of the Camera 5/1892	
	895	81	Measures of Spect. Plates (South Draper Cat) 1903-04	
	896	82	" " " " " " 1903	
	897	83	" " " " " " 1903-04	

all W.P.F.?

see .866

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missing 1/1947

898	96	Objects of Interest - Bruce Spectrum Plates	1896-1909	
899	98	" " - Northern	1898-1911	
900	99	" " - So. Bache Plates	1907-1911	W.P. Fleming
901	1	Variables + Halley's Comet		W.S. Frank
902		Colors of 2149 Southern Stars		" "
903	1	Variables		B.P.G.
904	2	"	1912-29	"
905	3	"	1900-20	"
906	4	"	1899-1927	"
907	5	Spectrophotometry of B+O Stars		"
908	6	New Variables	1899-1919	"
909	7	Color Indices of long Period Variables		"
910	8	Spectrophotometry of B ₁ + Wolf-Rayet Stars		"
911	9	Variable Stars	1900-27	"
912		B Star Observations	1902	Maud E. Harriss
913		mc plates taken for Standard Magnitude	1908	" "
914		Measurement of Variable Stars	1908	Margaret Harwood
915		" widths of A + B Stars	1922	Marian A. Harwood
916	4	Assorted Plate measurements	1912-18	" "
917		5-in. Equatorial	1918	" "
918	1	Variable Stars	1904-06	{ Anson S. Lear Guy Hill
919		Variable Star Observations	1889-1916	E.H. ?
920		Color correction for tel. objectives	1878	Charles P. Housar
921		Assorted Plate measurements		L. Hofraeger
922		" " "	1928-30	"
923	1	Measurements of Plates, Stars, etc.	1895-98	Edward S. Ku
924	2	Reductions of Measures	1899-	" "
925	3	Notes: Photographic Instruments	1904-24	" "
926	3	Measurements: Distances, Altitudes, Plates	1901-02	" "
927	4	Assorted Plate Measurements	1902	" "
928	5	Color distance measurements	1920	" "
929	6	Schilt Photometry	1927-28	" "
930		Photographic Measurement of Light	1897	
931		Computation Book No. 2	1916	Edward S. Ku
932	1	Photographic Magnitudes, Misc	1914-18	Henriette S. Lozier
933	2	Variables, Observations	1902-03	" "
934	4	Examination of Plates	1903	" "
935	5	Variables	1903	" "
936		Phoebe	1904	" "

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937	1	Circumpolar Variables	1895-96	Henrietta S. Lewis
938	2	Variable Star Observations	1896	" "
939	3	" " " + Plate measures	1896	" "
940	4	" " " " "	1896	" "
941	5	" " " " "	1902	" "
942	6	Circumpolar Variables	1902-04	" "
943	7	Variable Star Observations	1904	" "
944	9	Miscellaneous Observations	1904-10	" "
945	13	" "	1906-16	" "
946	22	Discovery of New Variables	1907-08	" "
947	23	Comparison Stars	1906-07	" "
948	24	Observations of New Variables	1906-07	" "
949	25	" " "	1907-14	" "
950	26	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - T' plates	1907-09	" "
951	27	" " "	1908-10	" "
952	28	" Magnitudes	1909-14	" "
953	29	Std. Photog. Magnitudes - South Pole	1910-12	" "
954	30	" " "	1910	" "
955	32	" " "	1911-14	" "
956	33	Miscellaneous Journal	1911-12	" "
957	34	Miscellaneous	1911-14	" "
958	35	Objects looked up by Request	1914-18	" "
959	36	Standard Magnitudes	1914-19	" "
960	37	Miscellaneous - Comp. Stars	1914-16	" "
961	38	Catalogs (Comparison Stars)	1915-19	" "
962	39	Miscellaneous (Variables)	1915-19	" "
963	40	Discovery of New Variables	1916-20	" "
964	41	Miscellaneous (esp. Nwae)	1916-20	" "
965	43	Standard Magnitudes	1919-21	" "
966	44	Miscellaneous (Variables ^{incl. RV Sp.} 1905)	1920-21	¹⁹¹¹ " "
967	1	Miscellaneous Observations - Variables	1893-96	Evelyn F. Lewis
968	2	" " " MS	1896	" "
969	3	" " " MS	1896	" "
970	4	" " " MS	1896-97	" "
971	5	" " " MS	1897-98	" "
972	7	" " " WGen	1897-98	" "
973	15	Measures of Eros (South Pole)	1899-1902	" "
974	16	" New Sat. (Phoebe) of Saturn, Nova Sgr	1899-1906	" "
975	25	Measures of M3, etc.	1902-03	" "

	976	26	Measures of Eros	1902-04	Evelyn F. Helan
038	977	27	Search for variables; measures	1902-03	" "
	978	28	" " "	1903-04	" "
See 11366.007	979	30	" " "	1904-07	" "
	980	31 & 32	" " "	1907-09	" "
	981	33	" " "	1904-10	" "
	982	34	Scale Measures (2p. instructions of ECP)	1907-10	" "
	983	37	" " "	1911-12	" "
038	984	35	" " "	1910-12	" "
	985	36	" " "	1910-11	" "
	986	38	" " "	1912	" "
	987	39	" " "	1913-14	" "
	988	40	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	989	41	Observing Book - M5	1913	" "
039	990	42	Series Reductions	1913	" "
	991	43	" " "	1913-14	" "
	992	44	" " and M5 Variables	1914-15	" "
	993	45	" " "	1913-14	" "
	994	46	" " "	1913-15	" "
	995	47	" " "	1914-15	" "
	996	48	" " "	1914-15	" "
	997	49	" " "	1915-17	" "
	998	50	" " "	1915-17	" "
	999	51	" " "	1915-17	" "
113.66	.000	53	Measures of Variables in M15	1917	" "
	.001	52	" " "	1916-17	" "
	002	54	" " "	1917-18	" "
	003	55	" " "	1917-18	" "
039	004	56	Observing Book	1918-	" "
	005	57	" " "	1918	" "
	006	58	Long Exposure H.S. Regions + Series	1918-19	" "
	007	29	New Satellite of Saturn + N. Polar Seg.	1904-11	" "
	008	59	M Determinations - North Pole Plates	1918-19	" "
	009	60	" " " " "	1919-	" "
040	010	61	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	011	62	" " " " "	1919-20	" "
	012	63	" " " " "	1920	" "
	013	64	MF Series	1920	" "
	014	65	" " "	1920-21	" "

	015	66	MF Series	1921	Evelyn F. Island
	016	67	MC and A Plates	1921	" "
040	017	68	Large Magellanic Cloud	1921-22	" "
	018	1	MC Plates	1915-16	H.S. Locke
	019	2	" "	1915-16	" "
	020	3	" "	1916	" "
	021	4	" "	1916, 18	" "
	022	5	" "	1916-17	" "
	023	6	" "	1917	" "
	024	7	Misc. Plates (AC, etc.)	1917-18	" "
040	025	8	MC Plates	1917-18	" "
	026	9	" "	1917-18	" "
	027	10	B and MC Plates	1917-19	" "
	028	1	Observing Book	1910-19	J.C.M. → Johanna C.S. Mack
	029	2	" " (Scale Measures)	1913-18	" "
041	030	3	" " (MD Plates)	1913-19	" "
	031	5	" " (Misc. Plates)	1918-19	" "
	032	7	B Series	1919	" "
	033	8	Observing Book (B Series)	1919	" also notes M.K.?"
	034	9	" " (Misc. Measures)	1919-20	" "
	035	10	Novae? (Maps of Sky, AC Plates)	1919-20	" "
	036	1	Observing Book - Variable Stars, etc.	1912-13	Genevieve F. Matthe
	037	2	" " Scale Measures	1913	" "
	038	3	" " Series Measures	1913-16	" "
	039	4	" " Series, etc.	1914	" "
	040	5	" " Miscellaneous	1914-15	" "
	041	7	Circumpolar Variables	1914-15	" "
	042	8	" " (Est. of Mag.)	1914-15	" "
	043	9	Series Measures (principally blue plates)	1915	" "
	044	10	" " (" yellow. ")	1915-16	" "
041	045	6	Circumpolar Variables	1914-16	" "
	046	11	" " (Est. of brightness)	1915-16	" "
	047	12	" " (overflow)	1915	" "
	048	13	" "	1916	" "
	049	14	" " (Record of Obs. on Photog's)	1916	" "
042	050		Tables of Ursa Majoris	1894-96	Antonia C. Mau
missing 11/1991	051		Rotation of Primary Star + Separation of Satellites	1928-32	" "
missing 11/1991	052		Formulae for Reduction, Phases in HA & F	1918-22	" "
	053		(Loose Papers) β Lyrae + others	1933	" "

042	054	1	Obs. Book, Meas. of Variables & Standard Sq.	1912	Mollie E. O'Reilly	
	055	2	Misc. Observations, Variables, Etc.	1914-17	" "	
	056	3	Scale Meas. of Std. Regions on I series	1913-14	" "	
	057	4	Circumpolar Variables - Meas. of Comp Stars	1914	" "	
	058	5	MC Plates	1914	" "	
	059	6	Meas. of Misc. Plates	1914	" "	
	060	7	" " "	1914	" "	
	061	8	MC & Misc. Plates	1914	" "	
	062	9	" " "	1914	" "	
	063	10	" " "	1914-15	" "	
042	064	11	" " "	1914-15	" "	
	065	12	" " "	1915-17	" "	
	066	13	" " "	1915	" "	
	067	14	" " "	1915	" "	
	068	15	" " "	1915	" "	
043	069	16	" " "	1915	" "	
	070	17	" " "	1915-16	" "	
	071	18	Southern and AS plates	1915-16	" "	
	072	19	MC and Misc. Plates	1916-17	" "	
	073	20	Miscellaneous	1916-17	" "	
	074	21	Obs. Book —	1916-17	" "	
	075	22	Southern plates	1916	" "	
	076	23	Mostly southern regions	1916	" "	
	077	24	" " "	1916-17	" "	
	078	25	" " "	1917	" "	
	079	26	" " "	1917	" "	
	080	27	Miscellaneous	1917-18	" "	
	081	28	"	1917-18	" "	
	082	29	Obs. book	1918	" " Sloan	
	083	30	Scale Measures	1918	" " "	
	084	31	B series	1918	" " "	
	043	085	32	Cat. Ac. Measures	1918	" " "
		086	33	For Cat. 1° square	1918	" " "
087		34	Cat 4° square	1918	" " "	
44	088	1	8" Polar Equatorial	1910-12	Philip G. O'Reilly	
	089	2	" " "	1912-13	" "	
	090	3	" " " (Variables)	1913	" "	
	091	1	Various Plate Measures		Cecilia H. Payne	
	092	2	" " "		" "	

	093	3	Various Plate Measures	Cecilia H. Payne
	094	4	" " "	" "
044	095	5	Wavelength Calculations	" "
	096	6	Apertured MC plates	" "
	097	7	Emission Lines, Apertured Spectra	" "
	098	8	Apertured Arcturus, Vega	" "
	099	9	Microphotometer, General	" "
	100	10	Apertured Altair, Betelgeuse	" "
044	101	11	Apertured c Stars + Others	" "
	102	12	Single Spectra (Capella, Rigel, Sirius, Altair)	" "
	103	13	Apertured β Cas	" "
	104	14	General Ledgers	" "
	105	15	Line Photometry	" "
	106	16	Gaertner	" "
045	107	17	Line Photometry	" "
	108	18	Plates	" "
	109	20	Apertured Mira, α Cyg, α Per	" "
	110	22	Pleiades Background	" "
	111	24	Mira, ξ UMa Summary	" "
	112	25	K Stars	" "
	113	26	Angstrom Magnitudes	" "
	114	27	Schilt Microphotometer	" "
	115	28	C-stars	" "
	116	29	" "	" "
045	117	30	" "	" "
	118	31	B-stars	" "
	119	32	C-stars	" "
	120	35	Temperatures	" "
	121	36	Miscellaneous	" "
	122	37	Line Areas	" "
046	123	38	Long Dispersion Spectrophotometry	" "
	124	39	Line Areas	" "
	125	40	K-stars	" "
	126	42	Line Contours; O-stars	" "
	127	43	μ ϕ of C-stars	" "
	127.1	52	Identifications (Sequences)	" "
	128	56	Various Plate Measurements	(Under C.H. Payne) Madlen R. Dreyer
046	129	56	" " "	" " Mary L. Miller
	130	57	" " "	" " Helen M. Leitz

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131	58	Various Plate Measurements	(under C. H. Payne)	Jenka Mohr
132	61	Ptm. Drating, Cluster Maps, Sequences		
133		Measures by Bond Astr. Club	under C. H. Payne 1928	
134		Various Plate Measures		
135		Miscellaneous	1877	Edward C. Pickens
136		Correspondence		E. E. Barnard
137	11	Progress of Draper Catalog		
138		Miscellaneous		
139		Various Plate Measures	1890-95	
140	1	Misc. Counts for Annual Report	1899-1900	Edward C. Pickens
141	2	" " " "	1908-18	" "
142	1	Misc. Memoranda	1902-12	" "
143	2	" " " "	1888-95	" "
144		Accident Book	1905-08	" "
145	2	Notebooks		
146		Eye Estimates of Stellar Maps - Instructions	1881	J. Smith
147		Plates + Observations		
148		Measures + Miscellaneous		? Edward C. Pickens
149		Eyepiece Measurements	1877	Frank Wald
150		Financial Record + Other Computations	1906	? Edward C. Pickens
151		Eclipse Notebook	1888-1900	
152	45	Determinations of Parallax by Photoq. Means	1852	William H. Pickens
153	44	Preparations for Observing Total Eclipse	1886	" "
154		Various Essays	1878	" "
155		" "	1879	" "
156	1	Variables and Asteroids	1914-16	Susan Raymond
157	2	Eros Series Measures, Economic Scale Meas.	1916	" "
158	3	Circumpolar Variables	1916	" "
159	4	Asteroids	1911, 17	" "
160	5	Asteroids, Misc.	1917	" "
161		Misc. Observations (under H H Plashett)	1875-76	William A. Ruge
162		Plates (Nova Aquilae)	1918	Arthur R. Say
163		M-determinations		" "
164		Variable Star Observations	1909-10	L. G. Schmittz
165		Observations of Nebulae	1900	Delisle Steuart
166		Plate Measures	1923?	Rufus O. Suter
167		" "		
168		Obs. + Calc. - Ecogographical Position	1897?	Winston Lupton
169	9	Latitude + Longitude, Arequipa Station	1896?	" "

	170	1	Scale Measures - Series + Chart Plates	1917-18	Mary H. Van
	171	2	Observations of Novae	1917-18	" "
	172	3	" "	1918 -	" "
	173	4	" "	1918	" "
044	174	1	Double Star Measures	1876	Leonard Wald
	175		Correspondance	1896-97	Anna Winkler
	176		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1911-13	Ada E. Wood
	177		SS Cygni	1917	" "
	178	1	Instructions, et c.	1915	" "
	179		Observations - 6-in Telescope	1913-17	" "
	180	4	Cluster Variables	1916	" "
	181	5	" "	1917-18	" "
	182	6	" "	1919-23	" "
049	183	7	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919	" "
	184	8	Objects suspected as Novae	1919	" "
	185	9	Examination of AM and AC plates	1919-20	" "
	186	10	Objects looked up for outsiders by request	1921	" "
	187	11	New Variables	1921-22	" "
	188	12	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
	189	13	Examination of Northern Regions	1920	" "
	190	14	Examination of AM and AC plates	1920	" "
	191	15	" " " "	1920-21	" "
	192	16	Objects suspected as Novae	1921	" "
	193	17	Special Objects	1922	" "
049	194	18	Examination of Southern Regions	1922	" "
	195	19	New Variables	1922?	" "
	196	20	Special Examination of MC Plates	1922-23	" "
	197	21	Nebulae and Asteroids	1923	" "
	198	22	Cluster Variables	1923	" "
	199	23	" "	1922-23	" "
	200	24	Special Examination of MC Plates	1923	" "
	201	25	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922	" "
050	202	26	Special Examination of MC Plates	1921-24	" "
	203	27	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1925-28	" "
	204	28	" " " "	1924-25	" "
	205	29	New Variables	1924-26	" "
	206	30	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1924-25	" "
	207	31	Cluster Variable	1927	" "
	208	32	Misc. Milky Way Regions	1925	" "

	209	33	Objects looked up for outsiders	1922-24 ^{02 04?}	Ida E. Woods
	210	34	Milky Way Regions, MC+MF Plates	1926-30	" "
	211	35	Interesting Objects, Suspected Variables	1926	" "
	212	36	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1926	" "
050	213	37	" " " "	1926	" "
	214	38	" " " "	1926	" "
	215	39	New Variables	1926	" "
	216	40	Misc Milky Way Regions	1927-28	" "
	217	41	" " " "	1926	" "
	218	42	" " " "	1926	" "
051	219	44	Objects looked up for outsiders	1926	" "
	220	45	Cluster Variables	1927	" "
	221	46	Examination of Milky Way Regions	1929	" "
	222	47	Dr. Gerasimovic, T Pyx, Shapley LPV's	1927	" "
	223		Spectrophotometry, Schilt Measures	1931	G. Maulbetsch
	224		" " "	1931	"
	225		" " "	1932	"
	226	140	Variables and Misc.	1905	Oliver C. Wendt
	227		A B plates	1934	G. Maulbetsch
	228	4	Spectrophotometry	1933	"
	229		Computation of Ephemerides	1904-07	? Oliver C. Wendt
	230	1	Notes on Orion Cluster, Interiors, B stars		CHL
	231		Star Sequences	1926	
051	232		RB Standard Star Identifications		JME + MM
	233	3	Chart Plates	1898-99	Louisa D. Wells
	234	1	T Andromedae	1916	H. C. Wilson
	235		Doubtful Variable Misc. Obsn's	1904-12	
	236		Pyrheliometer Record	1916	W.
	237		" " "	1917	
052	238		Variable Star Observations	1902-03	
	239	1	" " "	1903	Marion F. Michael
	240	1	" " "	1904	G. E. W.
	241	"	Meridian Photometer	1907	S. M. P.
	242		Halley's Comet Observations	1909	
	243		Reduction of Observations for Position	1909-10	Oliver C. Wendt " L. C.
	244	3	Nova Aquilae	1918	
	245		Comparison Stars	1906-09	
052	246		Calculations - Schaefer & Others	1905, 1911	
	247	1	24-in reflector journal	1907	

see also 256

	248		Plates, Photometers	1935-36	J. E. Jones
	249	94	RH Plates - Photometry	1933	
	250		Variable Observations	1907-08	
	251		SV Tauri	1925	C. Lamovsky
052	252	1	Observations	1909	Samuel C. Catterci
	253	12	Meridian Photometer	1908	
	254	22	Jupiter Eclipses, Variable Stars	1898	
	255	23	" " " "	1899	
	256	49	New Variables	1926-28	Ida E. Wood
	257	54	Evening Cloud Record	1916-17	
	258		Shade Glasses	1902-03	C. M. Olmsted
053	259	60	Pole Plates (MC) + Misc Experiments		F. Schult
	260	62	Photometric Experiments	1929	
	261	63	Variable Star Observations, Photm.	1929	
	262	64	" " " "	1929	
	263	65	" " " "	1929	
	264	66	" " " "	1929	
	265	67	" " " "	1929	F. Schult
	266	68	" " " "	1929	"
	267	69	" " " "	1929	"
	268	71	" " " "	1929	"
	269	72	" " " "	1929	"
	270	73	" " " "	1929	"
	271	74	" " " "	1930	"
053	272	75	" " " "	1930	"
	273	76	RH plates	1930	"
	274	77	" "	1930	"
	275	78	" "	1930	"
	276	79	" "	1930	"
	277	80	" "	1930-31	"
054	278	81	" "	1931	"
	279	82	" "	1931	"
	280	83	" "	1931	"
	281	84	" "	1931-32	"
	282	85	" "	1932	"
	283	86	" " PTM	1932	"
	284	87	" " "	1932	"
054	285	88	" " "	1932	"
	286	89	" " "	1932	"

	287	90	RH Plates	PTM	RB	1932	F. Schilt
	288	91	" "	"	"	1932-33	"
	289	92	" "	"	"	1933-34	"
	290	93	" "	"	"	1933	"
054	291	95	" "	"	"	1933	"
	292	96	" "	"	"	1933-34	"
	293	97	" "	"	"	1934	"
	294	98	" "	PTM	RB	1934	"
	295	99	" "	"	"	1934	"
	296		Equatorial Observations			1877	
	297		Equator Points, Meridian Observations			1877	
	298		Telescope Observations			1878	
055	299	R45	Reduction of Photometric Observations			1878	
	300	R47	" "			1878	
	301	R48	11	Variable Star Observations, Red'n of Phot Obs.			1878
Acc 11365. 481	302	R50	12	"	"	"	1878-79
	303	R51	13	"	"	"	1879
	304	R54	15	"	"	"	1879
	305	R55	16	"	"	"	1879
	306	R91	17	"	"	"	1879-80
	307	R92	18	"	"	"	1880
	308	R93	19	"	"	"	1880
	309	R95	21	"	"	"	1880-81
	310	R96	22	"	"	"	1881
	311	R98	23	"	"	"	1881
	312	R99	24	"	"	"	1881
	313	R103	29	"	"	"	1882
055	314	R104	30	"	"	"	1882-83
	315	R107		"	"	"	1883
	316		38	"	"	"	1884
	317			"	"	"	1885
	318			"	"	"	1885-97
	319			"	"	"	1885-86
	320			"	"	"	1886-87
056	321a			"	"	"	1888
	321b			"	"	"	1888
	322a			"	"	"	1888
	322b			"	"	"	1888-89
	323			"	"	"	1889

Herschel G. Wildt

Various?
Variable Star Observations

324					1889
325	57	"	"	"	1889-90
326		"	"	"	1891
327		"	"	"	1891
328	61	"	"	"	1891-92
329		"	"	"	1893
330		"	"	"	1893
331		"	"	"	1894
332		"	"	"	1895
333	78	"	"	"	1895
334	82	"	"	"	1895
335	83	"	"	"	1896
336	84	"	"	"	1896
337	85	"	"	"	1896
338	86	"	"	"	1896
339	87	"	"	"	1897
340	88	"	"	"	1897
341	89	"	"	"	1897
342	90	"	"	"	1897
343	91	"	"	"	1897
344	92	"	"	"	1897
345	93	"	"	"	1897
346	95	"	"	"	1898
347	96	"	"	"	1898
348	97	"	"	"	1898
349	98	"	"	"	1898
350	99	"	"	"	1898
351	100	"	"	"	1898
352	101	"	"	"	1898
353	102	"	"	"	1898
354	103	"	"	"	1898
355	104	"	"	"	1899
356	105	"	"	"	1899
357	106	"	"	"	1899
358	107	"	"	"	1899
359	108	"	"	"	1899
360	109	"	"	"	1899
361	110	"	"	"	1899
362	111	"	"	"	1899

056
Sun 11365
531-533

057

See 11365
539

057

058

058
Continued in
KG 11365.545

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A24
A25
A26

Various?
Variable Star Observations

Chronograph Record, Zone Stars, 24-in
Variable Star Observations

General Catalog, Circle Readings

Polar Catalog,

General Catalog,

Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars of Zone

Maskebyne Fund. Stars, Circle Readings

Circle Readings, Zone Fundamental Stars

Fundamental Stars

Coast Survey Catalog

Fundamental Stars

1899
1900
1900
1900
1900
1900
1900
1900
1900
1900
1900-01
1877
1901
1901
1871-72
1871-72
1871-73
1872-73
1872-73
1872-73
1874-75
1874-75
1874-75
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1879-80
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402 A27
 403 A28
 404 A29
 405 A30
 406 A31
 407 A32
 408 A33
 409 A34
 410 A35
 411 A36
 412 A37
 413 A38
 414 A39
 415 A40
 416
 417 A43
 418 B1?

Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars 1880
 " " " " 1880
 " " " " 1880-81
 " " " " 1881
 " " " " 1881
 Fundamental Stars, Observations 1881
 " " " " 1881-83
 Circle Readings, Fundamental Stars 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883-84
 " " " " 1884
 " " " " Fund + Zone Stars 1884-85
 " " " " 1885
 " " " " 1885-86
 " " " " 1877

060

419
 420 B3
 421 B4
 422 B5
 423 B6
 424 B7
 425 B8
 426 B9

Observation for Inclination of Declination Wire 1878-79
 Polar Circle Readings + Observations 1879
 " " " " 1879-80
 " " " " 1880
 " " " " 1880-81
 " " " " 1881-82
 " " " " 1883-84
 " " " " 1884

061

427 1
 428 2
 429 3
 430 4
 431 5
 432 6
 433 B1
 434 B2
 435 B3
 436 B4
 437 B5
 438 B6
 439 B7
 440

Zone measurements 1882
 Revision of Equatorial Zone 1883
 " " " " 1883
 " " " " 1883
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 " " " " 1883
 Fundamental Stars for Zones 1870-71
 " " " " 1871
 " " " " 1871
 " " " " 1871
 " " " " 1872
 " " " " 1872
 " " " " 1872
 " " " " (Obsns + Reducing) 1870-71

061

WSR + AM
 (Augustus
 McConee
 ?)

	441	F11	Fundamental Stars, Observation + Reductions						
061	442	F12	" " " "						
	443	F13	" " " "						
	444	F14	General Catalog	"	"			1871-72	
	445	F15	" " " "	"	"			1871	
	446	F16	" " " "	"	"			1871-72	
062	447	F17	" " " "	"	"			1871	
	448	F18	" " " "	"	"			1871-72	
	449	F19	" " " "	"	"			1871-72	
	450	F20	" " " "	"	"			1871-72	
	451	F21	" " " "	"	"			1871-72	
	452	F22	" " " "	"	"			1872	
	453	F23	" " " "	"	"			1872	
	454	F24	" " " "	"	"				
	455	F26	Polar Catalog	"	"			1872-73	
	456	F27	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	457	F28	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	458	F29	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	459	F30	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	460	F31	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	461	F32	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	462	F33	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	463	F34	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	464	F35	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
062	465	F36	" " " "	"	"			1872-73	
	466	F37	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	467	F38	" " " "	"	"				
	468	F39	General Catalogue	"	"			1874-75	
	469	F40	" " " "	"	"				
	470	F41	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	471	F42	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
063	472	F43	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	473	F44	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	474	F45	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	475	F46	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	476	F47	" " " "	"	"			1874-75	
	478	F48	Fundamental Stars	"	"			1876-77	
	478	F49	" " " "	"	"			1876-77	
	479	F50	" " " "	"	"			1876-77	

	480	F51	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions	1876-77
063	481	F52	" " " "	1876-77
	482	F53	" " " "	1876-77
	483	F54	" " " "	1877
	484	F55	" " (2ms) "	1877
	485	F56	Maskelyne Fundamentals	1877
	486	-	Meridian Circle	1875
063	487	F57	Maskelyne Fundamentals	1877
	488	F59	Fundamental Stars	1878
	489	F60	" "	1878
	490	F61	" "	1878
	491	F62	" "	1878
	492	F63	Coast Survey Catalog	1878
064	493	F64	" " "	1878
	494	F65	" " "	1878
	495	F66	Miscellaneous Stars	1878
	496	F67	Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions	1879
	497	F68	" " " "	1879
	498	F69	" " " "	1879
	499	F70	" " " "	1879
	500	F71	" " " "	1879
	501	F72	" " " "	1879
	502	F73	" " " "	1879
	503	F74	" " " "	1879
	504	F75	" " " "	1880
	505	F76	" " " "	1880
	506	F77	" " " "	1880
	507	F78	" " " "	1880
	508	F79	" " " "	1880
064	509	F80	" " " "	1880
	510	F81	" " " "	1880
	511	F82	" " " "	1880
	512	F83	" " " "	1881
	513	F84	" " " "	1881
	514	F85	" " " "	1881
065	515	F90	" " " "	-
	516	F89	" " " "	-
	517	F88	" " " "	1881
	518	F87	" " " "	1882

065

519 F86
 520 E1
 521 E2
 522 E4
 523 E5
 524 E6
 525 E7
 526 E8
 527 E9
 528 E10

Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions
 Flexure, Collimation Errors

1882
 1879
 1879-80
 1880-81
 1881
 1881-83
 1883
 1883-84
 1884
 1885-86

Zone Chromograph Records

529 A1
 530 A2
 531 A3
 532 A4
 533 A5
 534 A6

" " "
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1870
 1870
 1871
 1871
 1871
 1871

Zone Circle Readings

535 C6'

1871

Zone Chromograph Records

536 A7
 537 A8
 538 A9
 539 A10
 540 A11

" " "
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1871
 1871-72
 1872
 1872-73
 1873

765

541 A12
 542 A13
 543 A14

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1873-74
 1874
 1874

066

544 A15
 545 A16
 546 A17
 547 A18
 548 A19
 549 A20
 550 A21
 551 A22
 552 A26
 553 A25
 554 A23

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1874
 1874-75
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 1875
 1875-76
 1876
 1876-77
 1878-79
 1877-78
 1877

66

555 B1
 556 B2
 557 B3

Polaris, Observations + Reductions

1879
 1879-80
 1880

066

066

067

missing?

067

67

558 B4
 559 B5
 560 B6
 561 B2
 562 B3
 563 C1
 564 C2
 565 C3
 566 C4
 567 C5
 568 C6
 569 C7
 570 C8
 571 C9
 572 C10
 573 C11
 574 C12
 575 C13
 576 C14
 577 C15
 578 C16
 579 C17
 580 C18
 581 C19
 582 C20
 583 C21
 584 C22
 585 C23
 586 C24
 587 C25
 588 C26
 589 C27
 590 C28
 591 C29
 592 C30
 593 C31
 594 C32
 595 C33
 596 C34

Polaris, Observations + Reductions

Zone Observations + Reductions

1880-81
 1881
 1881-83
 1883
 1883-84
 1870
 1870-71
 1871
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 1874-75
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 1875
 1875-76
 1876

067
 597 C35
 598 C36
 599 C37
 → 600 C38
 601 C39
 068
 602 C40
 603 C41
 604 C42
 605 C43
 606 C44
 607 C45
 608 C46
 609 C47
 610 C48
 611
 612 F91
 613 F92
 614 F96
 615 F97
 616 F98
 617 F99
 618 F100
 619 F101
 068
 620 F102
 621
 622
 → 623
 624
 625
 626
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 628
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 630
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 632
 633
 069
 634
 635 J20

Zone Observations + Reductions	1876	
" " "	1877	
" " "	1877	
" " "	1877	
" " "	1877	
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" " "	1877-78	
" " "	1878	
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" " "	1883	
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" " "	1884-85	
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Fundamental Stars, Observations + Reductions	1883	
" " " "	1883	
" " " "	1883-84	
" " " "	1884	
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" " " "	1885	
" " " "	1885	
" " " "	1885-86	
Polar Catalog, Observations + Reductions	1885	
" " " "	-	
Collection of Results in Order of Dates	1879-81	
Readings of the Sun	1879	
Observations of the Sun	1879	
Error of Frodsham 1327	1903-04	M. F. Michael W. W. White
" " "	1904-05	"
" " "	1905	"
" " "	1905-06	"
" " "	1906-07	J. A. Dunne + W. H.
" " "	1907-08	W. H.
" " "	1908	"
" " "	1901	J. A. Dunne
" " "	1899-1900	"
" " "	1896-98	"
" " "	1902-03	J. A. Dunne M. F. Michael
Chronograph Record	1879-	W. A. Rogers

J1
 J2
 are 11346. → 636 J3
 871 and 637 J4
 872 638 J5
 069 639 J6
 640 J7
 641 J8
 missing 1/1891 642 J9
 missing 11/1891 643 J10
 644 J11
 645 J12
 646 J13
 647 J14
 648 J15
 649 J16
 650 J17
 651 J18
 652 J19
 653 J21
 654 J22
 655 J24
 656 J25
 069 657 J26
 658 J27
 659 J28
 660 J29
 → 661 J30
 662
 663
 664
 070 665
 666
 667 T6
 668
 669 T9
 670
 671
 070 672
 673
 674 K1

Chronograph Record

"	"	1871	A. McCannell
"	"	1871	"
"	"	1872	W. A. Rogers
"	"	1872	"
"	"	1872-73	"
"	"	1873	"
"	"	1873-74	"
"	"	1874	"
"	"	1874-75	"
"	"	1875	"
"	"	1875-76	"
"	"	1876	"
"	"	1876	"
"	"	1876-77	"
"	"	1877	"
"	"	1877	"
"	"	1878-79	"
"	"	1879-80	"
"	"	1880	"
"	"	1880-81	W. V. Brown
"	"	1881	"
"	"	1881	"
"	"	1881-82	"
"	"	1883	"
"	"	1883	"
"	"	1883-84	"
Reports, Meteorological Notes		1889-94	
" " "		1886-88	
" " "		1883-85	
North Pole Reductions		1897-1901	
South Pole Reductions		1896-1902	
Variable Stars, Computations		1895, 97, 1901	
Tabulations of Observations of Variable Stars		1903	
Memoranda and Reminders		1896?	
Bright Double Stars, Working Lists			
Current Relative + Absolute Estimates, Variable Stars		1896	
Variable Stars, Computations		1899	
Ephemerides of Variable Stars		1902	
Clock Errors, Instrumental Constants		1871-72	W. A. Rogers A. McCannell

	675	K2	Clock Errors, Polar Catalog, Instrumental Constants	1872-73	
	676	K3	" " General " " "	1874-75	
	677	K4	" " " " "	1878-79	
	678	K5	" " " " "	1883	
070	679	K6	Equator Points, Corrections	1871-73	
	680	K7	" " " " Flexure, Polar Cat.	1872-73	
	681	K9	" " " " Constants	1878	
	682	K10	Equator Pt. from Olans of $\alpha + \Delta$ U Mi	1876	W.A. Rogers ± JFM
	683	K12	Copy of Instrumental Constants 1870-71; Redetermin. of $\Delta T, m, h$	1870-78	
	684	K13	Instrumental Constants depending on Pulkovo Coordinates	1871-72	
071	685	K14	" " " " " "	1872-73	
	686	K15	" " " " " "	1873-74	
	687	K16	" " " " " "	1875	
	688	K17	" " " " " "	1876	
	689	K18	" " " " " "	1877	
	690	K19	" " " " " "	1877	
	691	K20	Final Values of $\Delta T, m + \text{Req}$ for Reduction of Zone Obsns	1870-74	
	692	K21	" " " " " "	1874-78	
	693	K22	" " " n and c	1872-76	
	694	K23	" " " " " 1870-72	1876-78	
	695	K26	Meridian Circle Constants, A, Star Constants	1872	W.A. Rogers
	696	K27	Instrumental Constants, Star Constants	1876	JFM
	697	K28	Inclination of Declination Wires	1877	JFV
	698	J1	DM places for 1855 + 1875, Zone Obs'ns, Final Red'n		
	699	J2	" " " " " " " " "		
071	700	J3	" " " " " " " " "		
	701	J4	" " " " " " " " "		
	702	J5	" " " " " " " " "		
	703	J6	" " " " " " " " Supplement list	1883-85	
	704		DM list +53° +54°	1883	
	705		" " +50°, +51°, +52°		
	706	D4	Thermometer, Barometer Runs	1873	
	707	D8	" " " " "	1875	
	708	D9	" " " " "	1875-76	
072	709	D10	" " " " "	1876	
	710	R14	Planet + Satellite Observations		
	711	R17	Star Observations	1877-78	
	712	R18	" " " " "	1877-78	
	713	R27	" " " " "	1869 + before	

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714	R67		Meteorological Record	1880-82	
715		10	Notes on S.M.P.	1892	
716		12	Micrometer Level	1877	
717		17	Reduction of Observations by Schmidt by Reed		
718		33	Early lists of Gaseous Neb, Stars. Pec. Spectra	1880	
719		34	Discussion of H.A. 24, Group M.P. accord to DM		
720		35	" " " " " "		
721		38	Stars + Clusters, Lists with X Plates Entered	1899	
722			Double Stars		
723			" "		
724			Asteroid Zone Book		
725		#3	Eros Book	1893	
726		#4	" "	1876	
727			Zone stars	1870	
728	U4		Russian Transit Recordings		
729	U5		Zone Circle Readings	1870	
730	U6		" " " "		
731	U7		" " " "	1871	
732	U10		D.M. List		
733	U		Brown's Note Book	1880	
734	U		Record of work by D.B. Pratt	1883-84	D.B. Pratt
735	U14		Stars (Zone) Needing Re-examination of chronograph sheets	1871	
736	U15		Stars to be re-observed		
737	U16		Star places	1875.0	
738	U17	1	K'K d d'		
739	U18	3	" "		
740	U19		Zero stars, Red. to apparent place		
741	U20		Table for Reductions		
742	U22		Fundamental Stars, Ephemerides	1879	
743	U23		" " " "	1879	
744	U24		Working Lists, Fundamental Stars	1879	
745	U25		" " " "	1879	
746	U27		Longitude Campaign - Obs. + Red.	1872-73	
747	U28		Miscellaneous Observations	1881	
748	U30		Montreal - Cambridge Longitude Observations	1883	
749	U31		Longitude Campaign: Montreal - Cambridge	1883	
750	U34		General Catalog List		
751	U37		? (Bork)	1875	W.A. Rogers
752			Miscellaneous		

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753 U40
754 U41
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Chronograph Record
List of Polar stars w/ dates of Obs
Flexure Collimation Revers
Investigation of Circle Observations
Longitude of Circle Errors
Investigation of Circle - Discussion
" of Errors of West Circle from Stops
" of Circle
" Observations

1885
1880 W.C.
1879
1881
1884
1877-79
1871-79

→ 762

763
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Investigation of Errors of West Circle for Stops
" " " " "
" " " " "
" " " " "
Investigation of Circle Observations

1884-85
1885
1885
1885
1879

074

767
768
769
770
771
772

3
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6
9

Jupiter Ecl. + Var. Stars
" " " "
" " " "
" " " "
Various? Stars Zone P.M. XI

1900
1902
1894
1903 R.W.H.

772
773
774
775

" " " " XII
Arequipa Time Book No. 1
Chronograph Comparisons
Comparison of Waltham Clock w/ South Clock

1891-92
1892
1878
1908

776
777
778
779
780

Error of sidereal Clock
" " " "
" " " "
" " " "
Observations

J.A. Dunne
" W.W.
W.A. Rogers
W.H. + J.A. Dunne
Philip O'Beilly
" "
" "

074

781
782
783
784
785
786
787
788

Time Book
" "
" "
" "
Time service [Clock Errors?]
Clock Errors
Time service
" "

1876 W.A. Rogers
1875 " "
1874 " "
1874 " "
1874 " "
1879 " "
1878 " "
1888-90

→ 785

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787
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790
791

Time service [Clock Errors?]
Clock Errors
Time service
" "
" " 7 Russian Transit
Check Readings of Sheets of Obs. for Longitude

1879 " "
1878 " "
1888-90
1890-91 J.A. Dunne
1891 " "
1877 L. Waldo
1871 H. Gannett

075

	792	Russian Transit	1883	
	793	Time Service, Clock Errors + Russian Transit	1877	L. Waldo
075	794	" " " " " "	1877	"
	795	" " Clock Comparisons	1881	F. Waldo
	796	Level of East Transit	1877	L. Waldo
	797	Time Service	1887-88	
	798	" "	1882-83	
	799	" "	1892-94	J.A. Dunne
	800	" "	1880	Harriet Wace
	801	" " Clock Comparisons	1879-80	F. Waldo
075	802	" " " "	1878-79	L. Waldo
	803	Reference Books: Stars, Asteroids, etc. under observation		
	804	Errata in Rogers' AGC Catalogue	1904	J.A. Dunne
	805	Meridian Circle - General Record	1879-80	W.A. Rogers
	806	Constellations		
	807	Working List of Star Data	1871	
076	808	" " " " for 1880	1880-81	
	809	Constellation Data	1879-80	
	810	Reduction of Bonn Observations from 1855 to 1875		
	811	Discordant Stars		
	812	Reports on Obsn of Stars in N. Hemisphere to 9 th mag, Pulkovo	1879	
	813	Star Reduction	1890	
	814	Measure of Plates	1890	
	815	No. 2 Computations - long sheet of Bohrian + Peruvia Station	1894	
	816	Zone Observations	1883-84	
	817	No. 1 Measurements: WA Rogers Micrometer	1894-97	
	818	Sun Images	1880	
	819	Miscellaneous Notes		D.C. Baird
	820	Chronograph Sheet Readings	1884	
076	821	Computation of Residuals		
	822	Corrections for Error	1869-70	
	823	Observations of Southern Variable Stars	1899-1904	
	824	Nautical Almanac	1883	
	825	Lunar Brightness	1881	
	826	XII 12-in Horizontal Telescope records	1899	
	827	Satellite IV	1888-90	
77	828	Reductions		
	829	Bibliography		
	830	Observations + Reductions Part II	1876	

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D.C. Baird
Baird

	831		Observations + Reductions, Part III	1876	
	832		Re-readings of Chronograph sheets	1880	
077	833		Investigations of Division Errors of Circle "East"	1880-81	
	834		Chronograph Readings	1881	H. Stevens
	835		Readings of Chronograph sheets	1879	L. Waldo
	836		Star Data	1884-85	
	837		" "	1882	
	838		Star + Comet Data	1881-84	P.C. Ricketts
	839		Reductions	1880-81	S.C. Chandler
	840		Comet Data & Comparison Stars	1881	
	841		Time Service	1885-86	W.A. Rogers
077	842		Dates of Observations of Zone Stars for 1883+1884		
	843		Miscellaneous Star Observations		
	844		Star Observations		
	845		Zone Observations	1884	
	846		Fundamental Zone Stars Circle Readings	1885	
	847	J 2	Current Observations of Variable Stars	1895-96	
	848		Record of Observations	1898-99	F.W. Thorer
	849		Variable Star Observations	1899-1900	H.C. Bailey
	850		Absolute Work Runs 1879, 80, 81	1898-99	
078	851		(Variable Stars)	1883-84	
	852		West Dome 6 1/4"	1883	S.C. Chandler
	853		" " "	1883	
	854		" " "	1896-98	
	855		Wedge Zones	1887	
	856		Correction to Ephemeris - Jupiter's Satellites		
	857		Final Adopted Maps: Comp Stars for Variables	c 1901	
	858		" " " " "	c 1900	
	859		Variables + Other Stars - Naked Eye Obsns.	1889-1890	
	860		Variable Star Observations	1894-95	H.C. Bailey
	861	19	Variable Stars	1898-99	
078	862	18	Computation Book	1899-1900	
	863	17	" "	c 1902	
	864		Wedge Photometer Zone Stars	1894-	
	865		Meridian Photometry	1881-84	
	866		Multiple Theory (H.N. Russell) - Notes	1925	
	867		Notes to be Examined re. Peters' Zones	1877-78	
	868	R21	Equatorial Zones	1877	
079	869		Location of Comparison Stars for Variable	1894	

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- 877 I
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- 881 V
- 882 VI
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- 885 IX
- 886 X
- 887 XI
- 888 XII
- 889 XIII
- 890 XV [sic]
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- 904 XXVIII
- 905 XXIX
- 906 XXX
- 907 XXXI
- 908 XXXII

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Chronograph Record				1870	
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- chronometer Comparisons				1896-97	R. D. Ward
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916	<u>XL</u>	"	1749, 1750, 1751		"
917	<u>XLI</u>	"	1759, 1760, 1790		"
918	<u>XLII</u>	"	1791, 1795		"
919	<u>XLIII</u>	"	1796, 1801, 1802		"
920	<u>XLIV</u>	"	1808, 1809, 1826		"
921	<u>XLV</u>	"	1827, 1884		"
922	<u>XLVI</u>	"	1885, 1889, 1890		"
923	<u>XLVII</u>	"	1930, 1931, 1956		"
924	<u>XLVIII</u>	"	1957, 1963, 1964		"
925	<u>XLIX</u>	"	1973, 1974		"
926	<u>L</u>	"	1980, 1981, 2009		"
927	<u>LI</u>	"	2010, 2011, 2012		"
928	LII	"	2014, 2015, 2074		"
929	LIII	"	2076, 2081, 2082		"
930	LIV	"	2093, 2094, 2145		"
931	LV	"	2146, 2172		"
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933	LVII	"	2184, 2185, 2234		"
934	LVIII	"	2235, 2367, 2368		"
935	LIX	"	2374, 2375, 2377		"
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944	LXVII	"	3045, 3046, 3189		"
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	988	CXXXV	"	"	9389	9413	9414	"
See 1068 for missing volume	989	CXXXVII	"	"	9461	9492	9491	Ernestine Fuller
	990	CXXXVIII	"	"	9495	9496	9732	Martha C. Bortin
	991	CXXXIX	"	"	9733	9754	9782	"
	992	CXL	"	"	9783	9785	9786	"
	993	CXLI	"	"	9817	9818	9859	"
	994	CXLII	"	"	9860	9997	9998	"
	995	CXLIII	"	"	10030	10031	10072	Ernestine Fuller
	996	CXLIV	"	"	10073	10103	[10102]	"
	997	CXLV	"	"	10227	10228	10231	Martha C. Bortin
	998	CXLVI	"	"	10232	10263	10264	"
	999	CXLVII	"	"	10385	10386	10532	Ernestine Fuller
	1000	CXLVIII	"	"	10533	10604	10760	"
	1001	CXLIX	"	"	10692	10693	10701	Martha C. Bortin
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	1003	CLI	"	"	10737	10738	10743	"
082	1004	CLII	"	"	10746	10748	10753	"
	1005	CLIII	"	"	10761	10933	10934	Ernestine Fuller
	1006	CLIV	"	"	10605	10998	10999	"
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083	1022	CLXX	"	"	11932	11997	11998	"
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	1024	CLXXII	"	"	12028	12043	12044	"
	1025	CLXXIII	"	"	12068	12069	12075	Martha C. Bortin

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Martha C. Borton
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 Ernestine Fuller?
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 Martha C. Borton
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Plate characteristics

Neptune Plates (Princeton?)

Neptune Measures of halaude 20406

Neptune Plates

Harvard Lunar Plates

Supplementary Notes + Data

Hayn's Correction for plates of Oct 7, 1911

Harvard Lunar Plates

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Supplementary Notes

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 H. N. Russell
 H. N. Russell
 Ernestine Fuller?
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086	1071	"	Bright Meteors Reported to H. CO 1925-32				" "
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090	1075	"	Meteors, Lunar Eclipse				" "
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093	1078	"	Meteors				" "
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